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(POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL)**

ZAMANI ZO MU TAFI: AL'ADUN HAUSAWA A DUNIYAR INTANET

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SADUKARWA

Na sadukar da wannan kundi ga masu neman sanin gaskiya, da rayuwa bisa gaskiya da rikon amana, tare da wasiyya da rikon gaskiya.

CERTIFICATION

This Dissertation by Abu-Ubaida Sani (18210106015) has met the requirements for the award of the Degree of Master of Arts (Hausa Studies) of the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and is approved for its contribution to knowledge.

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GODIYA

Da sunan Allah Mai rahama Mai jinkai. Tsira da mincinSa su tabbata ga shugaban halitta manzon tsira Annabi Muhammadu da iyalansa da sahabbansa. Na gode wa Ubangiji da ya ba ni damar kammala wannan kundi cikin nasara.

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Abstract

The internet has become an indispensable aspect of human life. By the end of 2020, there were at least 44 highly visited Hausa websites with diverse contents and high online visibility that brought about the need to research "Hausa on the internet." However, this research is set to analyze Hausa culture on the internet with the view of determining ways to improve its future. The scope of the study is limited to Hausa culture within the domain of the internet. The study methodologically used interviews and online textual analysis in obtaining the research data. Platonism is adapted as a theory that guides the research, on the basis of which the research opines the existence of a physical world and an incorporeal world – the latter being the internet. It is also based on the Hausa philosophy that "zamani riga ce" (change before you have to). The research confirms Hausa websites and blogs face a lot of challenges one of which is inadequate knowledge of the language by the websites and/or blogs administrators. Individuals and authorities concerned - including agencies, departments, instructors, and researchers - should make efforts to ensure adequate representation and presentation of Hausa on the internet.

Tsakure

Tuni intanet ya zama wani bangaren rayuwar 'yan'adam. A zuwa karshen shekarar 2020, akwai a kalla manyan kafofin intanet na Hausa guda arba'in da huɗu (44). Lura da haka, ya zama dole a gudanar da nazarce-nazarce a wannan fanni. Manufar wannan bincike ita ce nazartar al'adun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet domin tantance inda aka fito, da inda aka kwana, tare da kokarin samar da matakan inganta makoma. Farfajiyar binciken ba ta wuce al'adun Hausawa da ke cikin duniyar intanet ba. An yi amfani da manyan hanyoyi biyu domin gudanar da binciken, wato hira da kwankwance kunshiyar kafafen intanet kai tsaye. An yi amfani da ra'in Pulatoriyya (Platonism) wajen gudanar da binciken inda aka dauki intanet a matsayin duniya mai zaman kanta. Sannan an yi amfani da hanyar dora aiki da ta dace da tunanin Bahaushe cewa "zamani riga ce." Binciken ya tabbatar da cewa, akwai matsaloli da dama da ke dabaibaye da kasancewar Hausa a duniyar intanet, ciki har da matsalolin da suka shafi karancin ilimin Hausar ga masu gudanar da kafafen. Daga karshe binciken ya ba da shawarwari da suka hada da kira ga waɗanda abin ya shafa, ciki har da hukumomi da malamai da manazarta, da su waiwaici al'amarin Hausa a duniyar intanet domin samar da kyakkyawan wakilci.

BABI NA DAYA

GABATARWA

1.0 Shimfida

Wannan bincike ya dauki intanet a matsayin “duniya” mai zaman kanta. A ciki (duniyar) akan tarar da duk wadansu al’amura na yau da kullum suna gudana tamkar yadda suka kasance a sananniyar duniyar mutane.¹ Wani lokaci kuwa, al’amuran na kasancewa cikin siga da salo makamanciyar yadda suke a duniyar zahiri. Akan kuma samu cudanya tsakanin al’amuran da ke wanzuwa a duniyoyin guda biyu.² Babban al’amari kuma shi ne, akan rayu kuma a mutu a duniyar intanet.

A rahoton da BBC ta fitar bayan bincike kan Fesbuk a shekarar 2016, ta bayyana kafar Fesbuk a matsayin wata babbar makabarta. Rahoton na da taken: “Yadda Facebook ya zama makekiyar makabarta.” An tabbatar da cewa, shekaru takwas

¹ A duniyar intanet akan samu daidaiƙun mutane (akawun-akawun da kafafen intanet na daidaiƙun mutane). Akan kuma samu unguwanni (zauruka da kafafen intanet na tarayya). Ana kuma samun garuruwa da kasashe. Al’amuran da ke gudana a kowane daga cikin bangarorin sun kasance tamkar a duniya ta daban wadda ta kai ta dogara da kanta. A duniyar intanet:

- i. Akan samu kasuwanci na gudana tamkar yadda ake yi a duniyar zahiri ta mutane (kasuwanni da shaguna da dillalai da makamantansu).
- ii. Ana samun zamantakewa da rayuwa mai kama da mafarki. Misali, ana iya samun tarayya tsakanin al’ummomi daga bangarorin duniya wadanda ba su taƙa kallon juna a zahiri ba.
- iii. Akan samu makarantu da azuzuwa har da dakunan karatu.
- iv. Akan samu gine-gine da wurare da sauran abubuwan amfani masu matsayi kwatankwacin na abubuwan amfanin ‘yan’adam a rayuwar zahiri.

² Daga duniyar zahiri ne ake samun damar cudanya da duniyar intanet ta hanyar na’urori. Wasu lokutan akan kai ga dawo da gudanarwar cudanyar zuwa duniyar zahiri. Misali, soyayyar duniyar intanet ta Isa Suleiman Fanshekara (ɗan Kano a Nijeriya) da Ba’amurkiya Janine Sanchez ta zama gaskiya. Don farin bayani a duba BBC, (2020: 1)² ko Abubakar, (2020: 1).

(8) kacal bayan buɗe Fesbuk, an samu masu amfani da kafar da suka mutu kimanin miliyan talatin (30,000,000). Tun a shekarar 2012, adadin masu amfani da Fesbuk da ke mutuwa a kowace rana ya kai dubu takwas (8,000) (BBC, 2016: 1). Ke nan adadin zai ci gaba da hauhawa yayin da ake samun karuwar masu amfani da kafar.

Hakifa akwai buƙatar a samu jakadu da wakilan Hausa da Hausawa a duniyar intanet, tamkar yadda ake da su a duniyar zahiri. Wannan bincike sharar fage ne da zai buɗe hanyar samar da wakilcin al'adun Hausa a duniyar ta intanet. An karkasa aikin zuwa babuka biyar kamar haka: Babi na farko ya kasance gabatarwa ga binciken. A ciki ne aka kawo dalilin bincike da manufar bincike da makasudi da tambayoyin bincike. Bayan nan babin ya zayyana farfajiyar binciken tare da dabarun da aka yi amfani da su wajen kai wa ga nasarar kammaluwarsa.

Babi na biyu kuwa ya kasance bitar ayyukan da suka gabata. Da farko an yi bitar muhimman batutuwan binciken. Daga nan sai aka gangaro kan bitar ra'i. Daga karshe kuma an yi bitar ayyukan da suke da dangantaka na kai tsaye da wannan bincike. Babi na uku ya mai da hankali ne kan duba ya zuwa bunkasar al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. A nan ne aka dubi ci gaba da al'adun suka samu a intanet ya zuwa yau. A babi na huɗu kuwa, an kawo bunkasa da kalubalen kafafen intanet na Hausa. A ciki ne aka nazarci ci gaban da kakafen intanet na Hausa suka samu. Bayan nan sai aka dubi ire-iren ci baya da kafafen ke da shi.

Babi na biyar shi ne na farshe. Ya kasance kammalawar aikin. Ya kunshi tafaitawa da sakamakon bincike da kuma shawarwari.

1.1 Dalilin Bincike

Intanet ya zo da gagarumin sauyi a bangarorin rayuwa daban-daban a fadin duniya. Da wuya a samu wani al'amari da ya yi tasiri kan rayuwar al'umma tamkar intanet. Babu wani ɓangare na rayuwar ɗan'adam wanda intanet bai taɓa ba.³

Bayan samuwar intanet, rayuwa gaba ɗaya ta karkata alkiblarta zuwa gare shi (intanet). Clement, (2020: 1) ya bayyana cewa: *"By now, a world without the internet is unimaginable."* Ma'ana: "A yanzu, ba za a iya kwatanta yadda duniya za ta kasance ba idan aka ce babu intanet." Domin tabbatar da maganar Clement, a yau an wayi gari:

- i. Kasuwanci ba zai haɓaka ya yi gawurtar a-zo-a-gani ba, sai an haɗa da intanet.
- ii. Makaranta ko cibiyar ilimi ba za ta kai kololuwa a fice ba, sai ta gwane wajen sarrafa intanet.⁴

³ Duk wani ɓangare na rayuwa da al'amuran zamantakewa da aka duba, sai an samu tasirin intanet ko dai kai tsaye, ko a kaikaice. Bayan taron watan Maris na shekarar 2010 da BBC ta shirya kan Tasirin Fasahar Intanet, ta wallafa a shafinta cewa: "Fasahar intanet fasaha ce da wasu masana ke cewa ta sauya fasalin yadda ake gudanar al'amuran rayuwa a duk fadin duniya."

⁴⁴ Yayin da makaranta ko cibiyar ilimi ke son ta yi fice a duniya, dole ta kasance ta yi amfani da intanet yadda ya kamata. A ciki za ta baje hajarta. Hakan zai sa mutane daga ko'ina a fadin duniya su ci karo da ayyukan da makarantar ko cibiyar ke gudanarwa.

- iii. Kasa ba za ta samu bunkasa da karfin ikon fada-a-ji ba, har sai ta nuna wa duniya ita ba kanwar lasa ba ce a sha'anin intanet.
- iv. Muryar malamin addini ba za ta karade duniya ba, har sai an hada da intanet.
- v. Al'adu da tadojin wata al'umma ba za su yadu a hakikanin siffofi da sigoginsu ba sai idan masu su sun auri intanet.⁵

La'akari da wadannan bayanai, abu ne mai muhimmanci a yi hobbsa wajen samar da kyakkyawan wakilcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Kamar yadda Bahaushe ke cewa: "Sai bango ya tsage kadangare ke samun mafaka." Yayin da aka nuna halin ko-in-kula game da bayyana wa duniya hakikanin al'adun Hausawa, an ba da kofa ga mutane na daban domin aikata yadda suka ga dama.

A bangare guda kuwa, an samu karuwar kafafen intanet na Hausa musamman daga wajajen shekarun 2015 zuwa yau (2020). Babban kalubalen shi ne, da dama daga cikin wadannan kafafen intanet ba Hausawa ne ke jagorantar su ba. Hausawan ma da suke jagorancin kafafen sun kasance ba masu ilimin harshe da al'adar Hausawa ba. Dangane da yawaitar rubuce-rubucen Hausa a kafar intanet musamman na labarai, wata manazarciyar kagaggun labarai ta ce:

⁵ Yayin da aka yi rashin sa'a al'umma ba ta da wakilai a kan intanet, za a samu wasu mutane na daban wadanda za su riƙa dora bayanai dangane da al'adunta. Ba dole ne su dora gaskiya ba kasancewar ba su da ilimi na hakika game da al'adun. Abdullahi, (2017) ya yi tir da bayanan da ya ci karo da su a wata kafar intanet mai suna **Maguzawa**, kasancewarsa masani a wannan bangare (An tattauna da shi a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo Sakkwato a wajajen watan Satumba, shekarar 2017).

Mu ne ya kamata mu yi wani kofari na bincike tun da wuri domin mu gano tare da tantance inganci da rashin ingancin labaran Hausa da ake dorawa a kafafen intanet. Idan ba mu yi haka ba, kafin mu farga an yi musu gagarumar illa. (Hira da Aliya Adamu a shekarar 2019)⁶

Wannan na nuna cewa, tabbas akwai bukatar gudanar da bincike a wannan ɓangaren. Dole ne binciken ya bibiyi inda aka kwana dangane da al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Hakan zai ba da haske kan irin kofari da masana da kuma cibiyoyi da sassan nazarin Hausa ya dace su yi. Ko da ma dai "Wafa a bakin mai ita ta fi dadi."

Wani dalilin gudanar da wannan bincike shi ne sha'awar mai binciken kan al'amuran da suka shafi kwamfuta da intanet. A takaice idan aka yi amfani da wannan sha'awa yadda ya kamata, sai sakamakon ya kasance wata dirka da za ta tallafi wani gefe na shigifar al'adun Hausawa. Wannan ɓangare kuwa ya shafi kare ingancin wakilcin Hausawa a duniyar intanet tare da isar da al'adun nasu wuraren da ba su kai ba.

1.2 Manufar Bincike

Manufar wannan bincike ita ce nazartar al'adun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet domin tantance inda aka fito, da inda aka kwana, tare da kofarin samar da matakan inganta makoma (makomar al'adun Hausawa a intanet).

⁶ Dr. Aliya Adamu wanda a lokacin take Shugabar Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya na Jami'ar Jahar Sakkwato, ta furta wannan batu ga Dr. Umar Bunza. Shi ya kasance dakta a ɓangaren adabi a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.

1.3 Makasudi

Domin cimma manufar wannan bincike, akwai manyan makasudai guda uku da aka zayyana. Su ne:

- i. Nazartar yanaye-yanayen al'adun Hausawa cikin duniyar intanet,
- ii. Nazartar ci gaba da kalubalen da ke dabaibaiye da kafafen intanet na Hausa, da
- iii. Nazartar hanyoyi da matakan amfani da intanet wajen bunkasawa da yayata al'adun Hausawa.

1.4 Tambayoyin Bincike

Akwai manyan tambayoyi guda uku da wannan bincike ya dukufa wajen samar da amsoshinsu. Samuwar amsoshin nasu shi zai kai ga cin nasarar makasudan da aka zayyana a sama (karkashin 1.3). Hakan kuwa shi ke tabbatar da cimma manufar wannan bincike. Tambayoyin su ne:

- i. Yaya yanaye-yanayen al'adun Hausawa suke a duniyar intanet?
- ii. Wadanne nau'ukan kalubale kafafen intanet na Hausa ke fuskanta?
- iii. Wadanne hanyoyi da matakan amfani da intanet ne za su iya taimakawa wajen ingantawa da yayata al'adun Hausawa?

1.5 Muhimmancin Bincike

Daga cikin muhimmancin wannan bincike akwai:

1. Zai zama sharar fage ga manazarta domin nazarin harshe da al'ada da adabin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Hakan zai ba da damar samar da ingantaccen wakilci a kowane ɓangare. Ana sa ran ya kasance wani abin nazari ga dalibai da malamai da manazarta domin neman bayanai da suka shafi al'adun Hausawa a intanet.
2. Ana sa ran aikin ya samar da nagartattun shawarwari kan ingantattun hanyoyin da za a bi domin yayata al'adun Hausawa. Hakan zai taimaka wajen samar da tabbatattun bayanai game da al'adun Bahaushe tare da rage yaduwar gurbatattun bayanai.⁷
3. Zai taimaka wa dalibai da malamai a darrusan da suka shafi ilimin intanet da harshe (Language and ICT).
4. Ana sa ran ya kasance wani mataki na samar da farin litattatafai da mujallu da makalu (da makamantansu) na Hausa a kan intanet. Hakan zai taimaka wajen bunkasawa da yayata al'adu har ma da harshe da adabin Hausa.
5. Zai taimaka a matsayin wani hobɓasa na sanya Hausa cikin jerin Harsunan duniya da ke gudun-ya-da-kanin-wani a duniyar intanet. Wannan kuwa ci

⁷ Har yau ana kai-komo a kan tarihin Bahaushe. "Maimakon a yi canjaras ga abu daya, sai a ga kowane bakin wuta da irin nasa hayaki." (Bunza, 2014: 1). Hakan ya biyo bayan kasancewar rubutattun bayananku fanko kan tarihin ba Hausawa ne suka samar da su ba. Idan har aka yi sakacin barin duniyar intanet ba tare da wakilan kwarai ba, babu makawa tarihi na iya maimaita kansa. Kafin a farga, gurbatattun bayanai kan Hausa da Hausawa na iya mamaye duniyar intanet.

gaba ne da zai iya kara wa harshen daukaka tare da yawaitar makaranta da manazartansa a matakin duniya.

6. Ana hasashen cewa, aikin na iya taimakawa ga muhawarar da aka daɗe ana gudanarwa dangane da *Harshen Kasa* (Harshen Hukuma) a Nijeriya.⁸ Duk wani mataki na bunkasa al'adu da harshen Hausa karin daraja ne ga harshen (kamar yadda aka yi tsokaci a farkashin lamba ta 5 da ke 1.5). Bayan haka, yana mazaunin karin ta-cewa ga muhawarar gabatar da Hausa a matsayin *Harshen Kasa*.

1.6 Farfajiyar Bincike

Wannan bincike ya takaita ne a kan al'adun Hausawa da intanet. Kadadar binciken ba ta wuce duniyar intanet ba. Ko a duniyar intanet din ba ko'ina aka duba ba. Binciken ya takaita a kafafen intanet na Hausa kawai. Dangane da sauran kafafen intanet, an yi kokarin duba al'adun Hausawa ne kawai daga cikinsu tare da nazartar irin tasirin da suka yi a kan al'adun Bahaushe. Ma'ana, an bibiyi kafafen domin ganin abin da suke fada ko suke nunawa dangane da al'adun Hausawa. An cimma nasarar hakan ta hanyar:

- i. nazartar nau'ukan rubuce-rubucen da ke kan kafafen dangane da al'adun Hausa;
- ii. nazartar hotuna da ke kan kafafen dangane da al'adun Hausawa;

⁸ An daɗe ana gudanar da muhawara a kan wannan batu. Don karin bayani ana iya duba Bamgbose, (1991) da Akindele & Adegbite, (1999) da Danladi, (2013) da Ogbonna, (2013) da Argungu, (2016) da Ashafa, (2016) da Olatuja, (2016) da Tsaure & Sani, (2016).

- iii. nazartar bidiyoyi da ke kan kafafen dangane da al'adun Hausawa; da
- iv. nazartar alamomi da ke kan kafafen dangane da al'adun Hausawa.⁹

Ba a iyakance adadin kafafen intanet da za a dubo waɗannan ba. Dalili kuwa shi ne, ya zuwa yau (2020), akwai kafafen intanet a duniya da adadinsu ya kai biliyan ɗaya da miliyan ɗari bakwai da hamsin da ɗaya da dubu talatin da ɗaya da ɗari huɗu da arba'in da bakwai (1,751,031,447) (Internet Live Stats, 2020: 1). Zaben wasu tsiraru daga cikin kafafen intanet ɗin na iya sa a tsallake wasu muhimman abubuwa da suka dace a yi magana a kansu. Hakan zai faru idan fitilar binciken ba ta haska kafafen intanet da ke ɗauke da waɗannan bayanai ba. A bangaren tasiri kuwa, za a yi fokarin binciken irin gurbin kafafen na intanet ga rayuwar Bahaushe, musamman al'adunsa.

Domin nazartar hanyoyin inganta wakilcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet kuwa, za a mayar da hankali ne kan kafafen intanet na Hausa kawai. Har zuwa lokacin da aka shimfiɗa tabarmar kudurin wannan bincike, fitattun kafafen intanet na Hausa ba su wuce arba'in da huɗu (44) ba. Su ne:

1. Abincin Hausawa: <https://abinci.com/>
2. Al'ummar Hausa: <https://www.alummarhaus.com.ng/>
3. Amsoshi:¹⁰ <https://www.amsoshi.com/>
4. Arewa Fresh: <https://www.arewafresh.com.ng/>

⁹ Alamomi da ke kan intanet wasu zane-zane ne waɗanda ba hotuna ba. Ana amfani da su domin yin ishara ko sauƙaƙa bayani.

¹⁰ Mallakin Abu-Ubaida Sani da Shehu Auwal

5. Arewa Nishadi: <https://www.arewanishadi.com/>
6. Arewa Swag: <https://www.arewaswag.com.ng/>
7. Arewarmu: <https://www.arewarmu.com.ng/>
8. Azare Online: <http://azareonline.com/>
9. Baban Sadik: <https://www.babansadik.com/>
10. Bakandamiya:¹¹ <https://www.bakandamiya.com/>
11. Batsa Post: <https://www.batsapost.com/>
12. Dandali: <http://www.dandali.com/>
13. Duniyarso: <http://duniyarso.blogspot.com/>
14. Gidan Karatu:¹² <https://www.gidankaratu.com>
15. Gidan Novels: <https://gidannovels.guidetricks.com/>
16. Gobir Mob: <https://gobirmob.com/ha/>
17. Gumel: <http://www.gumel.com/>
18. Haiman: <http://www.haiman.com.ng/>
19. Hausa Dictionary: <http://hausadictionary.com/>
20. Hausa Gett: <https://www.hausagett.com.ng/>
21. Hausa Loaded: <https://www.hausaloaded.com/>
22. Hausa Ng: <http://www.hausang.com/>
23. Hausa Online:¹³ <https://hausasonline.wordpress.com/>
24. Hausa Top: <http://www.hausatop.com/>

¹¹ Mallakin Malam Lawan Dalha

¹² Mallakin Mohammed Atabo

¹³ Mallakin Mr. Uwe Seibert

25. Hausa Trust: <https://www.hausatrust.com/>
26. Hausa Weddings: <https://hausaweddings.com/>
27. Hausawa Site: <https://www.hausawasite.com.ng/>
28. Hutu Dole:¹⁴ <https://hutudole.com/>
29. Isyaku: <https://www.isyaku.com/>
30. Jakadan Fasaha: <https://www.jakadanfasaha.com/>
31. Jaridar Hausa: <https://jaridarhaus.com/>
32. Kalubale: <https://qalubale.news.blog/>
33. Kano Online: <http://kanoonline.com/>
34. Katsina Post Hausa: <http://katsinaposthaus.com/>
35. Madubiya: <https://www.madubiya.com/>
36. Makarantar Hausa:¹⁵ <https://makarantarhaus.com/>
37. Managarciya: <https://managarciya.com/>
38. Muryar 'Yanci: <https://www.muryaryanci.com/>
39. Muryar Hausa 24: <https://www.muryarhaus24.com.ng/>
40. Rumbun Ilimi:¹⁶ <https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng/>
41. Teach Yourself Hausa: <http://www.teachyourselfhaus.com/>
42. Tsangayar Adabi: <http://tsangayaradabi.blogspot.com/>
43. WikiHausa: <https://www.wikihaus.com.ng/>

¹⁴ Mallakin Bashir Ahmed

¹⁵ Mallakin Bello Muhammad

¹⁶ Mallakin Abubakar Muhammad Tsangarwa

44. Zahra Muhammad Mahmud:

<http://zahramuhammadmahmud.blogspot.com/>

Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, akan samu wasu kafafen intanet da ke dāuke da bayanai cikin harshen Hausa bayan waɗannan. Wasu daga cikinsu ba a gina su don Hausa kai tsaye ba. A bisa wannan dalili, ba a sanya ire-iren waɗannan kafafe cikin jerin waɗanda za a nazarta ba. Wasu kafafen kuwa, mallaki ne na gidajen rediyo ko talabijin ko jaridu. Waɗannan kafafe suna da manufofi takamaimai. Yawanci sukan mayar da hankali ne kan labarai cikin rubutu da hotuna da bidiyo da odiyo.¹⁷ Wasu daga cikin waɗannan kafafe su ne:

1. Arewa24 News: <https://www.arewa24news.com/>
2. Dala FM: <https://dalafmkano.com/>
3. Freedom Radio Kano: <https://freedomradionig.com/>
4. Gidan Rediyon Amurka: <https://www.voahausa.com/>
5. Gidan Rediyon Bejin: <http://hausa.cri.cn/>
6. Gidan Rediyon Faransa: <http://ha.rfi.fr/>
7. Jaridar Aminiya: <https://aminiya.dailytrust.com.ng/>
8. Jaridar Leadership Hausa: <https://hausa.leadership.ng/>

¹⁷ Akan samu wasu shirye-shiryen na daban da suka shafi faɗakarwa da ilmantarwa da nishaɗantarwa. Misali, *Gane Mana Hanyar* (BBC), *Ra'ayi Riga* (BBC), *Afirka a Mako* (DW), *Ra'ayin Malamai* (DW), *Amsoshin Tambayoyinku* (DW), *Ciki da Gaskiya* (VOA), *Lafiya Uwar Jiki* (VOA), *Al'adunmu* (FRI) (An samu waɗannan bayanai daga hira da aka yi da Malam Aliyu Hamma, ranar 5 ga watan Maris, shekarar 2020).

Dangane da wadannan kafafen intanet na Hausa, za a mayar da hankali ne kan abin da ya shafi al'adu kawai. Hakan na nuna cewa, harshe da adabin Hausa ba sa cikin kadadar binciken. A cikin kafafen, za a yi fokarin zakulo al'adun Hausawa.

Wannan kuwa ya shafi:

- i. nazarin inda aka fito dangane da adanawa da yayata al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet;
- ii. nazarin matsayin da al'adun Hausawa suka tsinci kansu a yau cikin wadannan kafafen intanet na Hausa;
- iii. nazarin matsaloli ko barazanar da al'adun Hausa ke fuskanta a duniyar intanet; da
- iv. nazarin hanyoyi ko mata kai da za a iya inganta kafafen.

Daga cikin kafafen arba'in da huɗu (44), an zaɓi guda talatin da tara (39) a matsayin waɗanda za a gudanar da binciken a kansu. Wannan ya yi daidai da ka'idar ɗaukar samfuri na Krejcie & Morgan, (1970). A takaice, huɗu daga cikin kafafen ne kawai ba a ɗauke su a matsayin samfuri ba. An yi amfani da tsarin zaɓe na kan-mai-uwa-da-wabi (random sampling).

Kafafen da aka zaɓa su ne:

- | | |
|--------------------|------------------|
| 1. Abincin Hausawa | 5. Arewa Nishadi |
| 2. Al'ummar Hausa | 6. Arewa Swag |
| 3. Amsoshi | 7. Arewarmu |
| 4. Arewa Fresh | 8. Baban Sadik |

- | | |
|--------------------|--------------------------|
| 9. Bakandamiya | 25. Hutu Dole |
| 10. Batsa Post | 26. Jakadan Fasaha |
| 11. Dandali | 27. Jaridar Hausa |
| 12. Duniyarso | 28. Kalubale |
| 13. Gidan Novels | 29. Kano Online |
| 14. Gobir Mob | 30. Katsina Post Hausa |
| 15. Gumel | 31. Madubiya |
| 16. Haiman | 32. Makarantar Hausa |
| 17. Hausa Gett | 33. Managarciya |
| 18. Hausa Loaded | 34. Muryar 'Yanci |
| 19. Hausa Ng | 35. Rumbun Ilimi |
| 20. Hausa Online | 36. Teach Yourself Hausa |
| 21. Hausa Top | 37. Tsangayar Adabi |
| 22. Hausa Trust | 38. WikiHausa |
| 23. Hausa Weddings | 39. Zahra Muhammad Mahmu |
| 24. Hausawa Site | |

1.7 Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike

Domin samun ingantattun bayanai tare da cimma manufar binciken, an bi wasu tsararrun hanyoyin gudanar da bincike. Hanya ta farko ita ce "hira." Wannan ya kasance ta fuskoki daban-daban. Za a iya karkasa su kamar haka:

- i. An yi hira da masana al'ada da adabi da harshen Hausa domin samun bayanai da suka haskaka wa binciken hanya. Har ila yau, daga bakin masanan ne aka samu tabbacin ingancin wasu ra'ayoyi da aka kalato yayin gudanar da binciken.
- ii. An yi hira da masana ilimin intanet a mata kai daban-daban. Hakan ya taimaka wajen samun haske game da duniyar intanet tare da samun ilimi kan hanyoyin tattara bayanai mafiya inganci.
- iii. An yi hira da masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa daban-daban. Wannan ya taimaka kai tsaye wajen samun farin haske kan inda aka fito da matsayinsu a yau tare da hasashen gobensu. Har ila yau, ya taimaka wajen fahimtar kalubale da kafafen intanet na Hausa ke fuskanta. Daga nan ne kuma aka samu damar nazartar hanyoyin magance matsalolin tare da matakan inganta al'adun Hausa a duniyar ta intanet.

Hanya ta biyu da aka bi ita ce karance-karancen kundayen digiri da kamusoshi da littattafai da mujallu da makalu da jaridu. Bai tsaya a nan ba, ya shafi nazartar duk wani ma'adanin ilimi a rubuce ko cikin bidiyo ko sauti (odiyo). An cimma hakan ta hanyar ziyartar dakunan karatu da cibiyoyin nazari (musamman na nazarin Hausa). Wannan duka ya taimaka wajen samun farin haske kan batun da ake magana a kansa. Bugu da fari ya taimaka wajen haskaka wasu kalmomi da batutuwa da suka shafi binciken.

Hanya ta uku kuwa ita ce bibiya da nazartar duniyar intanet ta fuskoki daban-daban. Wannan ya hada da nazarin sigar duniyar da hada-hada da kai-komo da sauran al'amura da ke gudana cikinta. A bangare guda kuwa ya shafi bincike kan kididdigaggun al'akaluman sha'anoninta na yau da kullum. Hakan ya ba da haske a yunkurin da ake yi na nazartar al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Ya kuma ba da damar nazartar tasirin intanet din a kan al'adun Hausawa. Kai tsaye an mayar da hankali wajen:

- i. Yin amfani da injunan nema domin zakulo bayanai da suka shafi al'adun Hausawa a duniyar ta intanet. Wadannan injuna sun hada da:
 - a. AOL
 - b. Ask
 - c. Baidu
 - d. Bing
 - e. DuckDuckGo
 - f. Google (Gogul)
 - g. Internet Archive
 - h. WolframAlpha
 - i. Yandex (Yandes)
 - j. Yahoo (Yahu)

A cikinsu an fi mayar da hankali kan Gogul kasancewar ya fi tattara bayanai sama da sauran injunan. Binciken Pandey, Shukla, & Pradhan, (2015: 138-143) ya tabbatar da cewa Gogul ne ke fara zuwa koyaushe kafin sauran injunan.

- ii. An bibiyi manya kuma amintattun kafafen da suka shahara wajen samar da kididdigar alkaluma dangane da duniyar intanet (misali *Live*

*Internet Stats*¹⁸ da *Statista*¹⁹). Hakan ya taimaka wa yunkurin wannan bincike na gano tasirin intanet kan rayuwar al'ummar duniya a jimlace. Daga nan kuma an kalli wannan tasiri a kan rayuwar Hausawa wanda shi ne ya shafi makasudin binciken kai tsaye. Abubuwan da aka bincika a nan sun hada da:

- a. Adadin kafafen intanet²⁰
- b. Adadin mutanen da ke amfani da intanet
- c. Adadin kafafen intanet na Hausa da alkalumman kididdigar da ke nuna adadin Hausawa da ke amfani da su a kullum
- d. Bayanai da ke nuna tasirin intanet kan rayuwar al'umma gaba ɗaya, da kuma Hausawa a keɓance

Yayin gudanar da binciken, wadannan hanyoyi uku sun kasance cikin sigar zamantakewa ta cude-ni-in-cude-ka. Ana sa ran idan aka yi amfani da su gaba ɗaya cikin sigar da ta dace, za a kai ga nasarar cimma manufar wannan bincike. A yayin gudanar da binciken:

¹⁸ *Internet Live Stats* kafa ce ta intanet da ta shahara wajen kawo kididdigar alkaluma da suka shafi duniyar intanet. American Library Association (ALA) sun bayyana su a matsayin mafiya amincin ingancin bayanai daga cikin kafafen intanet da ke samar da kididdigar alkaluman duniyar intanet. Domin farin bayani sai a bincika <https://www.internetlivestats.com/about/>.

¹⁹ *Statista* kafar intanet ce ta binciken alkaluma wanda ke da babban ofishinta a Hamburg da ke Jamani. Tana karɓar bayanai daga hukumomi da gwamnatoci da cibiyoyin bincike daban-daban da ke faɗin duniya. Tana samar da bayanai cikin harsunan Ingilishi da Faransanci da Jamusanci da Sifaniyanci. Manyan kamfanonin duniya sama da dubu goma sha huɗu (14,000) sun aminta da ingancin bayanan da take samarwa. Daga ciki har da Google da Paypal da Adobe. Domin farin bayani ana iya duba <https://www.statista.com/>

²⁰ Adadin kafafen intanet da ke duniya na nuna yadda al'umma suka damu da harkar intanet.

1. Karance-karance da hirarraki da aka gudanar, su suka tabbatar da ingancin bayanai da aka samo daga kafafen intanet dangane da al'adun Hausawa. Ta haka ne aka iya ware ingantattun bayanai da kuma gurɓatattu kai tsaye.
2. Wasu daga cikin littattafai da mujallu da makalu da jaridu a kan intanet aka same su. Da ma dai a farkashin 1.0, an bayyana cewa akan samu dakunan karatu a duniyar intanet kwatankwacin yadda abin yake a duniyar zahiri.
3. Hirarraki kuwa a daya ɓangaren, sun ba da haske kan hanyoyin da suka fi dacewa da a bi wajen samun ingantattun bayanai da za su kai ga cimma manufar binciken. Wasu daga cikin hirarrakin kuwa an yi su ne da taimakon kafafen intanet kamar *TeamViewer* da *Zoom*.²¹

1.8 Kalmomin Fannu

Fassarori

Akwai kalmomin fannu da babu fassarorinsu na gama-gari. Ma'ana, ba a riga da an yi musu takamaimai fassarori da suka sanu a tsakanin dalibai da manazarta da masana Hausa ba. A bisa wannan dalili, binciken ya zayyano ire-iren waɗannan kalmomi ko batutuwa tare da bayyana fassarar da aka ba wa kowanne. An yi hakan domin mai karatu ko nazari ya fahimci abin da ake nufi da kowace kalma ko batu.

²¹ *TeamViewer* da *Zoom* duk suna ba da damar wani da ke zaune a wuri na daban ya iya gudanar da al'amuran kwamfutar wanda suke magana da shi (a wani wuri na daban). Misali, wanda yake Indiya na iya gudanar da al'amuran kwamfutar wani da ke zaune a Nijeriya. Ta haka zai iya shiga cikin lunguna da sakunan kwamfutar abokin hirar tasa domin nuna masa abubuwa daban-daban. Akan yi haka domin fayyace al'amuran kwamfuta da intanet masu wuyar ganewa a bayanin baki. Ma'ana, bayanai baki ba su kai a samu ilimin shiga wuraren ba tare da jagora ba.

Bottom-up: Daga kasa zuwa sama

Graph: Giraf

Incorporealism: Ra'in Boyayyiyar Gaskiya

Incorporeality: Boyayyiyar Gaskiya

Natural: Al'adar Rayuwa

Pulatonism: Pulatoriyya

Realism: Zahiriyya

Service: Sabis

Spirituality: Badiniyya

Top-down: Daga sama zuwa kasa

Takaitattun Kalmomi

BBC: British Broadcasting Company

DW: Deutsche Welle

ND: No date (Ba shekara)

RFI: Radio France Internationale

VOA: Voice of America

1.9 Nadewa

Za a iya kallon intanet a matsayin duniya mai zaman kanta. Da ma dai ra'in Pulatoriyya na da tunanin cewa gaskiya iri biyu ce (wadda ake gani da wadda ba a iya gani). Da a ce intanet zai bayyana a gan shi ciki da waje, tabbas da za a tarar yana kunshe da duk wani abin da ake da shi a duniyar zahiri. Akwai farancin ingantancen wakilci na al'adun Hausawa a wannan duniya ta intanet. Hakan kuwa ba karamin kalubale ba ne ga Hausa da Hausawa a idon duniya. A bisa haka, akwai bukatar gudanar da bincike da zai nazarci lamarin tare da gabatar da ingantattun hanyoyi da matakan tunkarar kalubalen. Hakan kuwa shi ne manufar wannan bincike.

Domin cimma manufar, an gina binciken kan makasudai guda uku. Sun shafi nazarin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet da tasirin intanet din kan al'adun Hausawa da kuma hanyoyin ingantawa da yayata al'adun a kafafen intanet. Kadadar binciken ba ta fita daga cikin da'irar al'adun Hausawa da duniyar intanet ba. Ninƙaya cikin intanet da karance-karance da hirarraki su ne dabarun da suka taimaki binciken domin haka ta cimma ruwa.

BABI NA BIYU

BITAR AYYUKAN DA SUKA GABATA

2.0 Shimfida

Bincike a game da intanet abu ne da aka dadè ana aiwatarwa. Akwai ayyuka da dama da aka gabatar dangane da intanet. Kowanne daga cikin ayyukan akwai abin da ya fi mayar da hankali zuwa gare shi. Wasu sun shafi tarihin samuwar intanet dín; wasu dangantakar intanet da rayuwa; wasu matsaloli da ci gaban intanet, wasu kuwa kafafen da ake samu a kan intanet, da dai makamantansu. A kofarin wannan bincike na duba al’adar Bahaushe a duniyar intanet, akwai bukatar bitar wasu muhimman batutuwa. Sun shafi waiwaye kan tarihin intanet kansa da bibiyar nau’ukan tasirori da yake da shi ga al’adun al’umma. Daga nan ne za a iya fahimtar irin ci gaba ko koma-baya da yake tattare da shi.

2.1 Bitar Muhimman Batutuwa

Manyan batutuwan da suka gina ruhin wannan bincike su ne “intanet” da “al’ada.” Yana da kyau a bi taliyon kalmomin biyu tare da daddagar ma’anoninsu. Daga nan ne za a iya bin diddigin dangantakar da ke tsakaninsu.

2.1.1 Intanet

Kalmar intanet bakuwa ce a fannin nazarin Hausa (Mukoshy, 2015: 19). Asalin kalmar a Ingilishi ita ce “internet.” Masana da manazarta da dama sun yi kofarin ba da ma’anar intanet. Umar ya bayyana ma’anar intanet da cewa:

Intanet kafa ce wadda ta hada bayanai daban-daban, kuma an saukaka hanyoyin amfani da wadannan bayanai yadda kowa zai iya mika hannayensa a kowane lokaci a ko'ina. (Umar, 2012: 48)

Mukoshy, (2015) ya nazarci wasu daga cikin ma'anonin intanet da masana da manazarta suka bayar.²² Daga karshe ya bayyana tasa ma'ana da cewa:

Intanet kafar sadarwa ce ta na'urorin zamani wadda ta game duk duniya. Tana ba da damar sadar da bayanai kowadanne iri, kuma zuwa ko'ina a duniya cikin dan kankanin lokaci. (Mukoshy, 2015: 20).

Da alama Mukoshy ya yi aron hannu ga Umar, (2012) wajen fitar da wannan ma'ana ta intanet. Duka ma'anonin biyu (Mukoshy da Umar) suna nuna cewa, kowa na da damar yin amfani da intanet, sannan daga kowane wuri.

Hakika wadannan ma'anoni sun ba da haske kan ma'anar intanet. Duk da haka, akwai muhimmin al'amari da ya kamata bayani kan intanet ya kunsu. Wannan kuwa shi ne nuna bagire ko farfajiyar wannan kafar sadarwa wanda ta kasance bisa hanyoyin iska wadanda ba a iya ganin su. Tun a shekarar 2010 Amfani ya kawo wannan cikin ma'anar da ya bayar inda yake cewa:

Intanet tsari ne da ya hada duniya, ta hadakar layin iska na kwamfutoci wadanda ke amfani da tsare-tsaren yanar gizo don biya wa biliyoyin masu amfani bukatu a fadin duniya. (Amfani, 2010 a cikin Umar, 2012: 48).

Yayin da aka nazarci wadannan ma'anoni da ma makamantansu, za a tarar da cewa akwai muhimman abubuwan da suka taru suka samar da kafar intanet. Za a iya kallon su a matsayin siffofin intanet. Ko ma wace ma'ana ce ta fi kwanciya ga rayin manazarci, yana da kyau a fahimci cewa:

²² Sun hada da ma'anonin da suka fito daga Almajir, (2008) da Muhammad, (2011) da Umar, (2012).

- a. Intanet al'amari ne da ya samu a zamanance.
- b. Intanet ya kasance al'amari mai faɗi da ban mamaki. Yana kunshe da dukkanin wasu fannoni da ake samu a duniyar rayuwar yau da kullum.
- c. Intanet ba ya gudanawa sai da taimakon na'urori masu kwakwalwa (nau'ukan kwamfuta daban-daban).²³
- d. Hulɗayyar intanet abu ce wadda ba a gani, amma ana kallon sakamakonta ta fuskokin kwamfutoci.
- e. Intanet na da yaruka daban-daban. Yayin da aka tura saƙo bisa intanet, sai ya fassaru cikin yaren da intanet ke ganewa. Daga nan kuma sai ya sake fassaruwa zuwa yare ko sigar da masu neman sakamakon ke iya fahimta.
- f. Babu wani al'amari na intanet da ke da damar yin kansa. Komai aka gani a duniyar, to an yi shi ne. Duk da haka, ana iya ba wa wani al'amari a duniyar intanet damar maimaita kansa ko sarrafa kansa zuwa wasu sigogi mabambanta.
- g. Intanet al'amari ne da ya jawo nesa kusa,²⁴ ya mayar da abu mai yawa ya zama kaɗan,²⁵ ya mayar da abu kaɗan ya zama mai yawa,²⁶ sannan ya tsuke faɗin duniya.

²³ Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, kwamfuta na zuwa cikin sigogi da dama. Wayoyin hannu na shiga cikin jerin nau'ukan kwamfutoci da ake da su.

²⁴ Misali, wanda yake zaune a kasar Hausa zai iya yin magana da wanda yake birnin Sin yayin da suke kallon juna. Zai kuma iya taya shi wani aiki da yake gudanarwa a kan intanet a wannan lokaci.

²⁵ Misali, kafar intanet guda za ta iya ɗaukar dubban miliyoyin manyan littattafai waɗanda idan ɗakin karatu za a gina domin adana su, abin sai wanda ya gani.

²⁶ Idan za a ba da wata sanarwa ta amfani da jarida ko wasifa, ana bukatar buga takardu masu matuƙar yawa domin rarrabawa ko lillikawa a wurare domin amfanin jama'a. Ta hanyar amfani da intanet, rubutu guda yana biya wannan bukata ba tare da an yi ta maimaitawa ba.

- h. Intanet hadaka ce ta tsauraran al'amura daban-daban. Sun hada da yarukan intanet da gine-ginenta da hanyoyin shigarta da *service ko network* wanda shi ke ba da damar kai wa gare ta.

Lura da wadannan, ba da kammalalliyar ma'anar intanet da za ta bayyana dukkanin siffofinsa aiki ne ja. Duk da haka, ta bin sawun zaren tunanin magabata wajen ba da ma'anar intanet, za a iya cewa:

Intanet fasaha ce ta zamani wadda ta funshi hadakar tsauraran al'amura da suka hada da yaruka da na'urori da sabis wadanda haduwarsu ke samar da al'amari ko bagire da ke tattare da al'amura da fannoni tamkar wadanda ke duniyar yau-da-kullum, ciki har da abubuwan da suka shafi sadarwa da makarantu da bankuna tare da sauran halittu kamar mutane da waninsu.

2.1.1.1 Duniyar Intanet Jiya da Yau

An gudanar da rubuce-rubuce masu tarin yawa dangane da tarihin samuwar intanet da bunkasarsa.²⁷ Kawo tarihin tiryen-tiryen zai kasance tamkar maimaici ne ga ayyukan baya kawai ba tare da gabato da sabon al'amari ba. A bisa haka, wannan bincike zai fi mayar da hankali wajen zakulo sauye-sauye da ci gaba da aka samu a harkar intanet tun bayan kirfirarsa.

Bincike da dama da suka gabata sun danganta tarihin intanet da yunkurin wata hukumar tsaro da ke Amurka. Gerf, (2004: 1360) ya bayyana cewa, a shekarun

²⁷ Rubuce-rubuce da aka yi kan tarihin intanet sun hada da Leiner, et al (1997) da Romualdo & Alessandro (2007) da Kleinrock, (2010) da Mukoshy, (2015) da Press, (2015) da Strickland, (2020).

1970s ne aka samu hobɓasa na kafar intanet ta farko mai suna *ARPANET*. Wannan bayani ya yi daidai da wanda Mukoshy, (2015: 21) ya rawaito daga Deitel da Deitel, (2009). Mukoshy ya yi karin bayani da cewa, kafar intanet ta ARFA ta samu ne bayan hukumar da aka fi sani da *The Advanced Research Project Agency (ARPA)* ta gudanar da taro a shekarar 1969. Wannan hukumar ta kasance farkashin *Department of Defense in United States*.

A binciken da Romualdo & Alessandro (2007: 2) suka gabatar, sun tabbatar da cewa intanet a wancan lokaci ya shafi haɗaka ta kai tsaye ne daga kwamfuta zuwa kwamfuta. A farko-farkon al'amarin intanet, akwai manyan mata kai huɗu na ci gaba da aka samu. Romualdo & Alessandro, (2007: 2) sun bayyana su kamar haka:

a. Linear (Sambai)

Wannan shi ne tsarin intanet na farko. Dukkanin kwamfutocin da ke haɗe da intanet ɗin suna kan layi guda ne. Saƙo na tashi daga kwamfuta ta farko zuwa ta biyu sannan ta uku, har karshe. Misali, saƙo da ya tashi daga "A" sai ya je "B", ya je "C", ya je "D" sannan ya je "E." A irin wannan tsari, yayin da aka katse kwamfuta guda daga kan layi, to tamkar an katse sauran ne. Misali, idan aka katse "C", to "D" da "E" ba za su iya karɓar saƙo ba. Ga misali cikin hoton da ke kasa:

Hoto 2.1: Tsarin Intanet Mai Bin Sambai

Madogara: Romualdo & Alessandro, (2007: 3)

b. Ring (Zobe)

Ci gaba da aka samu ya sa aka fito da tsarin intanet Maizobe. A wannan tsari, saƙo na zagayawa ne cikin wani tsari na da'ira. Saƙo daga kowace kwamfuta na iya zuwa sauran kwamfutoci. Duk da haka, idan kwamfutar ba ita ke gefen wadda ta tura saƙo ba a kan intanet, to sai saƙon ya bi cikin kwamfutocin da ke tsakani a cikin jerin kwamfutocin kafin ya isa zuwa kwamfutar da za ta karɓi saƙon. Ga misali cikin hoton da ke fasa:

Hoto 2.2: Tsarin Intanet Maizobe

Madogara: Romualdo & Alessandro, (2007: 3)

c. Star (Tauraro)

Bunkasar al'amuran intanet ya kai ga samun ci gaba zuwa tsarin hadakar kwamfutoci cikin sigar tauraro. A wannan tsari, babbar kwamfuta da ta haɗa sauran kwamfutoci takan kasance a tsakiya. Saƙon da ya tashi daga gare ta yana isa ga dukkanin sauran kwamfutoci. Idan wata kwamfuta za ta tura saƙo ga 'yar uwarta, dole sai saƙon ya iso cikin wannan babbar kwamfuta. Daga nan ne saƙon zai iya kaiwa ga kwamfutar da aka aika shi.

Hoto 2.3: Tsarin Intanet Mai Zubin Tauraro

Madogara: Basu, (2019: 1)

d. Mesh (Jigida)

Ci gaba da aka sake samu a sha'anin intanet ya samar da sabon salon hadakar kwamfutoci. A wannan tsari, kwamfutoci sukan kasance a sarke. Kwamfuta guda na da damar isar da sako kai tsaye zuwa kwamfutoci biyu ko ma sama da haka. Abin lura a nan shi ne, kwamfuta na da damar isar da sako ne kawai ga kwamfutocin da aka riga da aka samar da hanyar isar da sako tsakaninsu. Hoton da ke kasa na dauke da farin bayani dangane da wannan tsari.

Hoto 2.4: Tsarin Intanet Mai Zubin Jigida

Madogara: Keary, (2021: 1)

A zuwa yau, tsarin intanet ya samu bunkasa da ya wuce dukkanin wadannan mataakai. A yau, kwamfutoci suna haɗe ne cikin wani tsari mai sarkakiyar gaske. Kowace kwamfuta na iya haɗuwa da ‘yar uwarta tare da tura mata saƙo kai tsaye. Misali, “A” na haɗe da “B” da “C.” “B” na haɗe da “A” da “C.” “C” na haɗe da “A” da “B.” A takaice, ba a buƙatar saƙo ya bi ta cikin wata kwamfuta kafin ya kai ga wata.²⁸

Akwai nau’ukan sabis ɗin intanet daban-daban. Masana na samar da rabe-raben intanet ne ta la’akari da faɗin wurin da sabis ɗin intanet ɗin ke kaiwa.²⁹ Fitattu daga cikin ire-iren intanet su ne:

1. PAN (Personal Area Network) - Keɓantaccen Sabis Ɗin Intanet

Wannan shi ne nau’in sabis ɗin intanet da ya shafi wuri guda kawai. Yawanci ana samar da wannan nau’in sabis ne domin amfanin mutum ɗaya. Sau da dama sabis ɗin ba ya wuce faɗin mita goma (10). Misali, idan mutum ya tura bidiyo ko hoto daga kwamfuta zuwa wayarsa ko daga waya zuwa kwamfuta, to ya yi amfani ne da irin wannan nau’in sabis. Haka ma mutum na iya kunna sabis ɗin wayarsa na hawa intanet domin ya ba wa kwamfutoci ko wayoyi sabis. Duk ire-iren wadannan ana kiran su da suna *PAN*.

²⁸ Duk da haka, akan yi wannan tsari musamman yayin da ake buƙatar tara saƙonni da tace su a wani mataki kafin a wuce da su zuwa sauran kwamfutoci.

²⁹ Masana da suka yi aiki game da nau’ukan intanet sun haɗa da Bourgeois, (2016) da Dornal, (2021).

2. LAN (Local Area Network) - Sabis Din Karamin Wuri

Wannan nau'in sabis ne da ya shafi ma'aikatu ko gidaje ko masana'antu. Za a iya samun ma'aikata mai kwamfutoci kamar guda goma (10) amma dukkanninsu suna amfani da sabis guda ne. Bayan haka, kwaƙwalen kwamfutocin na iya kasancewa a haɗe wuri guda. Wannan zai sa duk sauyin da aka yi a kwamfuta guda ya kasance ya shafi sauran kwamfutocin. Bayan haka, akan samu babban ofishi a ma'aikata da ke ɗauke da kwamfutoci da yawa a ciki. Ana iya tsara yadda dukkannin kwamfutocin za su rika tura takardun da za a gurza (printing) zuwa na'urar gurza takardu (printer) guda. Sabis ɗin da ya haɗa kwamfutocin shi ake kira LAN. PAN daban-daban ne ke haɗuwa su ba da LAN.

3. MAN (Metropolitan Area Network) - Sabis Din Yanki

Wannan nau'in sabis ne da ke karadɛ wani yanki. Nau'in sabis ɗin da ake samu a manyan jami'o'i da ke da gine-gine da dama na iya kasancewa MAN. Bayan haka, ana iya samun wata ma'aikata da ke da gine-gine ko ofisoshi a wurare daban-daban a cikin gari guda ko garuruwa da ke kusa da juna. Idan haka ta faru, ana iya amfani da sabis ɗin MAN domin takaita adadin kuɗi da ma'aikatar za ta rika kashewa ga sabis. PAN daban-daban ne ke haɗuwa su ba da LAN. Su kuma LAN sai su haɗu su ba da MAN.

4. WAN (Wide Area Network) - Sabis Na Dogon Zango

Wannan nau'in sabis ne da yake mamaye dogon zango. Yana kasancewa tsakanin gari da gari ko ma fasa da fasa. Misali, a Nijeriya akwai bankuna

da babu wata jaha da ba su da cibiya. Akwai nau'ukan sabis-sabis da dukkannin cibiyoyin da ke jahohin suke amfani da su a tare. Manyan kamfanonin fassara suna da tsari makamancin wannan. Misali, kamfanonin fassara da ke da ma'aikata da dama, sukan yi amfani da tsarin sabis guda. Ko a bangaren raba fayilolin fassara za a iya kallon wannan. Idan akwai fayiloli 20, za su kasance a kwamfutocin dukkannin ma'aikatan. Sannan kowannensu zai rika kallon fayil da aka riga aka yi aiki a kansa.³⁰ Yayin da PAN suka haɗu suka ba da LAN, su kuma LAN za su haɗu su ba da MAN. MAN kuwa su ke haɗuwa su ba da WAN.

Bullar kafafen intanet ya samar da wani sabon al'amari a duniyar intanet. Kafar intanet wani gida ne ko farfajiya ko rumbu da ake kirƙira. A cikinsa ne ake ajiye bayanai iri-iri. Za a rika bin wasu tsararrun hanyoyi wajen kai wa ga wannan gida tare da ta'ammuli da kayayyakin da ke cikinsa.³¹ Binciken Armstrong, (2019: 1) ya tabbatar da cewa, an kirƙiri kafar intanet na farko ne a shekarar 1991. Daga wannan lokaci aka ci gaba da samun bullowar kafafen intanet da bunkasarsu. Ya zuwa shekarar 2016, kafafen intanet sun kai biliyan guda. Giraf da ke kasa na dauke da farin bayani.

³⁰ Domin farin bincike game da nau'ukan haɗakar sabis din intanet, ana iya ziyartar <https://www.javatpoint.com/types-of-computer-network> ko <https://www.router-switch.com/faq/types-of-networks.html> ko <https://www.belden.com/blogs/network-types> ko <https://afteracademy.com/blog/What-are-the-different-types-of-network>.

³¹ Domin farin bayani dangane da kafafen intanet, ana iya duba Armstrong, (2019).

Giraf 2.1: Adadin Kafafen Intanet a Duniya

Madogara: Armstrong, (2019: 1)

A giraf na 2.1 da ke sama, za a ga tarihin samuwar kafafen intanet a takaice. A shekarar 1991 kafar intanet guda ɗaya aka samu. A 1992 adadinsu ya kai goma. A wajajen 2016, wannan adadi ya kai biliyan guda. Bayan haka, giraf din ya nuna shekarun da aka samar da wasu muhimman kafafen intanet. Sun kasance:

- a. Yahoo (Yahu) a shekarar 1994
- b. Google (Gogul) a shekarar 1998
- c. Facebook (Fesbuk) a shekarar 2004
- d. YouTube (Yutub) a shekarar 2005
- e. Instagram (Insitagiram) a shekarar 2010

2.1.1.2 Intanet a Kadadar Hausa da Hausawa

Daya daga cikin manyan tagomashin da Hausa ta samu shi ne yawan bincike da ake gudanarwa a kanta a mata kai daban-daban.³² Ba a kasar Hausa kawai ba, an fara koyar da Hausa a kasashen ketare/Turai tun a shekarun 1885 (Sani & Umar, 2018: 24). Daukakar Hausa da yawan al'ummarta sun sa a yau tana da gurbi a duniyar intanet. Akwai manyan gidajen rediyo a matakin duniya da ke yada labarai cikin harshen Hausa. Bugu da kari, sai aka yi dace suna da kafafen intanet. A nan ma, sukan samar da rubuce-rubuce da hotuna da bidiyoyi da suka shafi Hausa da Hausawa, waɗanda kuma ake rubutawa cikin harshen Hausa. An kawo misalan waɗannan kafafe a farkashin 1.6 da ke baki na ɗaya.

Wani muhimmin al'amari shi ne, ya zuwa yau, akwai kafafen intanet na Hausa da dama.³³ Waɗannan kafafe suna ɗauke da bayanai game da Hausa da Hausawa. Misali, babban makasudin kafar intanet ɗin nan ta Hausa mai suna *Abincin Hausawa* (<https://abinci.com/>) shi ne kawo bayanai kan nau'ukan abincin Hausawa. Abinci kuwa na daga cikin al'adun fasahar hannu (material culture) (Maikwari, 2020: 31-32). Ita kuwa kafar Amsoshi (<https://www.amsoshi.com/>), ta kasance gama-gari inda ta kunshi bangarorin al'ada da adabi da harshe. A takaice, samuwar kafafen intanet na Hausa da suka kai adadi mai yawa (har kimanin 44) na nuna matsayinta da yadurwarta a duniyar intanet.

³² Domin samun farin bayani dangane da Hausa da Hausawa ana iya duba Funiss, (1996) da Philip, (2001) da Bunza, (2008) da Abdullahi, (2008) da Gobir, (2012) da Sani & Umar, (2018) da Gobir & Sani, (2019) da Bunza, (2019).

³³ An lissafo kafafen intanet na Hausa guda arba'in da hudi (44) a farkashin 1.6.

Bunkasar Hausa a duniyar intanet ya kai wani mataki yayin da ta samu shiga cikin jerin harsunan da ake amfani da su a kafar Fesbuk. “Yanzu haka masu amfani da shafin da dama suna yi ne ta hanyar amfani da harshen Hausa a matsayin harshen umurni” (Morison a cikin ‘Yartsakuwa, 2017: 26). Masu amfani da Fesbuk na da damar mayar da saitin akawun dinsu cikin harshen Hausa. Bayan haka, kamfanin Fesbuk na ba da dubban daruruwan rubuce-rubuce da aka yi a kan Fesbuk domin a fassara su zuwa harshen Hausa. Duk wani rubutu da aka yi kan Fesbuk cikin wasu harsuna daban, mutum na da damar duba fassarorinsu cikin harshen Hausa. Idan ya kasance ba a fassara su zuwa Hausa ba a daidai lokacin da aka duba, injin din Fesbuk zai yi fofarin fassara su ta hanyar amfani da ilimin makamantan fassarori da suka gabata.

Hoto 2.5: Tsarin Fesbuk Cikin Harshen Hausa

Madogara: Akawun Din Abdulrahman Muhammad Manga na Fesbuk

A hoto na 2.5 da ke sama, za a ga cewa akawun din Fesbuk din cikin harshen Hausa yake. Dukkanin ɓangarorin akawun din an sanya sunayensu ne cikin harshen Hausa. Hakika wannan ci gaba ne sosai ga harshen. Yayin da aka bincika jerin harsunan da ake iya amfani da su a kan Fesbuk, za a tarar da cewa ba su kai ɗari da hamsin (150) ba (har ya zuwa ranar 24 ga watan Maris na shekarar 2020). Kada a manta cewa, harsunan duniya ba su gaza dubu bakwai (7,000) ba (Bunza, 2019: 7). Ko Yoruba da Igbo da ke bi ma Hausa cikin harsunan Nijeriya ba su da gurbi a Fesbuk.

Bugu da kari, kamfanin Gogul ya dade da ba wa Hausa muhimmanci. Yana fitar da dubban ɗaruruwan jimloli da kalmomi a-kai-a-kai domin fassara. Kamfanin yana da injin din fassara wanda aka fi sani da *Google Online Translator*. Daga cikin harsunan da ke kan wannan tsari har da Hausa. Wani kalubale na wannannan injin din fassara shi ne, yana iya kasancewa a ci karo da fassara da ba ingantacciya ba. Dalili kuwa shi ne, idan ya kasance jimlar da aka bincika ba ta da fassara a cikin injin din, to injin zai fassara ta. Zai yi fassarar ta hanyar amfani da ilimin fassarori makamantanta da ke kan injin din. A kullum kamfanin na fara inganta tsarin. A kasa an ba da misalin fassara mai inganci da marar inganci waɗanda aka ɗauko daga injin din fassara na Gogul:

Hoto 2.6: Fassara Mai Inganci Daga Injin Din Fassara na Gogul

Madogara: <https://www.google.com/search?q=english+to+hausa>

A hoto na 2.6 da ke sama, za a iya lura da cewa fassarar da injin fassara na Gogul ya bayar tana da inganci. A kasa an kawo misalin fassara mai rauni (duba hoto na 2.7):

Hoto 2.7: Fassara Marar Inganci Daga Injin Fassara na Gogul

Madogara: <https://www.google.com/search?q=english+to+hausa>

A hoto na 2.7 da ke sama, za a iya lura da cewa, fassarar da injin din fassara na Gogul ya bayar na da rauni. Ya fassara “her” wanda ya kasance jinsin mace a matsayin jinsin namiji, wato “shi.”

Ko bayan Gogul, akwai waɗansu injunan fassara a kafafen intanet waɗanda Hausa ke ɗaya daga cikin harsunan da ke kansu (supported languages). Wasu kuwa kamusoshin fassara ne daga cikin harshen Hausa zuwa wasu harsuna daban, ko kuma daga wasu harsuna zuwa harshen Hausa. A kasa an kawo misalan wasu daga ciki:

1. Bargery Online Dictionary (Kamusun Bargery na Kan Intanet). Adiresinsa shi ne: <http://maguzawa.dyndns.ws/>.
2. Hausa Dictionary (Kamusun Hausa). Adiresinsa shi ne: http://hausadictionary.com/Main_Page.
3. Stars 21 (Taurari 21). Adiresinsa shi ne: https://www.stars21.com/translator/english_to_hausa.html.
4. Translation 2 (Fassara 2). Adiresinsa shi ne: <https://translation2.paralink.com/English-Hausa-Translator/>.
5. Translator (Mai fassara). Adiresinsa shi ne: <https://imtranslator.net/translation/hausa/to-english/translation/>.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, kafar Wikifidiya (Wikipedia) fitacciya ce a duniyar intanet.³⁴ Da wuya a binciki wata kalma a injin nema na Gogul ba tare da an ci

³⁴ Domin farin bayani a kan wannan kafa ana iya duba <https://wikipedia.org/>.

karo da zaɓin Wikifidiya ya fito a shafin farko ba. Rubuce-rubucen wannan kafa ya shafi dukkanin bangarorin rayuwa tun daga kan siyasa da zamantakewa da addini da tarihi har zuwa kiwon lafiya da harsuna da al'ada da dai sauransu. A yanzu haka, wannan kafa ta fara samar da bayanai cikin harshen Hausa.³⁵ Babu makawa wannan kafa za ta taimaka wa harshen matuƙa wajen yaɗuwa da yayatuwa a duniya.³⁶ A kasa an kawo misalin shafin farko na wannan kafa cikin hoto.

Hoto 2.8: Kafar Wikifidiya ta Hausa

Madogara: Shafin farko na Wikifidiyan Hausa
https://ha.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babban_shafi

A hoto na 2.8 da ke sama, za a iya lura da cewa wannan shafi na Wikifidiya cikin harshen Hausa yake. A zuwa lokacin da aka dauki hoton (ranar 25 ga watan

³⁵ Shafin farko wanda ake kira “gida” (home page) na Hausa da ke kan kafar Wikifidiya yana da adiresi kamar haka: https://ha.wikipedia.org/wiki/Babban_shafi.

³⁶ Ya rage ga masana da manazarta Hausa da su shiga a dama da su cikin harkar bunƙasawa da inganta wannan kafa. Koma bayan haka, kafin a farga, barnar da za a yi wa Hausa a ilimance ba za ta misaltu ba!

Maris, shekarar 2020), akwai makalu dubu hudu da dari bakwai da tara (4,709) a kan shafin.

2.1.2 Al'ada

Al'ada ta shafi rayuwa ce gaba daya. Duk wani abin da ke gudana a rayuwa yana cikin kadadar al'ada ne. Idan aka yi la'akari da amfanin al'ada da matsayinta, ba abin mamaki ba ne da ya kasance an dukufa wajen gudanar da rubuce-rubucen ilimi dangane da ita. Maikwari (2020: 40), ya bayyana cewa: "Masana al'ada da zamantakewar al'umma (Anthropologist) sun bayyana cewa, an samu ma'anar al'ada tun a karni na sha tara (K19)."

A fashin bakin kalmar al'ada, za a iya cewa tana amfani ne a muhimman wurare guda biyu. Na farko shi ne al'amarin da ke faruwa ga mata, wato *al'adar zubar jini*. Na biyu kuwa ya shafi duk wani abu da aka saba aiwatarwa musamman bisa wasu mata kai sababbu kuma sanannu. Ma'anar al'ada da Abraham, (1962: 17) ya bayar ta kunshi dukkanin bangarorin biyu. A cewarsa, al'ada na nufin: "aure da buki da hails (al'adar mata) da magana da ciwon kai wanda aka saba da yi." A nan, Abraham ya jero misalai ne na al'ada ba tare da sanya su cikin bayani yadda za a gane ma'anar kalmar kai tsaye ba.

Ma'anar da Abraham, (1962: 17) ya bayar na da matufar kama da ta Bargery, (1934: 16). Shi ma ya kawo kalmomi ne a jere ba tare da sanya su cikin bayani ko sharhin da za a gane ma'anar al'ada kai tsaye ba. A yunkurinsa na ba da ma'anar kalmar, ya ce: "Tada ko dabi'a ko hanya ko hails..." Idan aka lura, shi ma Bargery

bai fita daga kadadar bayyana al'ada a bagirai biyu ba (abin da aka saba ko kuma al'adar mata).

A cikin *Kamusun Hausa na Jami'ar Bayero*, an ba da ma'anonin al'ada da ke kama da na Abraham da Bargery. An karkasa ma'anonin ne zuwa rukunne huɗu masu cin gashin kansu kamar haka: "(i) hanyar rayuwar al'umma (ii) jinin haila (iii) wani hali na daban na mutum (iv) magani ko tsafi" Sa'id *da wasu* (2006: 9). A nan ma ba a yi cikakken bayani ba da zai fitar da ma'anar kalmar fili. A maimakon haka, an dunkule ma'anonin ne.

Ba abin mamaki ba ne don an kira *jinin haila* da suna al'ada kasancewarsa sanannen al'amari kuma sababbe. Kusan dukkanin ma'anonin al'ada da masana da manazarta ke bayarwa, ba sa fita daga farfajiyar sababben al'amari. Misali, Ibrahim, (1982: iii) ya bayyana ma'anar al'ada da: "Abubuwan da mutum ya saba yi a cikin rayuwarsa ta duniya. Ta haka al'ada ta shafi yanayin rayuwar al'umma da harkokin da take gudanarwa na yau da kullum." A takaice, wannan bayani ya yi karin haske kan ma'anar da Abraham, (1962: 17) ya bayar, musamman wurin da ya ambaci "aure da buki." Ga bisa dukkan alamu kasancewarsu sababbin al'amura masu bin wasu sanannun matakan gudanarwa, shi ne ya ja hankalinsa wajen bayyana wannan ra'ayi.

A shekarar 1987, Dangambo ya samar da wata ma'anar al'ada wadda ke ɗauke da kalma mai jan hankali (amincewa). A tasa fahimta, sababbiyar hanyar gudanar da rayuwa kadai ba ta kai matsayin al'ada ba, har sai mafi yawa daga cikin al'umma

sun aminta da ita. Ya ce: “Al’ada ita ce sababbiyar hanyar gudanar da rayuwa, wadda akasarin jama’a na cikin al’umma suka amince da ita” Dangambo, a cikin Maikwari, (2020: 40).

Ma’anar al’ada da Bunza, (2006) ya bayar tana matufar kama da ta Gusau, (2010). Bunza, (2006: 7) ya ce: “Al’ada tana nufin dukkanin rayuwar Dan’Adam ce tun daga haihuwarsa har zuwa kabarinsa.” Shi kuwa Gusau, (2010: 2) cewa ya yi: “Al’ada ta kunshi dukkan bangarorin rayuwar dan Adam.” Idan aka duba ma’anonin guda biyu, suna nuna cewa, al’ada ta shafi rayuwar dan’adam ne gaba dāyanta. Gusau, (2010) ya ba da ma’anar al’ada mai faffadar bayani, ya ce:

Al’ada ta kunshi tafarki wanda wata al’umma take rayuwa a cikinsa dangane da yanayin abinci da tufafi da muhalli da rayuwar aure da haihuwa da mutuwa da wasu hulɗoɗin rayuwa kamar makwabtaka da sana’o’i da kasuwanci da shugabanci da bukukuzwa da sauran abubuwa waɗanda suke da alaƙa da haka. Gusau, (2010: 2)

Hafika wannan ma’ana ta Gusau ta ba da haske sosai kan kalmar. Ma’anar har ta kyallaro ire-iren abubuwan da al’ada ta kunsu. Sun shafi bayyanannu kamar “abinci da tufafi da muhalli” da kuma boyayyu da suka shafi “rayuwar aure da haihuwa da mutuwa da wasu hulɗoɗin rayuwa kamar makwabtaka.”³⁷

Wani abin lura shi ne, idan aka dāuki ma’anar al’ada a matsayin hanyar gudanar da rayuwa (Bunza, 2006: 7; Gusau, 2010: 2), to ana iya cewa, al’ada ba ta tsaya kan

³⁷ Yana da kyau a lura cewa, a cikin boyayyun al’adun da ya lissafo ana iya samun al’amuran al’ada da suka kasance bayyanannu. Misali, alhini da bakin ciki yayin mutuwa a boye suke, amma yanka dabba a bayyane yake.

mutane ba kawai. Tana iya shafar dukkanin halittu, tun daga waƙanda ake gani har waƙanda ba a gani.³⁸ A bisa wannan tunani ne Maikwari, (2020: 42) yake cewa:

Na lura ba mutane kaɗai ne suke da al'adu ba, hatta ma dabbobi da kwari kowa da irin tasa hanyar gudanar da rayuwa kuma da yadda yake aiwatar da tsarin rayuwarsa, kama daga kuka, da nema, da cin abinci da tanadi ga masu yin tanadi da sadarwa tsakaninsu da wasu da dai makamantansu. (Maikwari, 2020: 42)

Duk da haka, wannan bincike ya shafi al'adun mutane ne kawai. A mutanen ma, ya takaita ne ga nazartar al'adaun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet. Idan aka yi nazarin ma'anonin al'ada da masana suka bayar, za a iya fahimtar cewa:

- i. Al'ada ta shafi fitattun ɓangarori guda biyu. ɓangare na farko ya danganci al'adar mata da ake kira hails. Na biyu shi ne wanda ta shafi al'amuran da ake gudanarwa a rayuwa.
- ii. Al'ada ta shafi rayuwar mutum gaba ɗaya.
- iii. Al'ada ta shafi abin da aka saba gudanarwa.
- iv. Al'ada ta shafi abin da mafi yawan jama'a a cikin al'umma suka aminta da kasancewarsa ko gudanuwarsa cikin wani fasali na musamman.
- v. Al'ada ta shafi wani sanannen al'amari sababbe.
- vi. Al'ada na bambanta daga wuri zuwa wuri ko daga al'umma zuwa al'umma.

Bayan la'akari da duka waƙannan, za a iya cewa, al'ada na nufin tsarin rayuwa ta gaba ɗaya wanda ta haɗa da sanannun sababbun al'amuran da ke gudana yau da

³⁸ Kowace halitta tana da al'amuran da suka shafi rayuwarta.

kullu bisa wasu tsararrun fa'idoji da mata kai da kuma wafanda aka saba da wanzuwarsu kara zube ba tare da fa'ida ta musamman ba.

2.1.3 Tasirin Intanet a Kan Al'ummomi da Al'adunsu

A yau, intanet ya zama wani ɓangare na rayuwar al'umma. A cikin giraf na 1 da ke karkashin 2.1.1.1 a babu na biyu, za a ga cewa a shekarar 1991 ne aka samar da kafar intanet ta farko. A zuwa shekarar 2017, adadin kafafen intanet sun kai biliyan ɗaya da ɗigo bakwai da shida (biliyan 1.76). Adadin ya sauka a shekarar 2018 da 2019. A 2019, adadin na kafafen intanet ya kasance kimanin biliyan ɗaya da ɗigo bakwai da biyu (biliyan 1.72). Adadin na kafafen intanet ya kara yawa a shekarar 2020.³⁹

A ɓangare guda kuwa, sama da rabin mutanen duniya ne ke amfani da intanet. An samu wannan rahoto daga kididdigar da *Statista* ta yi a farkon shekarar 2020. A yayin rubuta rahoton a kafar *Statista*, Clement, (2020: 1) ya bayyana cewa:

Almost 4.54 billion people were active internet users as of January 2020, encompassing 59 percent of the global population.

Fassara

Masu amfani da intanet ya zuwa watan Janairu na shekarar 2020 sun kai kimanin biliyan 4.54, wanda hakan ya kai kashi 59 na adadin mutanen duniya.

³⁹ Wannan bincike ya yi kofarin daukar rahoton Internet Live Stats na ranar 20 ga watan Fabarairun shekarar 2020.

Giraf 2.2: Adadin Masu Amfani da Intanet a Watan Janairu na Shekarar 2020

Madogara: Climent, (2020: 1)

Ko bayan adadin mutanen da ke amfani da intanet, masu cudanya da duniyar intanet a kullum abin dubawa ne. Kowace kafa aka dauka za a tarar da akwai adadin mutane da ke ziyarta tare da gudanar da al'amura a kowace rana (wata ta fi wata yawan maziyyarta). A ranar 20 ga watan Fabarairu na shekarar 2020, an nazarci hada-hadar da ke gudana a duniyar intanet daidai kafe 11:30 na dare. A kasa an kawo bayanai game da alkaluman hada-hadar duniyar intanet na wannan rana.

Hoto 2.9: Hada-Hadar Yau da Kullum ta Wasu Kafafen Intanet 1

Madogara: Internet Live Stats, (2020: 1)

A hoto na 2.8 da ke sama, za a iya lura cewa, sama da mutane biliyan biyar ne suka yi amfani da intanet ranar 20/02/2020. Adadin ya fi yawan rabin mutanen duniya. Wannan na nuni da tarisin intanet ga rayuwar al'umma. Har ila yau, adadin kafafen intanet masu aiki a wannan rana sun fi biliyan guda da miliyan dubu dari bakwai da hamsin da daya. Za a iya hasashen cewa, wannan adadi ya fi yawan adadin gidajen da ke duniya.⁴⁰ A bangare guda kuwa, sakonnin imel da aka tura sun zarta biliyan dari biyu da hamsin da uku da miliyan dari da goma sha uku. Wannan ma na kara nuni ga yadda intanet ya zama wani bangaren rayuwar al'umma.

Hoto 2.10: Hada-Hadar Yau da Kullum ta Wasu Kafafen Intanet 2

Madogara: Internet Live Stats, (2020: 1)

A hoto na 2.8 da ke sama, za a iya lura cewa, an aika tambayoyi sama da biliyan shida da miliyan dari takwas da hamsin da huɗu a Gogul a ranar 20/02/2020. Kada a manta da cewa, Gogul ba shi kadai ne injin nema a duniyar intanet ba.⁴¹ A bangare guda kuwa, adadin sabbin labarai da aka dora a kan bulog-bulog a

⁴⁰ Kafar *The Conversation* ta wallafa rahoto a ranar 28 ga watan Fabarairun shekarar 2018 mai taken “*The world needs to build more than two billion new homes over the next 80 years*” wato “Akwai buƙatar a gina sababbin gidaje sama da biliyan biyu a duniya a cikin shekaru 80 masu zuwa.” A cikin rahoton ta nuna cewa, gidajen da ke duniya sun kasance kimanin biliyan guda da digo biyu (biliyan 1.2).

⁴¹ An kawo misalan injunan nema na duniyar intanet a babi na ɗaya farkashin 1.7 (Farfajiyar Bincike).

wannan rana sun haura miliyan shida da dubu dari biyar. Baya ga haka, an dora labarai sama da miliyan dari bakwai da hamsin da daya a kafar Tuwita.⁴²

Hoto 2.11: Hada-Hadar Yau da Kullum ta Wasu Kafafen Intanet 3

7,023,765,953

**Adadin bidiyoyi da aka
kalla a kan Yutub**

82,503,021

**Adadin hotuna da aka dora
a kan insitagiram**

Madogara: Internet Live Stats, (2020: 1)

A cikin hoto na 2.9 da ke sama, za a ga cewa, an kalli bidiyoyi sama da biliyan bakwai da miliyan ashirin da uku a Yutub a ranar 20/02/2020. Haka kuma, an dora hotuna sama da miliyan tamanin da biyu a kafar Insitagiram. La'akari da dukkanin waɗannan alkaluma, haƙifa intanet na da matuƙar tasiri ga rayuwar al'umma.

Wellman, *et al* (2002: 6) sun nazarci ayyukan Barlow, (1995) da Wellman, (2001) da Nie, (2001) da Nie, Hillygus, & Erbring, (2002) inda suka fitar da nau'ukan tasirin da intanet ke yi kan al'umma. Sun bayyana su kamar haka:

- i. *The Internet decreases community* (Intanet na samar da koma-baya ga al'umma)

⁴² Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, adadin masu amfani da Fesbuk sun fi na waɗanda ke amfani da Tuwita nesa ba kusa ba. Wannan na nuna cewa, labaran da ake dora a Fesbuk ya wuce wannan adadi sosai.

- ii. *The Internet transforms community* (Intanet na kawo sauye-sauye ga rayuwar al'umma)
- iii. *The Internet supplements community* (Intanet na samar da wata al'umma ta daban)

Koma-baya da intanet ke samarwa ga al'umma ya shafi fannonin rayuwarsu daban-daban. Misali, al'amuran nishadi da bata lokaci da intanet ke kunshe da su na dauke wa mutane hankali da shagaltar da su. A haka ne al'umma ke auren intanet a maimakon yin amfani da lokutansu wajen aikata ayyukan da za su taimake su a matsayin daidaike da a matsayin al'umma. Sauye-sauye da intanet ya zo da su kuwa nau'uka biyu ne. Akwai masu amfani, akwai kuma wadanda ke mazaunin kalubale.⁴³ A bangare guda kuwa, al'umma ta daban da intanet ke samarwa na nufin al'amura da hulfayya da ke wanzuwa a duniyar intanet.

Za a kara fahimtar tasirin intanet yayin da aka nazarci tasirin kafafen sada zumunta ga zamantakewar yau. A duniyar yau, kafafen sada zumunta sun zama wani bangare na rayuwar al'umma. Kusan za a iya cewa, duniyar mutane ba za ta

⁴³ Saukafa sadarwa da kasuwanci da sauran huldayyar al'umma ci gaba ne da ya samu a sakamakon intanet. A bangare guda kuwa, akwai al'amuran da intanet ya zo da su da suka kasance koma-baya ko cikas ga al'adu da zamantakewa. Sun hada da satar bayanan sirri da yada alfasha da mugun aiki da makamantansu.

iya rayuwa ba sai da su. Dalili kuwa shi ne, rayuwar mutane da dama ta dogara kacokan kan ire-iren wadannan kafafe. Nan ne cinsu, nan ne shansu!⁴⁴

A rahoton da Clement, (2019: 2) ya fitar, masu amfani da kafar Whatsapp a watanni kafan bayan samar da kafar sun kai kimanin biliyan guda da miliyan dari biyar (1,005,000,000). Binciken da Jayasekara, (2015) ya gudanar ya nuna cewa, ana samun karuwar masu amfani da kafafen sada zumunta matuƙa. Masana da manazarta da dama sun yi bincike da rubuce-rubuce game da tasirin kafafen sadarwa a zamantakewa.⁴⁵ Siddiqui & Singh sun bayyana cewa:

Now a day's social media has been the important part of one's life from shopping to electronic mails, education and business tool. Social media plays a vital role in transforming people's life style. Siddiqui & Singh, (2016: 71)

Fassara

A yau, kafafen sada zumunta sun zama wani muhimmin bangare na rayuwar dan'adam tun daga kan sayayya da tura sakonni da ilimi har zuwa kasuwanci. Kafafen sada zumunta suna taka muhimmiyar rawa dangane da salon rayuwar mutane.

Lallai wannan batu haka yake, domin kuwa ko a kasar Hausa akwai mutane da dama da suka raja'a matuƙa kan kafafen na sada zumunta. Akwai muhimman bangarorin rayuwa da wadannan kafafe suka fi shafa. Sun hada da:

i. Sada zumunta

⁴⁴ A shekarar 2019, kafar intanet din nan mai suna Sitatista da ke adana bayanai dangane da kafafen intanet ya fitar da kididdigar ma'aikatan Fesbuk. Ya bayyana cewa, a shekarar 2018, ma'aikatan sun kai dubu ashirin da biyar da dari daya da biyar (25,105).

⁴⁵ Wasu daga cikin rubuce-rubucen sun hada da na Baruah, (2012) da Korkmaz, Celebe & Yucel, (2014) da OwusuAcheaw & Larson, (2015) da Siddiqui & Singh, (2016).

- ii. Tattaunawa a matakin daidaike ko kungiyoyi
- iii. Kasuwanci da cinikayya
- iv. Ilimi da karantarwa

Tun farko dai wadannan kafafe an samar da su ne domin sada zumunta. Misali, Fesbuk da aka samar a wajajen 2004, ya kasance hobɓasa ne na dalibin Jami'ar Harvard mai suna Mark Zuckerberg. Ya kirkiro ta ne a matsayin kafar sada zumunta tsakanin daliban makarantar ta Harvard. Sannu a hankali daliban wasu makarantu na daban suka fara amfana da ita.⁴⁶ A shekarar 2006 ne kuma aka fitar da ita a matsayin kafar sada zumunta da duniya gaba ɗaya za ta iya amfani da ita (Baruah, 2012: 4; Clement, 2019: 2). A zuwa yau, Fesbuk ke kan gaba a duk cikin kafafen sada zumunta. Bayan ita, sai wasu daga cikin fitattun kafafen sada zumunta, su ne:

- a. Instagram
- b. Twitter
- c. Whatsapp

2.2 Bitar Ra'i

Wannan aiki ya kunshi manyan batutuwa guda biyu masu cin gashin kansu, wato "al'ada" da "intanet." Al'adar kuma ta Hausawa ce. A bisa wannan dalili, babu wani ra'i da ya fi dacewa da ya jagoranci wannan ɓangare na binciken face

⁴⁶ Makarantun da suka fara amfani da kafar sun haɗa da Columbia da Yale da Stanford (Clement, 2019: 2).

“Bahaushen Ra’i.” Akwai masana da ke goyon bayan amfani da Bahaushen Ra’i wajen gudanar da bincike. Bunza, (2019) na ɗaya daga cikinsu inda yake cewa:

Lokaci ya yi da al’adunmu da tunanin magabatanmu ya yi tasiri ga iliminmu da bincike-binciken iliminmu. Ban ce ra’o’in Turawa na ilmi na a kan kuskure ba, amma a kowane irin al’amari gara a kai na hannu gida kafin a dawo a kama na dawa. (Bunza, 2019: 721).

Idan aka yi la’akari da ma’anar karin magana kamar yadda wasu masana suka bayyana, za mu tarar da cewa sun kai matsayin hanyar dora aiki ko ra’i kai tsaye. Gray, (1987) kamar yadda aka rawaito a cikin Tambuwal, (2018: 32) ya ce karin magana: “Gajeren zance ne wanda ke cike da gaskiya da kayatarwa.” An dai kuwa san cewa, kafin a tabbatar da wani ra’ayi a matsayin gaskiya, dole sai an sha gwaji ana samun sakamako marasa cin karo da juna.

Za a sake gaskata wannan fahimta yayin da aka yi la’akari da masana da ke kallon karin magana a matsayin: “...maganganun hikima da fasaha, wadda ta cikin waɗannan zantukan ake fahimtar halaye da ɗabi’un wannan al’umma.” (Kirk-Green, 1966 da Skinner 1980 a cikin Tambuwal, 2018: 31). Da ma dai ta hanyar ra’i ne ake fahimtar yanayin wani al’amari. John, (1998: 364) ya rawaito Poole da Van de Ven na cewa: “*A good theory is, by definition, a limited and fairly precise picture.*” Fassara: “Ta fannin ma’ana, ingantaccen ra’i shi ne hoton wani al’amari ko yanayi a takaice.” Hakika karin maganar Bahaushen na da wannan matsayi na bayyana hoton al’amari a takaice.

Ra’ayin Malumfashi da Nahuce, (2014) ma ya bayyana karin magana a matsayin abin da zai iya ɗaukar ma’anar ra’i. Suna da fahimtar cewa, karin magana na nuni

ga al'ada da salon rayuwar al'ummar da ke amfani da wadannan karin maganganu. Idan kuwa haka ne, karan karin maganganun Bahaushe sun kai tsaikon zama a matsayin ra'i. Idan muka duba ma'anar ra'i wanda Sashen Ilimin Jarida da Sadarwa ta Jami'ar Fulorida da ke Amurka (College of Journalism and Communications University of Florida) ta bayar, za mu sake tabbatar da karin maganganun Bahaushe ra'o'i ne. Sun bayyana ra'i da cewa:

Theory explains how some aspect of human behavior or performance is organized. It thus enables us to make predictions about that behavior. (UF College of Journalism and Communications, (ND)).

Fassara

Ra'i yana bayani a kan tsari da fasalin dabi'ar dan'adam ko aikinsa. A bisa haka, yana ba mu damar yin hasashe dangane da wannan halayyar (ta dan'adam).⁴⁷

Ado, (2017: 32) ya kawo fassarar ma'anar ra'i da Oxford, (1998) ya samar. A wannan fassara, ra'i na nufin: "Tunani ko jerin tunane-tunane waɗanda aka shawarta cewa su ne ke iya yin bayani kan wani abu da ya faru ko zai faru." Wannan ma'ana na kara tabbatar da karin magananganun Bahaushe a matsayin ra'i ko hanyar dora bincike. Dalili kuwa shi ne, bai fita a da'irar ma'anar karin magana da Danyaya, (2007: vii) ya bayar ba. Ya ce: "Karin magana zance ne gajere, mai fadakarwa kan zaman duniya." An dai san cewa, fadakarwa na kunshe da bayani kan lamura da sakamako mai kyau ko marar kyau da ka iya biyo bayan aikata wani aiki.

⁴⁷ Sai dai yana da kyau a lura cewa, ra'i na iya fayyace halayya ba na dan'adam ba kadai, har ma da sauran abubuwa (wadanda ake gani da wadanda ba a gani). Ba abin mamaki ba ne da ma'anar ra'in da suka bayar ta takaita kan dan'adam kasancewar Sashen na Ilimin Jarida da Sadarwa ne. Al'amuran sashen kai tsaye sun shafi 'yan'adam ne.

Duk da haka, akwai masana da suke da fahimtar cewa, karin magana bai kai ya tsaya a mazaunin ra’i ba. A maimakon haka, sai dai a dauke shi a matsayin “hanyar dora aiki.”^{48,49} Wannan bincike ya tafi kan ra’ayi na biyu (karin magana a matsayin hanyar dora aiki) bisa waɗannan dalilai:

- a. Har yanzu masana harshe da al’ada da adabin Hausa ba su kai matsaya kan karin maganganu a matsayin ra’i ko hanyar dora aiki ba.
- b. Ko ba komai, ra’i ma jagoranci ne na aiki. Hanya ce da ake dora tunanin bincike (alkiblar da zaren tunanin bincike zai nufa). A bisa wannan dalili, ko da an kai matsayar aminta da karin magana a matsayin ra’i, hakan ba zai saba da matsayar wannan bincike ba.

An dora wannan aiki kan karin maganar Bahaushe ta: “**Zamani Riga**” domin jagorancinsa. A tunanin Bahaushe, zamani tamkar riga ce wato yayi-yayi. “Wato ke nan idan ya zo sai kowa ya dauka ya sa a jikinsa?” (Yunusa, 1989: 40). A lokacin yayin abu, sai a yi shi. Bayan yayin ya wuce kuwa, sai a watsar domin a riki sabon yayi. Bahaushe ya kara karfafa wannan fahimta a karin maganarsa da ke cewa:

⁴⁸ Dr. Isah Abdullahi Muhammad ya jaddada wannan batu yayin taron kara wa juna sani na kasa karo na huɗu da aka gudanar a Tsangayar Fasaha da Addini Musulunci da ke Jami’ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato. Taron na da taken: “*Zamfara Kingdom: Social and Political Transformation from 14th Century to Date.*” An gudanar da shi daga 24 zuwa 28 ga watan Fabarairu ta shekarar 2020.

⁴⁹ A hirar da aka yi da Sa’idu Umar Yahaya ta waya ranar 6 ga watan Mayu ta shekarar 2020, ya bayyana cewa: “Ass. Prof. Abdullahi, I.S.S. na da ra’ayin cewa ba za a kira karin magana ra’i ba. A maimakon haka, sai dai a ce hanyar dora aiki.”

“Lokacin abu a yi shi!” Duk wanda bai taka rawar kidan gangar zamani ba, lallai kafin ya farga an masa fintinkau.⁵⁰

Akwai ayyuka da suka gabata wadanda karin maganganu ke musu jagoranci a matsayin ra’o’i ko hanyoyin dora aiki. Bunza, (2019: 721) ya yi amfani da “Ba banza ba kuda a warki” a cikin bincikensa mai taken “Kwarya a Farfajiyar Adabi da Al’adun Bahaushe.” An wallafa wannan makala cikin *East African Scholars Journal of Education, Humanities and Literature Vol. 2, Issue 12*. Karin maganar ya yi wa binciken nasa jagoranci wajen binciko dalilan da suka sa kwarya ta mamaye adabi da al’adar Bahaushe. Lallai “ruwa ba ya tsami banza.”

Sani, Buba & Mohammad, (2019: 45) sun yi amfani da karin maganar da ke cewa: “Mai nema yana tare da samu” yayin gudanar da bincikensu. Binciken na da taken: “Wanda Ya Tuna Bara...: Bida da Tanadi a Tsakanin Hausawa Matasa a Yau.” An buga makalar a cikin *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, Vol. 1, Issue 1 & 2*. Ra’in ya jagoranci binciken nasu wajen bayyana cewa, takunkumin tattalin arzikin da ya dabaibaye matasan Hausawa a yau na da alaka da rashin hazakarsu wajen fafutukar neman na kai. Ko da ma dai, “Ba a kama zomo daga zaune.”

Shi kuwa Yahaya, (2020: 7) ya yi amfani da karin magana ne a matsayin hanyar dora aiki. Ya zaɓi karin maganar nan na “Zamani Riga.” A kansa aka gina

⁵⁰ A nan gangar zamani ba ta nufin sharholiya. A maimakon haka, tana nufin ci gaba da zamani ke zuwa da shi a fannin kiwon lafiya da kimiyya da fasaha da ra’ayoyi da al’adu da zamantakewa da makamantansu.

bincikensa mai taken: “Damben Hausawa a Zamanance.”⁵¹ Dangane da wannan hanya ta dora aiki, Yahaya ya ce: “Wannan karin magana manufarsa ita ce bayyana yadda lokaci wato zamani yake shiga cikin bangarorin rayuwa ya samar da tsari da zai tafiyar da wani sha’ani daidai da zamani” (Yahaya, 2020: 7).

Fahimtar Bahaushe ta “Zamani riga” ta tafi kan cewa, karbar sauye-sauyen da zamani ya zo da su dole ne domin samun ci gaba mai dorewa. A bisa wannan tunani, abin da ya fi dacewa ga Hausawa shi ne su rungumi intanet a matsayin abin da zamani ya zo da shi. Da yake ana magana a kan al’adunsu ne, saka rigar zamani zai ba su damar:

- i. Tantancewa da kalubalantar duk wasu bayanan karya dangane da al’adunsu da ke duniyar intanet, da
- ii. Samar da ingantattun bayanai dangane da al’adun Hausawa a duniyar ta intanet.

Wani hanzari ba gudu ba shi ne, wannan hanyar dora aiki kadai ba za ta iya biyan bukatar binciken gaba daya ba. Kamar yadda John, (1998: 364) ya bayyana, ra’i dole ne ya kasance ya wadatar a fannonin da suka hada da: “*definitions, domain, relationships, and predictive claims to answer the natural language questions of who, what, when, where, how, why, should, could and would.*” Ma’ana, dole ne su wadatar da bangarorin: “ma’anoni da bagire da dangantaka da ra’ayoyin da ke samar da

⁵¹ An nazarci wannan bincike bayan ya tsallake matakin jarabawar cikin gida (Internal Defense) a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami’ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.

amsoshi kan tambayoyi kamar “wa?” da “me?” da “yaushe?” da “a ina?” da “ta yaya?” da “me ya dace?” da “me zai yiwu?” da “me za a yi?””

A bisa wannan dalili, za a yi amfani da wani ra’in na daban wanda zai mayar da hankali kan ɗaya ɓangaren binciken (intanet). Masana da dama sun tabbatar da cewa, mai bincike na iya amfani da ra’i sama da guda musamman domin ya samu ra’o’in da suka dace da dukkanin ɓangarorin bincikensa.⁵² Ojua, ya bayyana cewa:

In most social science and humanity, you should know that no single theory best correctly explain a social issue. Ecclectic usage of theories is very adequate. (Ojua, 2019: 1).

Fassara

Ya kamata a fahimci cewa a mafiya yawan fannonin ilimin kimiyyar zamantakewa da na mu’amala, babu wani ra’i guda ɗaya da yake bayanin wata matsala yadda ya kamata. Amfani da ra’i sama da guda shi ne ya fi dacewa.

Ra’in da ke jagorancin ɓangare na biyu na wannan bincike shi ne **Pulatoriyya** (Platonism). Da zarar an ambaci wannan ra’i, hankali zai koma kan fitaccen malamin falsafar nan Plato⁵³ (Gerson, 2005: 253). Duk da haka, abin lura shi ne, a farkon lokaci ba a kiran wanan ra’i da Pulatoriyya. Daga cikin mabiya ra’in da ba

⁵² Masu wannan ra’ayi sun haɗa da Fafowora, B. da ke *University of Ibadan, Nigeria* da Mwangi, N. da ke *London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine* da Laverne A. Davis da ke *Grand Canyon University, US* da Ali Nasser Al-Tahitah da ke *USIM | Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia* da Wright, D. da ke *University of Nevada, Las Vegas* da Ojua, T. da ke *University of Calabar, Nigeria* da Rehman, U. da ke *Aligarh Muslim University India* da Muhanga, M. Sokoine *University of Agriculture (SUA) Tanzania* da Ojua, T. da ke *University of Calabar, Nigeria*. Domin karin bayani ana iya duba: https://www.researchgate.net/post/Can_I_use_Two_or_more_theories_to_support_my_research_model

⁵³ Plato ɗan asalin Athens ne da ke Girka (Greece). Ya rayu tsakanin 428/427 BCE - 348/347. Dalibi ne ga Socrates sannan malami ga Aristotle. Domin samun cikakken tarihin Plato, ana iya duba: Meinwald, C. C. (2020). Plato (Greek Philosopher). In *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Retrieved on 17th March 2020 from: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Plato>.

su rayu lokacin da aka sanya masa wannan suna ba akwai Speusippus⁵⁴ da Xenocrates⁵⁵ da Antiochus⁵⁶ da Numenius. Wannan ya samar da babbar tambaya cewa: “Shin Plato mabiyin Pulatoriyya ne?” A bisa haka ne Gerson, (2013: 3) yake cewa:

The question is only marginally more illuminating if we take it to mean “Would Plato have agreed with one or another of the historical, systematic representations of his philosophy?” Naturally, this question, like all questions about counterfactuals in the history of philosophy, is unanswerable. (Gerson, 2013: 3)

Fassara:

Tambayar ba za ta kasance mai armashi ba har sai idan tana nufin cewa: “Shin Plato zai yarda da tarihi ko tsararren wakilci na falsafarsa?” A al’adar duniya, wannan tambayar ba mai amsuwa ba ce, tamkar dai sauran tambayoyin idan-da⁵⁷ a falsafance.

Lura da wannan, binciken nan na da fahimtar cewa, Pulatoriyya tunani ne da falsafa ta Plato. Duk da haka, ana iya samun sauye-sauye kan tunani da sigogin ra’in na asali. Hakan na faruwa kasancewar a kullum akan samu sabbin tunani. Baya ga haka, masu bincike na iya gyaran fuska ga ra’i domin dacewa da tsarin bincikensu.

Pulatoriyya ya tafi kan cewa, rayuwa ta funshi gaskiya nau’uka biyu (wanda ake kallo da wanda ba a gani). Wannan tunani ya tsaya a tsakiyar fahimtar mabiya Boyayyiyar Gaskiya (Incorporealism) da mabiya Zahiriyya (Realism). ‘Yan falsafa da ke kallon gaskiya a boye take suna da ra’ayin cewa duk wani abin da ake gani a

⁵⁴ Ya rayu tsakanin 410 – 339 B.C.E.

⁵⁵ Ya rayuwa tsakanin 396 – 313 B.C.E.

⁵⁶ Ya rayu tsakanin 130 – 68 B.C.E.

⁵⁷ Tambayoyin idan-da a nan na nufin ire-iren tambayoyin da akwai “da” a cikinsu. Misali: “Da a ce rana ta kudu take fitowa, da duniya za ta fi dadin kallo?”

duniya rayawar zuci ce kawai. Misali, launin fari ko baki ko shufi da rigar mutum ke d'auke da shi, ba zahiri ba ne. A maimakon haka, rayawa da kwafalwa ta yi na samuwar launin ne ya sa har idanu ke kallon sa.

Masu fahimtar Zahiriyya kuwa, sun tafi kan cewa, babu wani abu boyayya. Duniya dungurungum ta takaita ne a kan abubuwan da d'an'adam ke iya kallo. A takaice ke nan, Pulatoriyya ya tsaya ne a tsakaninsu. Ya hada tunanin duka biyu. Wannan ne ya sanya mabiya ra'in suke d'ora ayar tambaya kan Badiniyya (spirituality) da rayuwa bayan mutuwa da makamantansu. A wannan tunani, abubuwan da ido ke iya kallo ko kunne ke iya ji ko jiki ke iya tabawa su ne kadai ke wanzuwa.

A ra'ayin Pulatoriyya, akwai abubuwan da suna wanzuwa ne a duniyar badini. Babban misali a nan shi ne kurwa. Sai dai ko cikin mabiya Pulatoriyya akan samu muhawarori dangane da ire-iren waɗannan boyayyun gaskiya. Misali, ra'in ya fi mayar da hankali kan bayanin yadda kurwa take, sama da abubuwan da suka haɗu suka samar da kurwar. Thein, (2018: 57) ya jadda hakan inda yake cewa:

... despite the very different aim and setting of both dialogues, the problem is much the same: what exactly is the soul that performs the actions that reach beyond the states of our visible and tangible body? (Thein, 2018: 57)

Fassara

... duk da bambancin da ke tsakanin manufa da kuma wurin zama da aka gudanar da waɗannan muhawarori, kanun muhawarar guda ne: Kai tsaye mece ce wannan kurwar da take da siffon da suka wuce ganin idonmu ko ji a jikinmu?

A nan, muhawarorin da marubucin ke nufi su ne (i) Me kurwa ke yi, kuma me ake iya mata? (ii) Mece ce kurwa? Pulatoriyya ya fi damuwa da tambaya ta biyun. Kamar yadda yake a tunanin Pulatoriyya, sanin kurwar (sama) shi zai ba da damar sanin abin da ya samar da ita da kuma abubuwan da take iya yi da waƙanda ake iya mata (ƙasa).

Wata siffa ta Pulatoriyya ita ce jaddada cewa: (a) A cikin kowane abu ko lamari akwai abu mai kyau da marar kyau.⁵⁸ Haka kuma (b) Abu marar kyau shi ke gurbata mai kyau har daga ƙarshe ya lalata shi. A dangane da wannan, Thein, (2018: 65) ya rawaito cewa: *“The bad is what destroys and corrupts, and the good is what preserves and benefits.”* Ma’ana: “Abu marar kyau shi ke gurbatawa da lalatawa. Abu mai kyau kuwa shi ke adanawa da amfanarwa.” Wani mawaki ya gina waƙarsa kan irin wannan tunani. Ya kira kafafen sada zumunta na intanet da suna “Duniyar Matasa.” Ya ce:

Soshiyal midiya duniyar matasa,
Mu yada alkairi kar mu yada zamba.
(Dan’iro Katsina: Waƙar Soshiyal Midiya Dandalin Matasa)

Akwai masana da suke hasashen wannan ra’i na da alaƙa da falsafar ‘Yan Kwafkwafi (skeptical philosophers).⁵⁹ Daga cikin ‘Yan Kwafkwafin farko akwai

⁵⁸ Thein, (2018: 65) ya kawo misalan da suka haɗa da “tsatsa ga ƙarfe”, “rubewa ga ice”, “rashin lafiya ga jiki.” Ya bayyana cewa, waɗannan duka munanan abubuwa ne da suke tabbatattu a al’adar rayuwa. A fahimtar wannan bincike ma haka abin yake.

⁵⁹ Ko da ma kwafkwafi na ɗaya daga cikin abubuwan da suka assasa falsafa a doron ƙasa. Mabiyan sun damu da tambayar asalin haƙifanin yadda al’amura suke da dalilan faruwarsu.

Arcesilaus⁶⁰ da Carneades⁶¹ da Clitomachus⁶² da kuma Philo wanda ya rayu tsakanin 158 - 84 B.C.E. (Gerson, 2005: 253-254). Ba abin mamaki ba ne a samu dangantakar ra'in Pulatoriyya da falsafar 'Yan Kwakkwafi. Dalili kuwa shi ne, gaba ɗaya duniyar falsafa da ma ta tattara kan ra'ayin binciken hakikanin lamura ne. Sukan yi tambaya da suka hada da:

- i. Me? (What?)
- ii. Me ya sa? (Why?)
- iii. Ta yaya? (How?)
- iv. A ina? (Where?)
- v. Mene ne tabbaci? (How certain/How sure?)
- vi. Shin an kai a tabbatar? (Right to be sure?)

Za a iya hasashen cewa, ra'in Pulatoriyya na cike da ire-iren wadannan tambayoyi.

Yayin da Gerson, (ND: 7) yake bayani a kan fitattun siffofin Pulatoriyya, sai ya ce:

What is most distinctive about Platonism is that it is resolutely and irreducibly 'top-down' rather than 'bottom-up'. A top-down approach to philosophical problems rejects and a bottom-up approach accepts the claim that the most important and puzzling phenomena we encounter in this world can be explained by seeking the simplest elements out of which these are composed.

Fassara

Siffar da ta kasance fitacciya ga Pulatoriyya ita ce dogewarsa kan tsarin "daga sama zuwa kasa" a maimakon "daga kasa zuwa sama." Tsarin tunkarar matsalolin falsafa na sama zuwa kasa ya yi watsi da ikirarin cewa abubuwa mafiya muhimmanci da ɗaukar hankali da

⁶⁰ Ya rayu tsakanin 316 - 251 B.C.E.

⁶¹ Ya rayu tsakanin 204 - 129 B.C.E.

⁶² Ya rayu tsakanin 187 - 110 B.C.E.

ake cin karo da su a rayuwar duniya ana iya bayaninsu ta hanyar kwankwance mafi kankantar abubuwan da suka taru suka hada su. Tsarin tunkarar matsalolin falsafa na kasa zuwa sama ya aminta da wannan zance.

'Yan Zahiriyya na da fahimtar cewa, batutuwa irin su ilimi da hankali ba sa wanzuwa sai da dan'adam. Kafin a fahimce su, sai an fahimci dan'adam tare da fahimtar mafi kankantar abubuwa da suka samar da shi, sannan suka samar da abubuwan da yake cudanya da su. Pulatoriyya kuwa yana kallon waƙannan batutuwa (misali ilimi da hankali da lura da rayuwa da makamantansu) suna wanzuwa ne ta hanyar cin gashin kansu. Nau'uka ne na gaskiya waƙanda ba a iya gani. Fahimtarsu shi ne zai ba da karin haske dangane da halittu da ke dāuke da su.

A hasashe irin na nazari, za a iya cewa akwai ayyuka da suka gabata waƙanda aka dōra su kan ra'in Pulatoriyya. Kasancewar babu wanda hannu ya kai kansa ba hujja ba ce ta rashinsu. Abin la'akari shi ne daƙewar da ra'in ya yi da kuma yawan mabiyansa tun daga zamanin Plato zuwa yau.

Gerson, (2013) ya yi kofarin yin bayani a kan haƙifanin abin da ake kira Pulatoriyya. Wannan ya sa taken aikin nasa ya kasance tambaya "What is Platonism?" Wato "Mene ne Pulatoriyya?" Ya bibiyi tarihin Pulatoriyya sannan ya zayyana wasu daga cikin mabiyar ra'in. Daga nan ya mayar da hankali kan nazarin tunanin mabiya ra'in. Aikin nasa na da shafuka talatin. Ya fito cikin mujalla da aka yi wa suna *From Plato to Platonism*. Wato "Daga Rayuwar Plato Zuwa Ra'in Pulatoriyya."

Pena, (2018) ya rubuta makala mai suna “*Platonism as a Philosophical Method*,” wato “Pulatoriyya a Matsayin Ra’in Falsafa.” An wallafa wannan makala a cikin mujallar kasarsu Platon (Athens). Sunanta *Athens Journal of Humanities & Arts* (Volume 5, Issue 1 - Pages 45-60). A ciki ya yi kokarin bayyana ma’anar Pulatoriyya. Daga nan ya mayar da hankali kan bitar wasu maganganun Plato. Daga shafi na 52 zuwa 55, ya yi kokarin danganta falsafar Pulato da babban dalibinsa wato Aristotle.⁶³

Editocin *Encyclopedia Britannica*⁶⁴ (Augustyn, et al., 2020) sun yi rubutu mai taken: *Platonic Criticism* (Tarken Pulatoriyya). A ciki sun kawo bayani dogo mai gamsarwa dangane da ra’in. Wannan ya hada da dangantakar ra’in da tunanin addinin Kiristanci da kuma sauran bangarorin falsafofi. Sun kuma kawo fahimtar ra’in a kan duniya da al’uran da ke gudana cikinta (wadanda ake iya gani da wadanda ba a iya gani).

Ire-iren wadannan ayyuka da kai tsaye suke magana a kan Pulatoriyya, suna kara fito da ra’in fili. Bayan haka, suna nuni ga shahararsa, da cancantarsa wajen jagorancin bincike. Ko ba komai Plato na daya daga cikin manyan fitattun malaman falsafa na farko. Yana daya daga cikin malaman falsafar da ayyukan da aka gudanar kansu ke da dimbin yawa sama da na saura.

⁶³ Bincike ya tabbatar da Plato na da bambancin ra’ayi sosai da dalibinsa Aristotle. Don farin bayani ana iya duba Pena, (2018: 52-55).

⁶⁴ Ana iya duba edotocin *Encyclopedia Britanica* a cikin wannan kafa: <https://www.britannica.com/editor/The-Editors-of-Encyclopaedia-Britannica/4419>.

A wannan bincike, gurbin Pulatoriyya a bayyana yake. Binciken zai duba tasirin intanet ne (sama) kan al'adun Hausawa (kasa) tamkar dai yadda Thein, (2018: 57) ya yi bayanin tsarin tunkarar mas'ala ta Pulatoriyya (daga sama zuwa kasa).⁶⁵ Kai tsaye za a fahimci hakan idan aka yi la'akari da cewa:

- i. Gaskiya da ake kallo ta shafi suturarmu da abincinmu da gine-ginenmu da ababen hawanmu da muhallanmu da wasanninmu da sauran abubuwa makamantan wadannan.
- ii. Gaskiya wanda ba a kallo ta shafi duniyar intanet. Wannan ya hada da al'adunmu da ke ciki, da siyasarmu da muhallanmu da harkokinmu da tufafinmu da abincinmu da dukkanin sauran abubuwa da ke wanzuwa a cikin intanet. A tafaice, a wannan bangare an samu duniyoyi guda biyu: Duniyar Zahiri da Duniyar Intanet.⁶⁶

Yana da kyau a kula da cewa, cudanyar da ke tsakanin duniyoyin biyu (intanet da zahiri) ba ya sa a ce intanet ba duniya ba ce mai zaman kanta. Misali, Musulmai sun yi imani da cewa, duk abin da dan'adam ke aikatawa mala'iku na rubutawa. Mazaunin mala'iku ba duniyar mutane ba ne, duk da sukan zo. Haka ma Musulmai sun yi imani da zaman barzahu. Idan aka yi nazarin kwakkafi ga lamarin, sai a tarar da cewa, akwai dangantaka tsakanin rayuwar duniyar mutane

⁶⁵ Sabanin ta Zahiriyya da suke bin tsarin daga kasa zuwa sama. Da a Zahiriyya ne, binciken da za a yi zai mayar da hankali ne kan al'adu da nau'ukan tunani da suke kai ga amfani da intanet. Yayin da aka ci karo da al'ada a cikin intanet din, za a yi fofari ne a binciko abin da ya kai ta, ba wai tasirinta kan al'adar al'umma masu ita a duniyar zahiri ba.

⁶⁶ Tamkar dai yadda ake da wasu duniyoyi da suka hada da duniyar sararin samaniya da duniyar barzahu da kuma lahira.

da rayuwar barzahu da kuma rayuwar duniyar sararin samaniya. Dole ne kuma a dauki kowace a matsayin rayuwa mai cin gashin kanta. Dalili shi ne, kowace tana da tsare-tsarenta da yanaye-yanayenta wanda hakan ya bambanta ta da 'yar uwarta. A fahimtar wannan bincike, za a iya bayyana duniyoyi da ake da su kamar haka:

- a. Duniyar mutane (duniyar zahiri)
- b. Duniyar intanet
- c. Duniyar tunani
- d. Duniyar mafarki
- e. Duniyar sarari (duniyar sama)
- f. Duniyar matattu (barzahu)
- g. Duniyar tatsuniya

Wannan bincike na da fahimtar cewa, duniyar intanet na dauke da kyawawan abubuwa da kuma munana. Hakan ya yi daidai da ikirarin Pulatoriyya kamar yadda Thein, (2018: 65) ya bayyana. Kyawawan al'amura su ne za su iya amfanarwa. Munana kuwa, za su iya gurbata kyawawan ko ma su lalata su. Ke nan, idan ba a yi hobɓasa ba dangane da al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet, gurbatattun bayanai da ra'ayoyi marasa kyau na iya lalata al'amarin gaba daya. Zai iya kai matsayin da ba a kallon komai sai rashin amfanin intanet dangane da al'adun Hausawa. Za a iya yarda da wannan yayin da aka yi la'akari da wasu kafafen intanet na Hausa da kai tsaye suka ci karo da addini da al'adun Bahausha.

Babban misali a nan shi ne kafar intanet din nan da ta shahara wajen kawo hotuna da bidiyoyi da maganganun batsa, wato *Batsa Posts*.

2.3 Bitar Ayyuka Masu Dangantaka ta Kai Tsaye da Aikin

Wannan bincike ya ci karo da ayyuka da dama da ke da dangantaka da shi. Mafi yawansu an yi su ne cikin wasu harsuna ba Hausa ba. Wannan ɓangare na binciken zai bibiyi ayyukan da suka gabata waɗanda ke da matuƙar kama da binciken. Hakan zai tabbatar da an kauce wa maimaita aikin da aka riga da aka gudanar. Bugu da fari, nazartar ayyukan zai ba da haske tare da jagoranci ga wannan bincike. An kawo bitar daki-daki inda aka fara da kundayen digiri. Daga nan an gangaro kan litattattafai da mujallu da muƙalu.⁶⁷

2.3.1 Kundayen Digiri na Uku

Wannan bincike bai ci karo da wani kundin digiri na uku da ke da alaƙa da shi na kai tsaye ba. Duk da haka, an ci karo da kundayen da suka taɓo batutuwa masu alaƙa da binciken da ake gudanarwa. Sun haɗa da aikin Nadama, (1977). A cikin aikin an kawo batun zuwan Turawa kasar Hausa wanda ya yi sanadiyyar rugujewar daulolin kasar Hausa da dama. Dangantakar kundin nasa da wannan bincike kawai shi ne kasancewar dukkanninsu biyu sun taɓo batu kan sauye-sauyen da ke aukuwa sakamakon sauyin zamani. Akwai kuma kundin Akodu, (1985) inda ya yi magana kan sauye-sauye da aka samu ga rayuwar Maguzawa a

⁶⁷ Wannan ba shi ne kaɗai tsarin da ake bi wajen nazartar ayyukan da suka gabata ba. Akwai masana da ke da ra'ayin cewa ba za a raba ayyukan da aka nazarta zuwa rukunnai ba. A maimakon haka, za a bi tsarin shekaru ne (daga mafi daɗewa zuwa mafi sabunta). Daga cikin masana masu wannan ra'ayi akwai Fraenkel, (2003) da McCombes, (2020).

zamanance. 'Yar alakar da kundin yake da shi da wannan bincike ba ta wuce batun zamananci ba.

Aikin Sallau, (2009) ma na da 'yar alaka da wannan bincike kasancewar ya tabo batun sauye-sauyen da zamani ya samar ga sana'ar wanzanci. Aminu, (2015) kuwa ya mayar da hankali wajen nazartar nason al'adun Turawa a kan al'adun Hausawa musamman a lardin Sakkwato. Tarihin zuwan Turawa kuwa ba ya cika ba tare da an tabo batun sauye-sauyen zamani ba. Hakan ne kuma abin da ya alafanta shi da binciken da ake gudanarwa.

2.3.2 Kundayen Digiri na Biyu

Aikin Nasir (2009), ya kasance yunkuri irinsa na farko a fagen karatun Hausa inda aka samu gabatar da tatsuniya a zamanance cikin sigar katun (hoto mai motsi). Kundin nasa na da danganta da wannan aiki kasancewar dukansu biyu sun mayar da hankali kan Hausa a duniyar zamaninta.

A shekarar 2009, Almajir ya yi rubutu kan yadda abubuwan zamani suka yi tasiri kan rayuwar matasa Hausawa. Manya daga cikinsu sun shafi kafafen intanet ne. Daga ciki kuwa har da Fesbuk da Was'af a matsayin kafafen sadarwa. Akwai kuma kafafen da ke gurbata tarbiyya. Kundin Almajir na da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar dukansu sun shafi intanet da al'adun Hausawa. Duk da haka, Almajir bai mayar da hankali kan wakilcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba. Ya fi karkata kan nazarin yadda duniyar ta intanet ke shafar al'adun Hausawa, musaman matasa.

Mukoshy (2015), ya ya yi fokarin tattara wasu muhimman kalmomin kwamfuta musamman waƙanda suka shafi intanet tare da samar da fassarorinsu. Kalmomin da ya fassara sun haɗa da na intanet da na kwamfuta da na burauzozi da makamantansu. A shafi na 108, ya yi kira da cewa: “Ya kamata Hausawa su shiga cikin sha’anin nazarin fannin kwamfuta, su yi ruwa, su yi tsaki a dukkan ɓangarorinta.” Ya nuna ɓunkasa da matuƙar alfanu da tagomashin da harkar intanet da kwamfuta ke da shi a shafuka na 107-108.

Kundin Mukoshy na da da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar duka sun taɓo duniyar intanet. Bugu da ƙari, duka suna kira da faɗakar da Hausawa kan inganta matsayinsu a wannan duniya ta intanet. Duk da haka, ayyukan biyu mabambanta ne. Mukoshy ya mayar da hankali ne kan fassarawa da adana kalmomin fannu da suka shafi intanet da kwamfuta. Wannan aiki kuwa ya karkata ne kan nazartar al’adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet da kira ga samar da wakilci nagartacce a duniyar.

Wani aikin da ke da dangantaka da wannan bincike shi ne na Magaji, (2018). Kundin ya bayyana cewa, hanyoyin sadarwar zamani sun yi tasiri a kan zumuncin Hausawa. Hanyoyin kuwa sun shafi kafafen intanet na sadarwa irin su Was’af da Facebook. Sanannen abu ne cewa zumunci na daga cikin ɓoyayyun al’adun Bahausha.⁶⁸ Kundin Magaji da wannan bincike suna da dangantaka kasancewar dukansu sun taɓo tasirin intanet a kan al’adun Hausawa. Duk da haka,

⁶⁸ Rubuce-rubuce da dama sun tabbatar da “tarbiyya” a matsayin ɗaya daga cikin ɓoyayyun al’adun Hausawa. Daga cikinsu akwai Tambuwal, (2018: 102) da Maikwari, (2020: 106).

kundin na Magaji ya takaita ne kawai a kan al'adar *zumunci*. Wannan bincike kuwa ya shafi al'adun Hausawa mabambanta da ake samu a duniyar intanet.

2.3.3 Kundayen Digiri na Farko

Masana da dama na da ra'ayin cewa binciken kundayen digiri na farko na da rauni. Duk da haka, wannan bincike ya ci karo da wasu kundayen digiri na farko da ke da matuƙar dangantaka da shi. A bisa haka an yi bitar su duk da raunin da suke da shi. Sun haɗa da:

Makuwana (2011), ya nazarci yadda Hausa ta yaɗu a duniyar intanet. Yaɗuwar ta haɗa da kafafen intanet daban-daban da kuma kafafen sada zumunta. Abin da ya bambanta kundin da wannan bincike shi ne, Makuwana ya mayar da hankali ne kan nazartar bunkasar Hausa a duniyar intanet. Wannan bincike kuwa zai bibiyi al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet tare da nazarin hanyoyin inganta su.

Ashiru (2012), ya rubuta kundin digiri na farko wanda ke da matuƙar dangantaka da wannan bincike. A ciki an nazarci hanyoyi daban-daban da adabin Hausawa ke bunkasa a dalilin intanet. Wannan ya haɗa da rubuce-rubucen adabi da ke kan kafafen intanet. Bugu da ƙari, akan ɗora waƙoƙin Hausa har ma da littattafai da aka karanta a matsayin odiyo. A takaice, kundin ya mayar da hankali kan yaɗuwar adabin Hausawa a intanet tamkar dai yadda wannan bincike ya dukufa wajen nazartar al'adun Hausawa a intanet ɗin. Wannan bincike bai takaita ga nazartar adabin Hausa a duniyar intanet ba kawai.

Aikin 'Yartsakuwa (2017), ya mayar da hankali wajen nazartar sadarwa a kafar intanet ta Whatsapp. Daga shafi na 15 zuwa na 17, an kawo tarihin intanet. A shafi na 37, an kawo illolin intanet kan al'adun Hausawa. Illolin sun fi shafar gurbata tarbiyya da bata lokaci. Kundin na da alaka da wannan bincike musamman la'akari da cewa dukansu sun mayar da hankali kan al'adun Hausawa da duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, kundin 'Yartsakuwa ya fi karkata kan sadarwa a intanet. Bai bibiyi matsayin al'adun Hausawa a ciki ba. Bai kuma yi nazarin hanyoyin inganta su ba.

2.3.4 Mujallu da Mukalu

Almajir (2008), ya rubuta makala wadda ta mayar da hankali kan nazartar matsayin Hausawa a duniyar intanet da yadda ake amfani da ita wajen sadarwa. Sadarwa da Hausa ya shafi kafafen intanet na sada zumunta daban-daban. Bambancin makalar da wannan bincike shi ne, Almajir ya bibiyi Hausa ne da kuma al'amarin sadarwa cikin Harshen Hausa a duniyar intanet. Wannan bincike kuwa zai mayar da hankali kan intanet da al'adun Hausawa.

Amfani (2010), ya rubuta kan kalmomin intanet na Hausa. A ciki ya kawo kalmomi da dama da ake amfani da su a harshen Hausa waɗanda suka shafi intanet. Hakika makalar ta Amfani na da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar duk sun taɓo intanet da kuma Hausawa. Duk da haka suna da bambanci domin binciken nasa ya takaita ne a kadadar harshen Hausa. Wannan

bincike kuwa ya fi mayar da hankali kan zawarcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

A shekarar 2013 an fitar da gagarumin aiki da ya shafi al'ada da zamananci. Hukumar Raya Tarihi da Al'adu ta Jahar Katsina (*Katsina State History and Culture Bureau*) ita ce ta gudanar da gagarumin taron kara wa juna sani tare da hadin guiwar Jami'ar Umaru Musa 'Yar'aduwa, Katsina. An tattara mukalun da aka gabatar yayin wannan taro inda aka wallafa su a matsayin babban kundi a watan Yuni na shekarar 2013. Littafin ya kunshi mukalu da ke da alaƙa da wanna aiki. Daga cikinsu akwai Adamu, (2013)⁶⁹ da Ahmad, (2013)⁷⁰ da Garba, (2013)⁷¹ da Getso, (2013)⁷² da Guibi, (2013)⁷³ da Isah, (2013)⁷⁴ da Kiyawa, (2013)⁷⁵ da

⁶⁹ Ya fito da gudummuwar shirye-shiryen gidan radiyon Muryar Jama'a, Kano wajen kare taɓarɓarewar al'adun Hausawa. Ya fi mayar da hankali kan shirin 'Aiki Da Hankali' da 'Tamburan Kano.' Bai taɓo al'adun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁷⁰ Ya nazarci ire-iren tasirin da wayar salula ta samar a kan al'adun Hausawa. Za a iya lura da cewa, bai mayar da hankali wajen nazartar al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

⁷¹ Ya duba yanayin auren zoben Bahausha a karni na 21. Ya dora gidan Rediyon Rahama 97.3 FM a faifan al'ada. Shi ma wannan bai taɓo al'adun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁷² Ya nazarci irin rawar da kafafen yada labarai ke takawa wajen bunƙasawa ko ruguza al'adun Hausawa. Shi ma wannan bai taɓo al'adun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁷³ Ya nazarci rawar da kafafen yada labarai ke takawa kan al'adun Hausawa. Suna iya bunƙasa su ko su janyo taɓarɓarwarsu. Shi ma wannan bai taɓo al'adun Hausawa a cikin duniyar intanet ba.

⁷⁴ Ya taƙaita nazarinsa kan rawar da gidan rediyon Companion FM 104.5 Mhz Katsina ke takawa wajen bunƙasa al'adun Hausawa

⁷⁵ Aikin ya taƙaita kan nazartar tasirin finafinai kan tarbiyyar Bahausha.

Mai'aduwa, (2013)⁷⁶ da Mwami, (2013)⁷⁷ da Shehu, (2013)⁷⁸ da Sulaiman, (2013)⁷⁹ da Umar, (2013).⁸⁰

Mukoshy da Umar (2014), sun rubuta makala da ta mayar da hankali wajen nazartar yadda za a iya bunkasa karatun Hausa ta hanyar amfani da intanet. Sun bayyana yadda intanet ke taimakawa a harkar ilimi, musamman abin da ya shafi dakunan karatu bisa intanet da mujallun da ke kan intanet da makamantansu. Mukalar ta Mukoshy da Umar na da dangantaka da wannan bincike musamman idan aka duba kiran da suka yi cewa: "Mukalar tana kira ga dalibai da manazarta Hausa da su kara fokari wajen amfani da intanet wajen taskace sahihan bayanai domin bunkasa bincike da nazarin harshen Hausa" (Mukoshy da Umar, 2014: 10). Ko da ma dai, manufar wannan bincike shi ne nazartar al'adun Hausawa cikin duniyar intanet da kuma hanyoyi da matakan da za su iya taimakawa wajen inganta su. Ayyukan biyu sun bambanta ta fuskar farfajiya da manufar bincike.

Mukoshy (2016), ya gudanar da bincike inda ya yi fokarin bayyana wasu hanyoyin kasuwanci da hada-hada a duniyar intanet wadanda za su iya taimaka wa tattalin arzikin Hausawa. Sun hada da kasuwanci a intanet, da biyan kudi ta intanet. Makalar Mukoshy na da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar

⁷⁶ Shi ma wannan nazari ya takaita kan nazartar tasirin finafinai kan tarbiyyar Bahaushu.

⁷⁷ Ya nazarci yadda finafinai ke haifar da tabarbarwar tarbiyyar Hausawa. Ya nuna cewa wannan ya kara ruruta wutar samuwar daba.

⁷⁸ Wannan nazari ya kebanta kan duba tasirin wasannin kwaikwayon gidajen rediyo wajen bunkasa al'adun Hausawa. Ya fi mayar da hankali kan shirin 'Duniya Budurwar Wawa' da 'Jami'iyar Jatau Na Albarkawa.'

⁷⁹ Takardar ta nazarci tasirin finafinai wajen gurbata tarbiya, musamman abin da ya danganci fyade.

⁸⁰ Marubuciyar ta nazarci wata addu'ar da 'yammata ke yi wadda ta yadu a cikin wayar salula. Ta nuna cewa, zamananci ya yi tasiri a kan al'amarin zaɓen mijin aure a yau.

dukansu sun shafi Hausawa da duniyar intanet. Duk da haka, Mukoshy bai mayar da hankali wajen nazartar al'adun Hausawa da matakan inganta su a duniyar intanet ba.

Shehu da Aliyu (2019), sun rubuta makala wadda ta mayar da hankali wajen nazartar illolin wayar salula a kan al'adun Hausawa. Daga ciki har da al'adun da suka shafi zamantakewar aure. Daga shafin 708 zuwa 710, takardar ta bibiyi yadda shafukan intanet ke gurbata tarbiyya. Ta fi mayar da hankali a kan shafukan Fesbuk da Was'ap.

Makalar Shehu da Aliyu na da matufar dangantaka da wannan bincike. Dukansu biyu sun taɓo al'adun Hausawa da kuma intanet. Duk da haka, makalar tasu ba ta mayar da hankali kan nazartar hanyoyin da za a bunkasa tare da inganta al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Shehu da Rambo (2019), sun rubuta makala wadda ta yi kokarin fito da yadda kafar intanet ta Was'af ke lalata tarbiyyar Hausawa. A shafi na 359, sun kawo ire-iren sakonni da ake iya turawa ta kafar Was'af. Sun hada da rubutu da sautin magana da kuma bidiyo. Daga nan sai suka mayar da hankali wajen bayyana hanyoyin da wannan kafar intanet ke gurbata tarbiyyar Hausawa. Hakan ne kuma ya samar da dangantaka tsakanin makalar tasu da wannan bincike. Dukansu biyu sun shafi intanet da al'adun Hausawa. Duk da haka, Shehu da Rambo ba su nazarci al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba. Bayan haka, ba su nazarci

hanyoyin da za a iya bi domin inganta wakilcin al'adun Hausawan a duniyar intanet ba. Wannan bincike kuwa, hakan ne manufarsa.

2.3.5 Jaridu da Intanet

Adamu (2000), ya yi rubutu cikin harshen Ingilishi a kan harshe da al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. An buga ta a cikin jaridar *Weekly Trust* ta ranar 20 ga watan Nuwamba, shekarar 2020. A ciki ya bibiyi yaduwar rubuce-rubuce da al'adun Hausawa da yadda suke a intanet. Kai tsaye rubutun nasa na da dangantaka da wannan bincike musamman da yake sun tabo al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

Abubakar (2007), ya rubuta makala da aka buga a cikin Aminiya ta ranar ɗaya ga watan Maris, shekarar 2007. Ya mayar da hankali wajen fito da tasirin intanet a ɓangarorin rayuwar al'umma. Wannan ya haɗa da kasuwanci da ilimi da sauran ɓangarorin rayuwa. Rubutun nasa na da dangantaka da wannan bincike kasancewar dukansu biyu sun shafi hada-hadar duniyar intanet. Duk da haka suna da manufofi mabambanta. Abubakar ya mayar da hankali ne kan danganta harkokin rayuwa a zamanance da kuma intanet. Wannan bincike kuwa ya karkata kan zawarcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet tare da nazartan hanyoyi da matakan inganta su.

Ko bayan waɗannan ayyuka da ke da alaƙa ta kusa da binciken, an nazarci wasu ayyukan waɗanda za su iya taimakawa wajen kammaluwarsa cikin nasara. Ayyukan sun kasance masu dangantaka ta nesa da wannan bincike. Sun shafi

fannonin kwamfuta da intanet da sauran fasahohin zamani masu dangantaka da waƙannan. Daga cikinsu akwai Akibu, (2001) da Adamu, (2004) da Guifi, (2006) da Sambo, (2009).

2.4 Hujjar Ci Gaba da Bincike

A binciken Mukoshy an nazarci ayyukan masana da manazarta, sannan aka fitar da sakamakon da ke cewa: “Hausa tana da kyakkyawar safiya. Sai dai, matuƙar ana son wannan harshe ya ci gaba da haskakawa, dole masana su taskace sababbin kalmomi na sha’anin kwamfuta da intanet da kuma sauran bangarorin da ci gaban zamani ya kawo. Saboda haka Hausawa su shiga a dama da su a kowane ɓangare na amfani da kwamfuta da intanet” (Mukoshy, 2015: X). Wannan gaƙarumar yekuwa ce da ke da buƙatar gudummuwar manazarta a wannan fannin. Wani abin lura kuma shi ne, ba a samu wani aiki da ya nazarci al’adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba.

Hatta ayyukan da suke da makusanciyar dangantaka da wannan bincike (waƙanda aka yi bita a baya), za a tarar da cewa sun bambanta ta fuskar manufa. Misali, aikin Almajir, (2008) na “Hausa da Sadarwar Intanet,” bai mayar da hankali kan matakan inganta wakilcin al’adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba. Haka ma Makuwana, (2011) ya fi mayar da hankali kan nazartar yaƙuwar da Hausa ta yi a duniyar intanet kawai. A tafaice ke nan, an samu dalilin ci gaba da wannan bincike kasancewar babu wani aiki da aka ci karo da shi wanda ya cike gurabun da wannan bincike ke da muradin cikewa.

2.5 Nadewa

An dade ana gudanar da bincike a kan intanet da dangantakarsa da harshe da kuma al'adun al'umma, ciki har da Hausawa. Hakan ya biyo bayan dumbin tasirin da intanet din ke da shi ga rayuwar al'umma a yau. Binciken masana da manazarta da suka gabata da dama sun yi kira da a nazarci al'amarin intanet sosai domin shiga cikin jerin al'ummun da ke cin gajiyarsa. Da alama manazarta da daliban ilimi sun amsa wannan kira ganin yadda aka ci karo da ayyuka da dama a wannan fanni. Duk da haka, akwai gurbin da ba a cike ba wanda ya shafi zawarcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet tare da nazarin hanyoyin samar musu wakilci mai inganci.

BABI NA UKU

BUNKASAR AL'ADUN HAUSAWA A DUNIYAR INTANET

3.0 Shimfida

Abubuwan amfani na yau da kullum⁸¹ na tasiri a kan al'adun Hausawa. Al'amura da ke wanzuwa a duniyar intanet na da kwatankwacin wannan tasirin. Idan aka dora wannan batu kan Pulatoriyya, sai ya kasance cewa, al'adun Hausawa na samun tasiri iri biyu. Na farko shi ne sauye-sauyen zamani a duniyar zahiri. Na biyu kuwa sauye-sauye da ake samu a duniyar intanet. Wannan babi na uku ya bibiyi bangarorin al'adun Hausawa da intanet ya yi tasiri a kansu. Wannan tasiri na faruwa ne yayin da ta kasance cewa mutane (Hausawa) na ta'ammuli da al'amuran da suka shafi bangarorin rayuwa daban-daban a intanet. Misali, mata na iya daukar samfuran abinci daga intanet domin su dafa ire-irensu lokacin bukukuwa. Haka ma, matasa na iya daukar samfuran suturu da suka ci karo da su a intanet. A bisa wannan dalili, za a fara duba yaduwar al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet kafin a tunkari bayyana amfanin intanet da kuma aibinsa.

3.1 Intanet da Taskace Al'adu

Idan ana maganar al'adu a jimlace, kafar intanet ta kasance taska ta al'adu. Wannan ba sabon abu ba ne. Tuni kafafen intanet suka kasance wani bagire da ake rubuce-rubuce dangane da al'adu. Ko bayan rubuce-rubuce, akwai hotuna da bidiyoyi dangane da al'adun al'ummomi daban-daban. Wannan ya haɗa da

⁸¹ Misali ababen hawa da tufafi da kwamfutoci da gine-gine.

bayyanannu da boyayyun al'adu. A matakin duniya, abubuwan da ake samu dangane da al'adu a kafafen intanet sun haɗa da:

- a. Akan ci karo da samfuran abinci daban-daban. Sun haɗa da abincin bukukuwa da na otel-otel da abincin yau da kullum waɗanda ake samu a gidaje.
- b. Akan sanya hotunan tufafi. Akan kuma ci karo da nau'ukan tufafi daban-daban cikin bidiyoyi a kafafen intanet.
- c. Akan ci karo da gine-gine nau'uka daban-daban. Gine-ginen na kasancewa cikin hotuna da bidiyoyi.
- d. Har ila yau, a intanet akan ci karo da wasannin gargajiyar al'ummu daban-daban. Su ma sukan kasance cikin hotuna da bidiyoyi.
- e. Bugu da kari, akan ci karo da bukukuwan al'ummu mabambanta a kafafen intanet.
- f. Nau'ukan kitso da na aski ma ba a bar su a baya ba. Akwai kafafen intanet da ke kawo hotuna da bidiyoyinsu.

A takaice duk wata al'ada da aka sani ta mutane, akan samu kafafen intanet da ke kawo su. Wannan ba abin mamaki ba ne idan aka yi la'akari da yawan adadin kafafen intanet na duniya (sama da biliyan 1.72). Dangane da al'adun Hausawa kuwa, su ma akan samu da dama a kafafen intanet. An kawo misalai a 3.2 da ke kasa.

3.2 Intanet da Al'adun Hausawa

Tuni hankalin masana da manazarta ya kai kan tasirin intanet a kan al'adun Hausawa. A wasu lokutan sukan yi rubutu da ke nuna wannan tasiri kai tsaye. A wasu lokuta kuwa, akan tsinci batun ne yayin da suke tattauna tasirin zamananci kan al'adun Hausawa. Ko ba komai dai, intanet na ɗaya daga cikin manyan abubuwan da zamani ya zo da su, waɗanda kuma suke da matuƙar tasiri a rayuwar al'umma. Wannan ne ya ja hankalin Clement, (2020: 1) inda ya nuna cewa tuni intanet ya zama wani ɓangare na rayuwar al'umma.⁸²

Abin lura a nan shi ne, yawancin ayyukan da aka gudanar a kan wannan batu sun karkata ne zuwa ga bayyana illolin intanet a kan al'adun Hausawa. Babban misali a nan shi ne, aikin Shehu da Rambo, (2019) mai taken: "Shafin Zumunta na Was'af (Whatsapp): Tasirinsa ga Lalacewar Tarbiyyar 'Ya'yan Hausawa." Kai tsaye sun dubi yadda wannan shafi ke kai wa ga taɓarbarewar al'adun al'ummar Hausawa musamman tarbiyya. Wannan bincike kuwa zai rika bugin jiki yana bugun taiki. Babban burinsa shi ne nazartar tasirin intanet ɗin a kan al'adun Hausawa. Wannan tasiri na iya kasancewa mai kyau ko marar kyau.

Domin jin daɗin tattauna batun (bunƙasar al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet), ba za a yi wa al'adun kaɗar 'ya'yan kaɗanya ba. Maikwari, (2020: 29) ya bayyana cewa: "Masana da dama sun raba al'adun Hausawa zuwa gida biyu." Kason biyu su ne (i) Bayyananniyar al'ada (fasahar hannu) da (ii) Boyayyiyar al'ada (fasahar

⁸² A duba Clement, (2020: 1) a 1.1 (Dalilin Bincike) da ke babi na ɗaya na wannan bincike.

baka). Za a yi amfani da wannan rabo yayin tattauna yaduwar al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

3.2.1 Intanet da Bayyanannun Al'adun Hausawa (Fasahar Hannu)

Bayyanannun al'adu sun shafi dukkanin al'adun da idanu ke iya kallon su. Sun haɗa da wasannin gargajiya da abinci da gine-gine da sana'o'i da suturu da magunguna da bukukuwa da dazuka da koguna. Za a dauki waɗannan al'adu dalla-dalla domin zawarcinsu a duniyar intanet.

3.2.1.1 Intanet da Wasannin Hausawa

Wasa dai na nufin duk wata magana da aka furta ko wani aiki da aka aikata da nufin raha da nishadi. Kamusun Ingilishi na kamfanin Google ya ba da ma'anar wasa da cewa: *"an activity that one engages in for amusement or fun."*⁸³ Abin da yake nufi shi ne "duk wani abin da mutum ke aikatawa domin samun nishadi." Yayin da aka ce wasannin gargajiya kuwa, ana nufin wasannin Hausawa da suka kasance sanannu. Bayan haka, sun kasance na Hausa tsura ba waɗanda aka kwaikwaya daga bakin al'ummu ba. Daga cikinsu akwai waɗanda suke da takamaimai wuri da lokacin aiwatarwa, wasu kuma har da sanannun kayan aiki da ake amfani da su yayin gudanar da wasannin. Daga cikin wasannin gargajiya na Hausawa akwai na furuci, wato waɗanda suka shafi magana. Sannan akwai wasannin kurma, wato waɗanda aikatawa ake yi ba tare da wani furuci ba.

⁸³ A duba:

<https://www.google.com/search?q=game+meaning&oq=game+meaning&aqs=chrome..69i57j0i512l9.3156j1j4&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>.

Wannan bincike ya ci karo da wasannin Hausawa daban-daban a duniyar intanet.

Sun kasance ta fuskoki mabambanta. Daga ciki akwai:

- i. Rubuce-rubuce dangane da wasannin Hausawa
- ii. Hotounan wasannin Hausawa
- iii. Bidiyoyin wasannin Hausawa.

Hoto 3.1: 'Yara Mata na Gudanar da Tashe

Madogara: Arewa24, (2018) *Tashe Ep 5*

Hoto na 3.1 da ke sama ya kasance na wasan tashe. A ciki za a ga 'yara mata sun shafe fuskarsu da farin alli. An dauko wannan hoto daga bidiyon da aka dora a kafar intanet ta Yutub. Hakika wannan wata hanya ce ta adana wasannin Hausawa na gargajiya tare da koyar da yadda ake yin su ga masu kallo.

Hoto 3.2: Wasan Langa

Madogara: Abubakar, da Ladan, (2019: 1)

A hoto na 3.2 da ke sama, za a iya kallon matasa na wasar langa. Wannan dadadden wasan Hausawa ne. Hakika ire-iren wadannan na taimakawa wajen adana al'adun wasanni da yanzu haka suka dumashe, har suna fofarin facewa gaba daya.

3.2.1.2 Intanet da Abincin Hausawa

Bai zama laifi ba, idan aka fadi cewa kalmar abinci ba arariyar kalma ba ce daga kowane harshe. Dalilan fadin haka sun hada da kasancewar abinci daya daga cikin abubuwa na farko da dan'adam zai fara cudanya da shi yayin da ya zo duniya. Wannan na nuna cewa, dole ne ya samar wa kansa sunan da yake ambaton wannan abu da shi. Baya ga haka, kalmar abinci ta fi kama da hadaka na kalmomi guda biyu, wato abu da kuma ci. Za ta iya yuwuwa Hausawa sun fara ambaton sunan abinci ne da furucin: "abin da za a ci" ko "abin da ake ci." Sannu a hankali har aka gajarce shi zuwa abinci. Ohio Department of Taxation (ODT) sun ba da ma'anar abinci a shekarar 2004 a matsayin duk wani abu da: "... mutane ke hadiyewa ko taunawa sannan ana cin su ne domin dandanonsu ko amfaninsu a

jiki.”⁸⁴ Ma’anar ta ODT ta yi kama da ma’anar da aka samar a kafar Rumbun Ilimi inda suka ce abinci: “shi ne dukkan abin da za a ci sannan kuma ya bai wa jiki sinadaran da yake bukata domin samun karfi” (Rumbun Ilimi, ND: 1).

Wannan bincike ya ci karo da kafar intanet wanda aka gina ta sukutum a kan abincin Hausawa. Duka kumshiyar kafar ya karkata ne kan abinci. Hakan ne ma ya sanya sunan kafar ya kasance *abinci* (<https://abinci.com/>). Kafar na matuƙar kofari wajen dora hotunan abincin Hausawa tare da takaitaccen tsokaci game da yadda ake sarrafa su. A hoto na 3.3 da ke kasa an kawo misali:

Hoto 3.3: Hoton Masa a Matsayin Abincin Hausawa

Madogara: Abincin Hausawa, (2015: 1).

Masa sanannen nau’in abinci ne a kasar Hausa. A cikin hoto na 3.3 da ke sama, za a iya lura cewa da akwai tasirin zamani kan wannan nau’in abinci. Na farko dai

⁸⁴ “... ingestion or chewing by humans and are consumed for their taste or nutritional value.”

kullin masar kanta ta shinkafa ce a maimakon gero. Zainab,⁸⁵ (2020) ta bayyana cewa, da wuya a iya hasashen lokacin da Bahaushe ya fara masar shinkafa “domin kuwa dadadɗen al’amari ne.” Bayan haka, tanderun masar ya kasance na dalma a maimakon na kasa/laka da ake da shi a gargajiyan. Na uku, da cokalin silba ake amfani wajen juya masar a maimakon kalaba ko tsintsiya.⁸⁶ Koma dai yaya abin yake, tuni wannan nau’in masa ya nashe cikin gargajiyar Bahaushe.

3.2.1.3 Intanet da Gine-Ginen Hausawa

Gini na ɗaya daga cikin muhimman bayyanannun al’adu. A wannan bangare ma, Hausa ta samu tagomashi. Akwai kafafen intanet daban-daban da suke ɗauke da hotuna da bidiyoyin gine-ginen Hausawa. A duba misali a hoto na 3.4 da ke kasa:

Hoto 3.4: Hoton Fadar Katagum (Azare)

Madogara: Azare Online, (2020: 1)

⁸⁵ An yi hira da ita ranar 13 ga watan Maris, shekarar 2020. Tana da kimanin shekara 75 da duniya. Bayan haka, ta yi sana’o’i da jaura daban-daban, ciki har da masar sayarwa.

⁸⁶ Bunza, (2021) ya tabbatar wa wannan bincike cewa Bahaushe ya fara amfani da tsintsiya ne wajen juya masa. Daga baya ne ya koma amfani da kalaba.

A zuwa lokacin da aka bincika kafar intanet ta *Azare Online*, hoton Katagum (Azare) ne ke matsayin babban hoton shafin farko (home page picture). Kafar intanet ta Amsoshi ta kawo kwatankwacin wannan hoton. Sai dai ita fadar Sakkwato da Katsina da Kano ta kawo.⁸⁷ Za a iya lura da cewa, ginin fadar na zamani ne. Ma'ana ba tun ginin gargajiya aka adana ba. Ba makawa hakan na da nasaba da kasancewar a da babu wadatuwar kafafen intanet na Hausa.⁸⁸ Bayan gine-ginen zamani na Hausawa, akan ci karo kuma da na gargajiya. A duba misali da hoton da ke kasa:

Hoto 3.5: Hoton Ginin Hausawa na Gargajiya

Madogara: Dan Zubair, (2017: 1)

A hoto na 3.5 da ke sama, za a ga cewa gini ne na gargajiya. An kuma kawata shi sosai da yake ginin sarauta ne. Hakika ana da ire-iren wadannan gine-ginen tarihi

⁸⁷ Domin kallon hoton fadar Sakkwato, ana iya duba Bunza, (2020: 1).

⁸⁸ Idan ba a dauki mataakai da suka dace ba, abu mai sauƙi ne tarihi ya maimaita kansa. Idan kuwa aka mayar da hankali wajen samar da kyakkyawan wakilcin Hausa da Hausawa a duniyar intanet, tarihi cikin rubuce-rubuce da hotuna da bidiyoyi zai kasance a adane har Mahadi.

zai kasance mai amfani a nan gaba. A 3.5b da ke kasa ma za a iya kallon ginin gargajiya:

Hoto 3.5b: Ginin Hausa Na Gargajiya

Madogara: Yusuf, (2017: 1)

3.2.1.4 Intanet da Sana'o'in Hausawa

“A san mutum a san sana'arsa” in ji Hausawa. “Sana'a” ba Bahaushiyar kalma ba ce. An aro ta ne daga Larabci. A larabci tana nufin “aiki.” Sallau, (*edita*) (ND) na da ra'ayin cewa “Bayan tafiya ta yi tafiya sai ma'anar kalmar a wurin Bahausha ta kara faɗaɗa har ta kunshi duk wani aiki da za a yi don gudanar da wani abu da za a musanya a tsakanin daidaiƙun al'umma ko rukunin jama'a.” Sana'a kuwa in ji Newman, (1977: 177) ita ce “abin da mutum yake yi don sabawa kamar gini.” Akwai bayanai sosai game da sano'o'in Hausawa daban-daban a duniyar intanet. A kafar intanet mai suna *Al'ummar Hausawa*, Musa, (2019: 1) ya rubuta makala mai taken: “Sana'ar Kiyoyi a Kasar Hausa.” A ciki ya sanya hoton kaza da 'yan tsakinta. A duba hoto na 3.6 da ke kasa:

Hoto 3.6: Kaza da ‘Yan Tsakinta

Madogara: Musa, (2019: 1)

A tarihin tattalin arziki da sana’o’in Bahaushe, kiwo na da gurbi na musamman. Har ila yau, kiwon kaji sanannen al’amari ne a gidajen Bahaushe. A inda aka fito, da wuya a samu wani gidan Bahaushe da ba a kiwon kaji. Akwai sanannen kirarin nan da ake yi wa kiwon kaji cewa: “Yar karamar dukiya da babbar riba.”

3.2.1.5 Intanet da Suturun Hausawa

“Sutura ita ce mutum” in ji Hausawa. Jaridar Leadership 29 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2019 ta samar da fassarar wani rubutu da aka yi cikin harshen Ingilishi mai taken “*Sociology of Writing.*” A ciki an nuna yadda sutura ta kasance wata shaida da za a iya gane mutane da ita. A fahimtar marubutan, shi tufafi “wani abu ne wanda al’umma ta samar da shi, kuma me dauke da ma’anar da ke daidaita

yanayin mu'amala, ciki kuwa har da samar da yanayin da ake kallon abu a matsayin ado"⁸⁹

Wannan bincike ya ci karo da tufafin Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Sun fi yawa a kafar intanet din nan mai suna *Hausa Weddings*⁹⁰ (Auratayyar Hausawa). Dalili kuwa shi ne, kafar ta shahara ne wajen daukar hotuna da bidiyoyin auratayyar Hausawa tare da dora su duniyar intanet. A kasa an kawo misalin suturun Hausawa wanda aka dauko a intanet:

Hoto 3.7: Hoton Hausawa Cikin Ado Bisa Dawaki

Madogara: Shehu da Sani (2020: 1)

A hoto na 3.7 da ke sama, za a ga cewa Hausawa ne cikin ado bisa dawakai. Su ma dawakan an caba musu ado. Hakika wannan yayata al'adu ne na Hausawa. Dalili kuwa shi ne, al'ummomi daga wasu yankuna na duniya na iya kallon wannan

⁸⁹ A duba: <https://hausa.leadership.ng/ado-darussa-daga-sociology-of-fashion/>.

⁹⁰ Domin nazartar wannan kafar intanet, ana iya bin: <https://hausaweddings.com/>.

hoto ta kafafen intanet. Idan aka duba hoto da ke kasa kuwa (3.7b), za a ga Hausawa maza cikin tufafin Hausawa.

Hoto 3.7b: Hausawa Cikin Tufafin Gargajiya

Madogara: Wikiwand, (ND: 1)

3.2.1.6 Intanet da Magungunan Hausawa

Magani dadadden al'amari ne. Hasashen farkon samuwar magani ga wata al'umma daidai yake da hasashen farkon samuwar cuta ga al'ummar. Farkon samuwar cuta ga al'umma kuwa daidai yake da farkon kasantuwarisu a raye. Dalili shi ne, hasashe ya nuna ba a taɓa wani lokaci da ɗan'adam ba ya tare da cuta ba. Ko da babu cutar rashin lafiya, akwai ta zuciya wadda kuwa ba a samun kwanciyar hankali har sai an cimma muradin zuci.

Bargery, (1933: 743) ya ce: "Magani yana nufin riga-kafi da kariyar cuta."

Dangane da cuta kuwa, Gobir, (2012) ya tabbatar da cewa ta haɗa da ta jiki da ta zuciya. Ya kawo hakan cikin ma'anar magani da ya bayar. Ya ce: "Hanya ce ta

kawar da, ko kwantar da, duk wata cuta ta jiki ko ta zuciya, ko neman daukaka, ko kariya daga makaru da jifa da sihiri ko siddabaru.” Gobir, (2012: 224).⁹¹⁹²

Hoto 3.8: Magungunan Gargajiya

Madogara: Adamu, (2020: 1)

A hoto na 3.8 da ke sama, za a iya kallon magungunan gargajiya nau’uka daban-daban. A ciki akwai sassafe da ciyayi da jijiyoyi da gari da kuma sassan dabbobi. Hakifa wannan ma wani mataki ne na yayata al’adun Hausawa.

3.2.1.7 Intanet da Bukukuwan Hausawa

Buki na daya daga cikin al’adun Bahaushe masu jan hankali. “Buki dai wani taro ne da Hausawa kan yi domin nuna farin ciki a kan faruwar abin murna, ko domin gudanar da wani muhimmin abu da ya shafi rayuwarsu” Shehu, a cikin Maikwari,

⁹¹ Ko kafin wannan ma’ana da kuma bayanta, masana da dama sun bayyana ma’anar magani. Daga cikinsu akwai Tukur, (1988: 134) da Bunza, (1995: 135) da Sarkin Gulbi, (2014: 5).

⁹² Domin karin bayani kan magunguna ana iya duba Bunza, (1990) da Abubakar, (1997), Mahmud, (1997) da Adamu, (1998) da Gobir, (2002) da Bunza, (2004) da Bunza, (2005) da Ayad, (2008) da Sallau, (2010) da Sarkin Gulbi, (2014) da Gobir & Sani, (2017) da Gobir & Sani, (2018)².

(2020: 45).⁹³ Akwai kafar intanet sukutum wanda aka gina kan auratayyar Hausawa. Wannan kafa na da suna *Hausa Weddings*, wato *Auratayyar Hausawa*. A ciki, akan samu hotuna da bidiyoyi na auratayyar Hausawa daban-daban. A kasa an kawo hoton shafin farko na wannan kafa:

Hoto 3.9: Kafar Intanet Takamaimai Kan Auratayyar Hausawa

Madogara: Shafin farko na *Hausa Weddings*: <https://hausaweddings.com/>

Hoto na 3.9 da ke sama ya kasance na shafin farko na kafar *Hausa Weddings*. A tsakiyar hoton za a iya lura da tambarin kafar. Tambarin ya kasance hannun mace da aka caba wa ado. Da zarar an kalla, abu na farko da zai zo ga zuciyar mai kallon shi ne “amarya.”⁹⁴ Idan aka yi amfani da ire-iren waɗannan kafafe ta

⁹³ Wannan ma’ana ta Shehu na da matuƙar kama da ma’anar buki wanda Gusau ya bayar. Ya ce: “Buki ana yin sa don a nuna irin farin cikin da ake da shi ga wani abin farin ciki da ya faru, ko don tunawa da wani abu muhimmi ko don zagayowar wata rana. Biki ko bukukuwa suna daga cikin fitattun al’adun Hausawa waɗanda suka sami asali tun daga kaka da kakanni.” Gusau, (2012: 26). Domin farin bayani a kan bukukuwa ana iya duba Ibrahim, (1981) da Abu, (1985) da Ibrahim, (1985) da Muhammad, (1998) da Gwarjo *da wasu*, (2005) da Rambo, (2007) da Abdullahi, (2008) da Funtuwa da Gusau, (2010) da Guau, (2012) da Bunza, (2013) da Hassan, (2013) da Gada, (2014).

⁹⁴ Da zarar an ga amarya kuwa, abin da zai zo zuciyar shi ne “bukin aure.” Babajo, (2001: 12) ya rawaito Alhasan na cewa: “Aure alaƙa ce ta halaccin zaman tare tsakanin namiji da mace. Ana yin sa ne saboda abin da aka haifa ya sami asali da mutunci da daukaka da kiwon iyaye.” Domin farin bayani kan auratayyar Hausawa ana iya duba Ibrahim, (1985) da Rambo, (2007) da Faruk, (2011).

hanyoyi da suka dace, lallai za su taimaka wajen haɓaka Hausa da yayata ta, tare da kundace al'adunta.

3.2.2 Intanet da Boyayyun Al'adun Hausawa (Fasahar Baka)

Rukuni na biyu a rabe-raben al'adu ya shafi "boyayyun al'adu." Maikwari, (2020: 45) ya bayyana ma'anar boyayyun al'adu da cewa:

Boyayyar al'ada ita ce nau'in al'ada da ta shafi abubuwan da ba a iya gani ko tabawa, a maimakon haka, sai dai kwakwalwa ta fahimce su kawai. Wadannan abubuwa sun shafi halaye da dabi'u al'umma kawai (Maikwari, 2020: 45)

A takaice ke nan, boyayyiyar al'ada ta shafi sababbiyar amintacciyar hanyar gudanar da rayuwa wadda ba bayyananniya ba. Duk al'amuran da suka shafi tunani da basira da ladabi da biyayya da zamantakewa suna karkashin boyayyiyar al'ada ne. Wannan nau'in al'ada ma ba a bar shi a baya ba wajen shiga duniyar intanet. Akan samu al'amuran da suka shafi zamantakewa da tarihin Hausawa. Kai tsaye kafar intanet din nan mai suna *Tsangayar Adabin Hausa* ta buga a shafinta na farko cewa: "Tsangayar Da Ta Himmatu Wajen Kulawa Da Killacewa Da Taskace Abubuwan Da Suka Shafi Adabi Da Zamantakewar Al'ummar Hausawa."⁹⁵

A ɓangare guda kuwa, kafafen intanet da dama na fokari wajen kawo tarihin Hausa da Hausawa. Babban misali a nan shi ne kafar intanet mai suna *Rumbun*

⁹⁵ A duba shafin farko na Tsangayar Adabin Hausa: <http://tsangayaradabi.blogspot.com/>.

Ilimi (<https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng/tarihi.html>). A kasa (hoto na 3.10) an kawo misali:

Hoto 3.10: Tarihin Hausa da Hausawa a Kafar Intanet

Masarautu	Dauloli		Mashahuran Mutane
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kano • Daura • Dutse • Ilorin • Katsina • Pindiga • Zazzau 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usmaniyya • Damagaran • Kwararrafa • Birtaniya • Tarayyar Turai • Tarayyar 	<p>Kasashe</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Najeriya 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sir Ahmadu Bello • Tanko Yakasai • Adamu Chiroma • Danmasanin Kano • TY Danjuma • Alh. Atiku Abubakar

Madogara: Shafin tarihi a kan *Rumbun Ilimi*:

<https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng/tarihi.html>

A hoto na 3.10 da ke sama, za a iya ganin cewa illahirin kumshiyar shafin da aka dauko ya karkata ne kan tarihi. An rarraba tarihin zuwa rukunnai kamar haka:

- i. Tarihin masarautu
- ii. Tarihin dauloli
- iii. Tarihin kasashe
- iv. Tarihin shahararrun mutane

3.3 Amfanin Intanet ga Hausa da Hausawa

Kafafen intanet na da matuƙar amfani wajen haɓaka harshe da yayata shi. A babi na ɗaya, karkashin 1.1 (Dalilin Bincike), an nuna yadda al'amuran duniya a yau ba sa haɓaka har sai an haɗa da intanet. Masana da dama sun yi rubuce-rubuce dangane da tasirin intanet da zamananci a kan al'adun Hausawa. Daga ciki akwai aikin Almajir, (2009) da Muhammad, (2011) da Magaji, (2018) da Shehu da Aliyu, (2019) da Shehu da Rambo, (2019) da Usman da Bunza, (2020).

Abin lura a nan shi ne, mafi yawansu sun karkata ne kan fito da ire-iren illolin da intanet da zamananci ke da shi ga al'adun Hausawa. Duk da haka, akwai aikin da ya yi kokari matuka inda ya bugi jaki ya bugi taiki. Wannan aiki shi ne na 'Yartsakuwa, (2017). Aikin ya yi kokari matuka wajen zayyano amfani da kuma aibin kafafen intanet tsakanin shafi na 35-37. Wannan bincike ya nazarci ayyukan magabatan. Sakamakon ya nuna cewa, amfanin intanet ga Hausa da Hausawa sun hada da:

1. Samun Ilimi a Saukake

Daya daga cikin manyan alfanun intanet shi ne samun ilimi har gida. Ta hanyar amfani da intanet, mutum zai karanta nau'ukan rubuce-rubuce da dama yayin da yake kwance a dakinsa. Haka kuma, zai iya sauraron odiyo ko ya kalli bidiyoyi. Hakika wannan janyo nesa kusa ne tare da saukakawa. Misali, a shekarar 2020 da aka samu yaduwar cutar korona, kasashen duniya da dama sun komar da tsarin karatunsu kacokan zuwa kan intanet. Jami'o'in kasar Hausa ba su da wannan tsarin. Ko ba komai, Bahaushe ya ce: "Ba a fafe gora ranar tafiya."

Intanet kafa ce ta neman ilimi. Akwai makarantu da dama da suka kasance saman intanet. Dalibai za su yi rigista da irin wadannan makarantu daga duk wuraren da suke a fadin duniya. Za su rika daukar darusa ta intanet, su rubuta jinga ta intanet su kuma yi jarabawa ta intanet. Daga cikin irin wadannan makarantu akwai:

- a. Arizona State University-ASU Online

- b. Boston University. (Boston, Massachusetts)
- c. Indiana University-IU Online.
- d. Northeastern University
- e. Penn State World Campus. (State College, Pennsylvania)
- f. UMass Online. (Amherst, Massachusetts)
- g. University of Florida Distance Learning. (Gainesville, Florida)

Hausawa na iya morar wannan dama ta hanyar yin karatu a fasashen ketare ta kafar intanet. Baya ga haka, a yanzu haka akwai kafafen intanet na Hausa da suke fofarin samar da makarantu ta kafar intanet. Daga cikin masu wannan hobɓasa akwai masu gudanar da kafar Bakandamiya (<https://bakandamiya.com/>). Akwai kuma masu kafar Wikihausa waɗanda tuni suka fara koyar da kwasakwasai da suka haɗa da na koyan kwamfuta da girke-girke da sauran ɓangarorin ilimi da dama.⁹⁶ Bugu da ƙari, jami'ar Nijeriyar⁹⁷ nan wanda ke gudanar da harkokin karatunta ta kafar intanet ta sanya Hausa cikin jerin kwasa-kwasai da take koyarwa.⁹⁸

⁹⁶ Adreshin kafar Wikihausa shi ne: <https://wikihausa.com.ng/>.

⁹⁷ National Open University of Nigeria

⁹⁸ An samu wannan bayani a hirar da aka yi da Dr. Yahaya Idris a ofishinsa da ke Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usumanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.

2. Saukafawa

Saukafawa a nan bai takaita a kan sauƙin da mai karatu ke samu ba kadai. Yana nufin (i) Sauƙin da marubuci ke samu, inda yana iya dora rubuce-rubucensa bisa intanet. Wannan hanya ta fi sauƙi inda ba zai kashe kuɗin buga littafi mai yawa ba. (ii) Gwamnatoci da cibiyoyin ilimi na samun sauƙin dɔkar nauyin dɔkunan karatu. Bayan littattafan da ake tarawa da kundaye da sauran abubuwan karatu, akwai kuma abin da ake kira *e-library*,⁹⁹ wato dakin karatun intanet. Dakunan karatu na tara dubban daruruwan littattafai a kan intanet. Da a ce sai an samo kwafinsu, lallai akwai buƙatar kuɗaɗe masu yawa da kuma gine-gine masu yawa inda za a ajiye su.

3. Bunkasa Hausa

Kamar yadda ake bunkasa Hausa ta hanyar rubuce-rubuce a duniyar zahiri, haka ma abin yake a duniyar intanet. Wani abu mai jan hankali shi ne, sau da dama rubutu bisa intanet ya fi yi wa matasa sauƙi a kan rubutu ta amfani da takarda da alƙalami. A haka ana samar da rubuce-rubuce da dama a duniyar intanet. Ya rage ga masu kishin Hausa da su dage wajen bunkasa al'amarin domin kwalliya ta biya kuɗin sabulu.

⁹⁹ A nan sakamakon ya yi canjaras da tunani irin na Pulatoriyya. Dakunan karatun intanet ba a kallon su (duk da ma ana iya kallon littattafai da sauran kayan karatun yayin da aka Hausa intanet). A wuraren da suka ci gaba, idan aka ce dakin karatu na da littattafai miliyan goma, wataƙila miliyan bakwai duka a kan intanet suke. Da za a zo a lissafa, za a yi mamakin ina miliyan bakwai ɗin suka shiga. Lallai kuwa suna duniyar intanet.

4. Yayata Hausa

Idan mutum ya ci gaba da rubutu domin amfanin Hausawa, to haɓaka ta kawai yake yi. Idan kuwa ya kasance cewa waɗanda ba Hausawa ba na amfana da rubutun, to a nan yana yayata ta ke nan. Babbar hanyar yayata Hausa cikin sauki a yau shi ne ta amfani da intanet. Wanda ke zaune a kasar Hausa na iya yin rubuce-rubuce da za su zaga duniya. Hakan kuwa na kara wa harshen sanuwa tare da daga darajarsa cikin jerin harsunan duniya. Ba makawa, yayatuwar Hausa na daga cikin abin da ya fifita ta tare da daga darajarta sama da tsaranta a yau. Duk da haka, “idan kana da kyau, sai ka kara da wanka.”

5. Samar da Kafafen Sada Zumunta

Hakifa wata babbar gudummuwar da intanet ke bayarwa a yau ita ce samar da kafafen sada zumunta. Zumunci ya dawo ana iya sadar da shi alhali ana kwance cikin daki. Wannan ya kasance sabanin da (kafin samuwar intanet) wanda sai an tashi takanas domin ziyara. A yau, akwai kafafen sada zumunta barkatai a duniyar intanet.

6. Yada Labarai

Intane wuri ne na samun labaran abubuwan da ke wakana a duniya. Da yawa daga cikin jaridu da gidajen rediyo da na tibi suna dora labaransu a kafe daban-daban na intanet. Wasu labaran kan kasance a rubuce, waɗansu kuwa na magana, wani lokaci har da na bidiyo. Daga cikinsu akwai na Hausa, misali:

- a. BBC Hausa
- b. VOA Hausa
- c. Aminiya
- d. Arewa24

7. Samar da Muhimman Bayanai

Akwai kafafen Intanet daban-daban da suke adana muhimman bayanai game da ɓangarorin rayuwa mabanbanta. Wannan ya haɗa da harshe da kimiyya da fasaha da kiwon lafiya da sauransu. A irin waɗannan kafafe, akan samu muhimman bayanai cikin kankanin lokaci kuma ba tare da wata wahala ba. Kafafen Intanet na Hausa da ke adana bayanan ilimi sun haɗa da:

- i. Amsoshi (www.amsoshi.com)
- ii. Bakandamiya (www.bakandamiya.com)
- iii. Hausa (www.Hausa.wordpress.com)
- iv. Hausa Dictionary (www.Hausadictionary.com)
- v. Kano Online (www.kanoonline.com)
- vi. Makarantar Hausa (www.makarantarhaus.com)
- vii. Teach Yourself Hausa (www.teachyourselfHausa.com)¹⁰⁰

¹⁰⁰ An jero su ne bisa tsarin abajada. An bibiyi kowace kafa domin nazartar kumshiyarta. Dukkanin kafafen da aka zayyana, an zaɓe su ne ta la'akari da nagartan kumshiyarsu.

8. Samar da Kafafen Kasuwanci

Intanet babbar hanya ce ta cinikayya. Akwai masana'antu da dama a kasar Hausa da kuma musamman kasashen waje da ke amfani da kafafen intanet a matsayin farfajiyar kasuwanci. Sukan tallata hajarsu a kafafen na intanet. sannan cinikayyar na kasancewa a intanet. Wani lokaci har akan biya kuɗin kaya kafin a turo wa mai saya da kayan. Wani lokaci kuwa, sai an turo kaya ga mai saya kafin ya biya kuɗin. Daga cikin kamfanoni masu cinikayya ta kafafen Intanet akwai:

Wasu Kafafen Intanet na Kasuwanci a Nijeriya

- a. Dealdey Ltd (<https://dealdey.com.cutestat.com/>)
- b. Jumia (<https://www.jumia.com.ng/>)
- c. Kara (<https://www.kara.com.ng/>)
- d. Konga (<https://www.konga.com/>)
- e. Parktel Online (<https://parktelonline.com/>)
- f. Slot (<https://slot.ng/>)

Wasu Kafafen Intanet na Kasuwanci a Kasashen Waje

- a. 6pm (<https://www.6pm.com/>)
- b. AllSaints (<https://www.allsaints.com/>)
- c. Amazon (<https://www.amazon.com/>)
- d. Ann Taylor (<https://www.anntaylor.com/>)
- e. ASOS (<https://www.asos.com/>)
- f. Barnes & Noble (<https://www.barnesandnoble.com/>)
- g. Ray-ban (<https://www.ray-ban.com/usa>)

h. Urban Outfitters (<https://www.urbanoutfitters.com/>)

i. Yoox (<https://www.yoox.com/us>)¹⁰¹

9. Adana Tarihi

Tuni duniyar intanet ta kasance tamkar wani rumbun adana bayanai. Rubuce-rubuce da hotuna da bidiyo da odiyo na iya kasancewa a kafafen intanet na din-din-din.¹⁰² Saboda haka, garabasa ce ga Hausa da Hausawa a matsayin wata ma'adana ta al'adunsu. Idan aka yi amfani da wannan garabasa ta hanyar da ta dace, lallai abin zai kasance sai dai a ce san barka.

10. Samun Abin Masarufi

"A cikin kira ake dadi." Kafafen intanet na iya kasancewa harkallar da ke samar da abin masarufi ga masu gudanarwa. Babbar hanyar samun kudi ta intanet ita ce talla. Masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na karɓar talla daga kamfanonin cikin gida da na waje. Idan aka ci sa'a mutanen da ke hawa kafar intanet na da yawa, mai karɓar tallar zai caba.

11. Hana Yawon Banza

Yawon banza yana daya daga cikin halayen da Bahaushen ba ya so. Wannan ne ya sanya Bahaushen ke da hanyoyin rage yawon banza. A da, yakan yi amfani da tatsuniyoyi domin hana yara fita yawo. A nan, samuwar intanet ta rage yawon

¹⁰¹ An samo waɗannan bayanai ta hanyar duba sunayensu a intanet tare da shiga cikinsu domin tabbatarwa

¹⁰² Ana iya samun salwantar bayanai yayin da aka samu wata matsala ta musamman. Duk da haka, akwai hanyoyi da ake bi domin tabbatar da adanuwar bayanai na din-din-din.

banza. Dalili kuwa shi ne, matasa da dama sun fi bukatar su zauna a gida sannan su yi hira da duk wanda suke bukata ta hanyar amfani da intanet. A yanzu da aka samu ci gaba, kallace-kallacen finafinai duk sun koma kan intanet ta amfani da wayoyi. Wannan ya sake taimakawa wajen hana matasa tafiya gidajen kallon talabijin musamman da dare.

12. Bayyana Muradun Siyasa da Tallata 'Yan Takara

Intanet ya kasance kafa da 'yan siyasa ke bayyana manufofinsu. Haka kuma, mutane da dama na amfani da kafafen intanet domin tallata 'yan takara. A duk lokacin da zaɓe ya kusanto a kasar Hausa, kafafen intanet musamman na sada zumunta cika suke yi taf da zantukan siyasa na kamfe. Zabubbuka da dama da suka wakana, intanet ya taka rawar gani wajen sadar da manufofin 'yan siyasa zuwa ga talakawa.

13. Isar da Safo Cikin Sauri da Sauki

Intanet yana taka rawar gani wajen bazuwar safo cikin gaggawa. Gwamnatoci da cibiyoyin ilimi ko na kiwon lafiya na amfani da kafafen intanet domin isar da safo. Misali, idan akwai wata sanarwa da Jami'ar Usumanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato ke son isarwa ga dalibai, sau da dama takan yi amfani da kafar intanet nata domin isar da shi. Wani babban misali shi ne, tun a farko-farkon shekarar 2020 Hukumar Lafiya ta Duniya (WHO) take amfani da kafafen intanet domin isar da sakonni da suka shafi farkewar annobar Koronabaras da aka samu.

14. Bincike da Nazari

Tuni kafafen intanet suka zama wani gulbi da ake kamfatar ilimi daga cikinsu. Manazarta a fannoni daban-daban kan nemi bayanai a kan intanet. Masu binciken sun hada da dalibai da aka ba su jinga a aji, ko dalibai masu kokarin rubuta kundin digiri, ko kuma yayin rubuta takardun da za a gabatar a wuraren tarukan kara wa juna sani. Babban misali shi ne, fiye da rabin bayanai da wannan bincike ya samu, ya same su ne a kafafen intanet. Wannan ne dalilin da ya ja hankalin Abubakar Muhammad Tsangarwa har ya buɗe kafar *Rumbun Ilimi*. Ya bayyana dalilin da ya sa shi buɗe kafar da cewa: “Tallafa wa masu bincike ta kafar Intanet wajen samun hakikanin bayanai game da al'adun Hausa.”

3.4 Aibin Intanet ga Hausa da Hausawa

Duk da dimbin amfanin intanen ga Hausa da Hausawa da aka bayyana a karkashin 3.3 da ke sama, yana kuma da tarin aibi. A kasa an kawo wasu daga cikin aibin intanet ga Hausa da al'adun Hausawa:

1. Rage Zumuntar Sawu

A lamba ta 5 da ke karkashin 3.3 a babi na uku, an bayyana samuwar kafafen sada zumunta. A zahirin gaskiya, abin ya kasance hanjin jimina, wato akwai na ci akwai na zubarwa. Samuwar kafafen sada zumunta na da alfanu a bangare guda. A daya bangaren kuwa, yana da babbar illa. Daga ciki akwai fata lokaci da cin karo da hotuna da bidiyoyi da labaran batsa da dai makamantansu. Haka kuma, kafafen na taimakawa wajen rage zumuncin sawu a tsakanin al'umma.

Kasancewar koyaushe ana da damar gaisawa ta kafafen, zumuncin sawu sai ya rage tasiri.

2. Bayanan Karya

A farkashen lamba ta 3 na 3.3 an bayyana yayata Hausa a matsayin dāya daga cikin amfanin kafafen intanet ga Hausa da Hausawa. A ɓangare guda, wannan na kasancewa aibi. Yana zama aibi ne yayin da aka yi rashin sa'ar cewar bayanan da aka samar a kafafen intanet ba saihai ba ne. A irin wannan lokaci, waɗanda za su karanta daga wata uwa duniya na iya zaton haƙikanin yadda al'adun Hausa suke ke nan. A takaice, "a garin gyaran gira an rasa ido." A lamba ta 14 da ke farkashin 3.3, an kawo batun nazari da bincike. A wannan ɓangare ma akan samu matsala yayin da ya kasance an dogara da bayanan da aka samu a kafafen intanet. Idan ya kasance an ci karo da bayanan karya, haƙika ba za a samu sakamako mai inganci ba a binciken da ake gudanarwa. Kasar Hausa ba za ta manta ba da lokacin da aka yayata zancen karya game da cewa shugaban kasar Nijeriya zai aure wata. Wannan ya faru a wajajen 2019. Jaridu da dama sun rawaito wannan jita-jita. Ciki har da Rashin, (2019) da Kaina, (2019).

3. Lalata Tarbiyya

Intanet yana ɓata tarbiyya matuƙa. Akwai kafafe da dama a bisa intanet waɗanda ke sanya hotuna da bidiyoyi da rubuce-rubuce na batsa. Cikin waɗannan kafafe an fara samun na Hausa. Babban misali a wannan gaɓa shi ne kafar intanet ɗin nan mai suna *Batsa Post*. Wani bincike da aka gabatar a shekarar 2013 ya yi nuni da

cewa, kafafen ilmantarwa na intanet sun fi kafafen shiririta da kusan kashi saba'in (70%) cikin dari. Duk da haka, matasa sun fi ziyartar wadannan kafafen shiririta.

Shehu da Aliyu, (2019) sun bayyana cewa:

Wayar salula na daga cikin manyan matsalolin da suka dabaibaye rayuwar ma'aurata a kasar Hausa a yau... idan miji ba ya nan sai mace ta riƙa kiran samarinta na waje su riƙa hira tamkar saurayi da budurwa. A wani lokacin kuma, sukan riƙa musayar sakonni ba tare da sanin mijin ba. Shehu da Aliyu, (2019: 707).

A takaice ke nan, intanet ya zama sanadiyyar gurɓacewar tarbiyya. Matsalar har ta kai ga ma'aurata inda matar aure ke musayar sakonni da mazaje a waje. Haka shi me a bangaren namiji, wa ya ce duk matan da yake mu'amala da su a kafafen intanet ba matan aure ba ne? Ko da babu matar auren a cikinsu, hakan ya ci karo da al'ada da addinin Bahaushe a yau. Dan'iro ya kawo irin wannan batu cikin wakarsa inda yake cewa:

6. Abin takaici ma har da ma amare,
Su samu kato catin suke a tare,
Su kama yin soyayya kwarai a tare,
Har ma ta ce masa honi su canza yare,
Da iggiyar aure ukku kanta daure,
Shi miji gwangwani kun ga bai sani ba.
(Dan'iro Katsina: Wakar Soshiyal Midiya Dandalin Matasa)

A cikin wannan baiti, yana nuna cewa har amare sukan yi musayar sakonni ta kafafen sada zumunta da wasu mazaje. Sannan har abin kan kai ga kalaman soyayya. Irin wadannan mata ba su damu da auren da ke kansu ba. A ire-iren wadannan lokuta, shi mijin sam bai san wainar da ake toyawa ba.

4. Farfaganda

Bayanan karya na da bambanci da bayanai marasa inganci. Bayanan karya a nan sun fi shafar farfaganda. Da ma dai karya na nufin rusasshen zance marar asali ko tushe da ake furtawa ko rubutawa da nufin mai sauraro ko karanta ya aminta. Kafafen intanet, musamman kafafen sada zumunta sun kasance wuraren yada farfaganda da labaran karya. Akan baza jita-jita marar tushe a intanet. Irin wadannan jita-jitan sun hada da masu ta da hankali tare da harzuka al'umma domin su tayar da zaune-tsaye a samu hargitsi da tashin-tashina. Misali, akan sanya labarai masu jan hankali da niyyar jawo hankalin mutane su shiga wata kafar intanet. Sai bayan an shiga ne ake tarar da cewa labarin na bogi ne. Hakika wannan aibi ne na kafafen intanet.

Da ma dai, karya na daga cikin boyayyun al'adu da suka ci karo da al'ada da addinin Bahaushe. Dangane da haka ne Shehu da Aliyu, (2019: 790-710) ke cewa: "Al'adar Hausawa da addininsu duk sun yi haramci a kan aikata karya. Wannan ya sa idan mutum ya zama makaryaci bai da kima da mutunci a idon jama'a." Dangane da farfaganda a kafen sada zumunta, Dan'ido na cewa:

A yada alkairi kar a yada zamba,
A nan ake mai da kadan ta zamma babba,
A nan ake haddasa ki a rai da gaba,
A nan ake tarbiyyar da ban fadi ba,
A nan ake wargaza tarbiyyar su baba,
Duk a nan midiya in ba kus sani ba.¹⁰³
(Dan'iro Katsina: Wakar Soshiyal Midiya Dandalin Matasa)

5. Ta'addanci

A duk lokacin da mutane (musamman yara) ke kallon ayyukan ta'addanci, zuciyarsu tana kara bushewa ne da keƙashewa. Sannu a hankali tausayin da suke ji zai rika raguwa. Za a kai gacin da kwata-kwata nau'ukan ta'addancin ba sa wani tasiri irin na sanya tausayi ko jin kai a zukatansu.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, yana koya wa yara hanyoyin aikata rashin gaskiya daban-daban. Daga cikin nau'ukan abubuwan da ke furshe a kafafen sada zumunta waɗanda kuma ke da alaƙa da ta'addanci akwai:

- i. Hotuna da bidiyoyi da labarai a kan makamai da yadda ake sarrafa su.
- ii. Hotuna da bidiyoyi na makamai da yadda ake safarar su.
- iii. Hotuna da bidiyoyi da labaran kashe-kashe.
- iv. Hotuna da bidiyoyi da labarai game da ayyukan ta'addanci da aka aikata irin su fashi da makami da sata da garkuwa da mutane da makamantansu.

¹⁰³ Sallau, (2021) ya labarta yadda jami'an 'yan sanda suka yi iƙirarin cewa su ne suka fwato waɗansu mutane da masu garkuwa da mutane suka sace. Wannan labari ya bazu a duniya alhali a haƙifanin gaskiya mutanen ne suka samu nasarar kuɓucewa da kansu, ba tare da taimakon kowi jami'in tsaro ba.

A kasa an kawo ‘yan misalai wadanda aka tattaro daga kafafen sada zumunta.

Hoto 3.11: Bindigogi da Alburusai a Fesbuk

Madogara: An dauko wannan hoto ranar 2 ga watan Janairu, shekara ta 2020 daga Fesbuk.

A hoto na 3.11 da ke sama, za a ga hoton bindigogi da kuma alburusai. A kasar Hausa an saba ganin yadda yara ke kwaikwayon wasa da bindigogi wadanda suke hadawa da kara ko ‘yan itatuwa. Masu wayo daga cikinsu suna amfani da fayif da karamin katako ko falanki da ashana domin yin bindigar wasa wadda take kara. Duka wadanan na faruwa ne sakamakon kallace-kallacen hotuna da bidiyoyin nau’ukan bindigogin da kuma yadda ake sarrafa su. A bisa wannan dalilai, kai tsaye ire-iren hotunan nan na da tasiri a kan tarbiyya da falsafar yara masu tasowa.

Hoto 3.12: Bidiyon ‘Yan Bindiga na Shirin Kai Hari

Madogara: An dauko wannan bidiyo ranar 2 ga watan Janairu, shekara ta 2020 daga Fesbuk.

An sanya wannan bidiyo ne da sunan ‘yan bindigar Jahar Zamfara ne ke shirin kai hari. Sai dai bincike ya nuna cewa, labarin ba gaskiya ba ne. Hasali ma, ba a Nijeriya aka dauki wannan bidiyo ba.

6. Zamba da Damfara

A lamba ta 10 da ke karkashin 3.3 an kawo “*Samun Abin Masarufi*” a matsayin amfanin intanet ga Hausa da al’adun Hausawa. A ɓangare guda kuwa, akan samu masu bin haramtattun hanyoyi domin samun kuɗi ta amfani da intanet. Wannan ya haɗa da tura wa mutane sakonnin damfara. Ta wannan hanya sukan nemi samun bayanan sirri kan mutane ko su bukaci da a tura musu kuɗaɗe. Bayan nan akwai hanyar datsar akawun-akawun na mutane (hacking) domin a musu sata.

7. Bata Lokaci

A lamba ta 11 da ke karkashin 3.3 an kawo “*Hana Yawon Banza*” a matsayin ɗaya daga cikin amfanin intanet ga Hausa da al’adun Hausawa. Tuni ‘yammata da samari suka auri kafafen sada zumunta a yau. Kusan kullum matasa na bata tsawon awanni a kan intanet. Da a ce za su yi amfani da wannan lokaci wajen aikata wani aikin fwarai, lallai “da ba gizo ba in ji koki.” A nan za a iya cewa samar da kafafen sada zumunta da aka ambata a karkashin lamba ta 5 da ke 3.3 ba amfani kadai gare shi ba. Bayan amfaninsa a gefe guda, a ɗaya gefen ya tattare da aibi.

8. Gurbatar Kyawawan Al’adu

Gurbatar al’adun Hausawa na faruwa ne yayin da Hausawa suka ɗauki bakin al’adu a kafafen intanet. Intanet kafa ce da ke yada al’adun bakin al’ummu. Hausawa kan ɗauki al’adun wasu al’ummu musamman Turawa da Indiyawa da Larabawa. Mafiya yawan waɗannan al’adu sun ci karo da na Hausawa. Gurbatattun al’adu da ake ɗauka a intanet sun fi shafar halayya da tufafi. Tasirin intanet kan al’adun Hausawa ya ja hankalin manazarta da marubuta da dama. Daga cikin ciken rubuce-rubucen da suka fito da bayanai game da wannan batu akwai Almajir, (2009) da Magaji, (2018) da Shehu da Rambo, (2019) da Shehu da Aliyu, (2019).

3.5 Nadewa

Hafika al'adun Hausawa sun kai wani matsayi na bunkasa a duniyar intanet. Kusan babu wani ɓangaren al'adun Hausawa da ba a cin karo da shi a cikin kafafen intanet. Abin tambaya a nan shi ne: (i) Shin Hausawa ne mamallaka waɗannan kafafen intanet da ke nuna al'adun Hausawa? (ii) Idan Hausawa ne ko ba Hausawa ba, shin suna da ilimin harshe da al'ada da adabin Hausa? (iii) Shin al'adun Hausawa da ake cin karo da su a duniyar intanet na hafika ne ba gurbatattu ba? Domin amsa waɗannan tambayoyi, akwai bukatar nazartar "nasarori da kalubalen kafafen intanet na Hausa." Hakan ne zai ba da damar fahimtar inda aka kwana tare da hasashen gobe.

BABI NA HUDU

NASARORI DA KALUBALEN KAFAFEN INTANET NA HAUSA

4.0 Shimfida

Nazartar nasarori da kalubalen kafafen intanet na Hausa na da amfani a duniyar karatun Hausa a yau. Hakan ne zai ba da damar sanin inda aka kwana domin kyakkyawan tanadin gyaran gobe. Wannan babi na hudu ya karkata kan nazarin matsayin kafafen intanet na Hausa a yau. Kamar yadda aka bayyana a babi na ɗaya karkashin 1.6 (Farfajiyar Bincike), wannan bincike ya zakulu kafafen intanet na Hausa guda arba'in da uku (43). A cikinsu, za a mayar da hankali kan guda talatin da ɗaya (31) kamar yadda Krejcie & Morgan, (1970) suka zayyana a jadawalin zaɓen samfuri. A karshen wannan babi, ana sa ran fahimtar matsayin kafafen intanet na Hausa a yau. Wannan ya haɗa da ci gabansu da kuma nakasunsu.

4.1 Kafafen Intanet na Hausa

Ya zuwa watan Maris na shekarar 2020, adadin kafafen intanet na Hausa fitattun sun kasance kimanin 43. Yana da kyau a tuna cewa, ya zuwa 2019, kafafen intanet da ke duniya gaba ɗaya sun kasance kimanin biliyan 1.72.¹⁰⁴ Harsunan duniya kuwa sun kasance kimanin dubu bakwai (7,000) kamar yadda aka bayyana a babi na biyu karkashin 2.1.1.2.

¹⁰⁴ A duba Giraf 2.1 da ke babi na biyu.

Idan aka raba adadin kafafen intanet na duniya (biliyan 1.72) a waɗannan harsuna (7,000), adadin zai kasance wajajen miliyan ashirin da huɗu da ɗigo hamsin da bakwai (miliyan 24.27). A takaice, kason kafafen intanet na Hausa bai wuce wajajen 0.00000000025% ba. Sai dai wani abin lura shi ne, a adadin kafafen intanet na duniya har da na kafafen yaɗa labarai. Su kuwa kafafen intanet na Hausa, ba a sanya da kafafen yaɗa labarai ba. Baya ga haka, za ta iya yiwuwa akwai kananan kafafen intanet na Hausa waɗanda wannan bincike bai kai gare su ba (saboda rashin bunkasarsu wanda ya sa injunan nema ba sa iya gano su). ..sa..

A takaice, idan aka yi la'akari da yawan kafafen intanet da ke duniya, to Hausa ba ta da kafa na a-zo-a-gani! Duk da haka, tana kan gaba-gaba a cikin tsaranta harsunan Afirka, musamman na Nijeriya da Nijar. Kamar yadda aka nuna a babi na biyu karkashin 2.1.1.2, Hausa ce kaɗai daga cikin manyan harsunan Nijeriya ta samu shiga cikin Fesbuk. Bayan haka, tana da gindin zama a Wikifidiya.

Dangane da masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa, mafi yawa ba masu ilimin harshe da al'adun Hausawa ba ne. Wannan bincike kafa biyu kacal ya ci karo da su waɗanda suka kasance masu gudanar da su sun karanci Hausa a matakin digiri. Kafafen su ne *Amsoshi*¹⁰⁵ da *Makarantar Hausa*.¹⁰⁶ Misali, shahararrun kafafen intanet ɗin nan guda biyu *Hausa Online* da *Karin Magana*, ba

¹⁰⁵ <https://amsoshi.com/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://makarantarhaus.com/>

Bahaushe ba ne ke gudanar da su.¹⁰⁷ A shafin farko na kafar *Hausa Online*, ya wallafa hotonsa dāuke da bayani kamar haka:

Hoto 4.1: Hoton Mr. Uwe Seibert Tare da Tsokaci

🕒 THURSDAY, DECEMBER 21, 2017 👤 USEIBERT 💬 LEAVE A COMMENT

I have started this blog more than 11 years ago. It was meant to share ideas on learning Hausa and other less commonly taught languages. Lately, I have been a bit lazy and haven't posted any new ideas for a long time.

At the same time, the amount of online material that could be used for language learning keeps growing and

Madogara: Seibert, (2017: 1)

Seibert ya nuna cewa, ya buɗe kafar intanet na Hausa tun wajajen shekarar 2006.¹⁰⁸ Yayin da yake magana game da dalilin da ya sa ya rage dōra rubuce-rubuce, sai ya ce: “... *there are now more better elearning websites and smartphone apps than when I started Hausa online.*” Ma’ana: “Yanzu an samu wadatar kafafen intanet da manhajojin wayoyi masu ilimantarwa sama da lokacin da na buɗe *Hausa Online*.”

¹⁰⁷ Domin karin bayani game da mamallakin wandannan kafafen intanet, ana iya bincika: <https://hausonline.wordpress.com/about/?contact-form-id=2&contact-form-sent=1126&contact-form-hash=dd29ecf524b030a65261e3059c48ab9e1ecb2585&wponce=d00905671c#contact-form-2>.

¹⁰⁸ An yi la’akari da maganarsa da ke cewa: “I have started this blog more than 11 years ago.” Ma’ana: “Na buɗe wannan kafa sama da shekaru 11 da suka wuce.” Ya yi wannan maganar ne a shekarar 2017. Shekara 11 kafin 2017 zai kasance 2006.

Wannan maganar tasa na nuna cewa, har zuwa wajajen 2006 babu wadatar kafafen intanet na Hausa. Wannan ya yi daidai da abin da Chamo, (2020)¹⁰⁹ ya labarta cewa: “Lokacin da nake kasar waje, mutane da dama sun tambaye ni cewa: “Me ya sa babu rubuce-rubucen Hausa a kan intanet?””

An samu damar zantawa da masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa da dama.¹¹⁰ Duka wadanda aka yi hira da su, babban muradinsu na buɗe kafafen intanet na Hausa shi ne domin bunkasa Hausa a duniyar intanet.¹¹¹ Bashir Ahmed, wanda shi ne ke da kafar intanet ta *Hutu Dole*, ya bayyana dalilin buɗe wannan kafa da cewa: “Habbaka¹¹² Al'adun Hausa, Adabin Hausa, samar da bayai¹¹³ a zamanance ga Hausawa.” Shi kuwa, Lawan Dalha, dogon jawabi ya yi inda yake cewa:

Dalilan da suka sa muka buɗe¹¹⁴ Bakandamiya dai kamar guda biyu zuwa uku.¹¹⁵ Na farko mun fahimci cewa litattafan ilimi, wato literature, musamman a fannin kimiyya da fasaha sun yi karanci¹¹⁶ cikin harshen Hausa. Saboda haka, sai muka ga za mu yi amfani da taskar Bakandamiya don baiwa¹¹⁷ mutane dama suke rubuce-rubuce har da bidiyoyi wajen karantarwa da kuma yin muhawara akan¹¹⁸ kimiyya da fasaha don dalibai¹¹⁹ su fahimta.

¹⁰⁹ An yi hira da shi ranar 2 ga watan Maris, shekarar 2020. Shi ke jagorantar kafar intanet ta Hausa mai suna *wikihausa*.

¹¹⁰ Akwai masu kafafen intanet da suka boye adireshi da lambobinsu. Samun tuntuɓar ire-irensu ya ci tura.

¹¹¹ A rataye an kawo kididdiyar adadin mutanen da ke ziyartar wasu daga cikin kafafen intanet na Hausa.

¹¹² Haka!

¹¹³ Haka!

¹¹⁴ Haka!

¹¹⁵ Haka!

¹¹⁶ Haka!

¹¹⁷ Haka!

¹¹⁸ Haka!

¹¹⁹ Haka!

Abu na biyu, muna tunanin taskar zai¹²⁰ zama wurin tattara abubuwan tarihi ne na al'adun Hausawa da ma Arewacin Nigeria. Don haka muna dora¹²¹ sautuka (wakoki¹²² da wa'azuka¹²³ da makamantansu) da hotuna na tarihi tare da bayanai yadda duk wanda ya ci karo da su zai fahimci wani abu akai.¹²⁴

Na uku shi ne, muna ganin akasarin al'ummar dake¹²⁵ amfani da harshen Hausa, mu'amalarsu bata¹²⁶ da yawa da na'urorin zamani kasancewar yawanci na Turanci ne. Don haka, muna ganin samar da wata kafa ta Intanet kuma cikin harshen Hausa zai kara¹²⁷ baiwa¹²⁸ masu amfani da harshen dama su fahimci kuma su ci moriyar kafafen na zamani la'alla ta bangaren¹²⁹ ilmantuwa ko kuwa kasuwancin zamani.

Dangane da bunkasar kafafen intanet na Hausa kuwa, ana iya cewa ba yabo ba fallasa. Ya zuwa yau (2020) kusan kafafen sun taɓa dukkanin bangarori na rayuwa. Bangarorin da kafafen intanet na Hausa suka taɓa sun haɗa da:

- i. Kamusu
- ii. Labarai
- iii. Sadar da Zumunta
- iv. Kimiyya da Fasaha
- v. Ilimi
- vi. Adabi
- vii. Cinikayya

¹²⁰ Haka!

¹²¹ Haka!

¹²² Haka!

¹²³ Haka!

¹²⁴ Haka!

¹²⁵ Haka!

¹²⁶ Haka!

¹²⁷ Haka!

¹²⁸ Haka!

¹²⁹ Haka!

4.1.1 Kamusu

Kamusu matattara ce ta kalmomi da ma'anoninsu. Kamusu na da matuƙar amfani ga bunkasar harshe da ci gabansa na baki ɗaya. Tuni Hausa ta yi wa sauran harsuna sa'o'inta zarra a wannan ɓangare. A rumbun manhajojin wayoyi mai suna *Play Store*, akwai manhajojin kamusushin Hausa masu yawa. Suna kasancewa cikin tsari na musamman, misali ɗaya daga cikin:

- i. Kamusun kalmomin Hausa da bayanan Ingilishi
- ii. Kamusun kalmomin Hausa da bayanan Hausa
- iii. Kamusun kalmomin Hausa zuwa kalmomin Ingilishi
- iv. Kamusun kalmomin Ingilishi zuwa kalmomin Hausa

Daga cikinsu akwai waɗanda ba a iya amfani da su sai da data. Ma'ana dai, ko da an sauke su kan waya ko kwamfuta, to dole sai an kunna data kafin a iya amfani da su. Wasu daga cikinsu kuwa, da zarar an sauke su kan kwamfuta ko waya, to ana iya amfani da su ko da babu data. Kaso na uku su ne waɗanda ba a sauke su kan kwamfuta ko waya. A maimakon haka, ana yin amfani da data ne kawai a duba su a kan intanet. An kawo misali a kasa cikin hoto:

Hoto 4.2: Kamusun Hausa na Kan Intanet

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Hausa Dictionary*:

http://hausadictionary.com/Main_Page

A hoto na 4.2 da ke sama, za a ga kamusu ne na Hausa wanda ake amfani da shi a kan intanet. Kamar yadda ake gani cikin hoton, an ba da damar bincika kalma kai tsaye a gurbin da aka rubuta “Bincika <> Search.” Da zarar mutum ya rubuta kalma a wannan wuri, to kamusun zai budō da bayananta nan take. Bayan haka, an yi wani tsari na abajada. Yayin da mai nema ya latsa dāya daga cikin abajadan, kamusun zai gabato masa dukkanin kalmomi da suka fara da wannan harafi. Wani babban misali bayan wannan shi ne *Bargery Online Dictionary*.

4.1.2 Labarai

Akwai kafafen intanet na Hausa da suka shahara a bangaren yadā labarai. Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, a nan ba a nufin jaridu da gidajen rediyo ko talabijin da ke da kafafen intanet. Ana nufin kafafen intanet masu zaman kansu da ba su jingina jikin kowane kafar yadā labarai ba. Sukan samar da rubuce-rubuce da hotuna da bidiyoyin al’amuran da ke faruwa a kasar Hausa. Wasu lokutan har sukan taɓo labaran kasashen ketare. Babban misali dangane da wannan shi ne kafar intanet mai suna *Jaridar Hausa*. A shafinta na farko, ta wallafa rubutu kamar kamar haka:

Jaridar Hausa jarida ce da za ta dinga kawo muku abubuwa da ke faruwa a kowanne lungu na sako na duniya, sannan kuma ta baku¹³⁰ cikakken bayani a kan ainahin abin dake¹³¹ wakana cikin harshen Hausa (Shafin Farko na Jaridar Hausa: <https://jaridarhaus.com/>).

Hoto 4.3: Wani Bangaren Shafin Farko na *Jaridar Hausa*

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Jaridar Hausa*: <https://jaridarhaus.com/>

Wani babban misalin kafar intanet mai kawo labarai shi ne kafar *Hutu Dole*. Ita ma wannan kafa ta shahara a bangaren kawo labaran yau da kullum. A kasa an kawo hoton rukunnenta (categories):

Hoto 4.4: Rukunnai (Categories) na Kafar *Hutu Dole*

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Hutu Dole*: <https://hutudole.com/>

¹³⁰ Haka!

¹³¹ Haka!

“Shafin hutudole.com daya ne daga cikin shafukan yanar gizo da ke wallafa labarai da harshen Hausa...” Hutu Dole, (2018: 1). Idan aka yi la’akari da hoto na 4.4 da ke sama, za a lura da cewa shafin dungurungum ya karkata ne kan labarai. Sauran rukunnai da ke cikin hoton sun danganci bayanai ne a kan shafi. Misali, *TUNTUBI HUTUDOLE* da *DANGANE DA HUTUDOLE*.

4.1.3 Sadar da Zumunta

Sadar da zumunta ta intanet wani abu ne da ya mamaye duniyar yau. Galadanci *da wasu* (1990: 8) sun bayyana ma’anar sadarwa kamar haka: “... a tafai, ita ce sanya wani ya fahimci abin da kake so ya ji, ko ya yi ko ya sadu da abin da kake so ya karɓa.” Ya zuwa yau, an samu kafafen intanet na Hausa da ke ba da damar sada zumunta tsakanin al’umma. Babban misali a nan shi ne kafar *Kano Online*. A duba hoto da ke kasa:

Hoto 4.5: Sada Zumunta ta Kafar *Kano Online*

Madogara: Shafin tattaunawa mai taken *kacici-kacici* a kan kafar *Kano Online*: http://kanoonline.com/smf/index.php?topic=2739.0;prev_next=next#new

Idan aka duba hoto na 4.5 da ke sama, za a tarar da misali na tattaunawa a kafar *Kano Online*. Kafar na ba da damar tattaunawa tsakanin al'umma a zaure ko kuma a kebanche (group or private chats). Ko bayan wannan kafa, akwai kafar intanet mai suna *Bakandamiya*. Ita ma na da tsarin da ke ba wa mutane damar sadar da zumunta a tsakaninsu. Hakifa wannan wani ci gaba ne da ya samu. Idan an yi amfani da shi yadda ya kamata, lallai Hausa ce ke da tagomashin.

4.1.4 Kimiyya da Fasaha

A duniyar yau, kimiyya da fasaha na kan gaba. Mutuncin kasa da karfin tattalin arzikinta sun dogara ne kan karfin kimiyya da fasaharta. Akwai kafafen intanet da dama da ke tsakuro labarai da sharhi ko fashin baki da fadakarwa dangane da kimiyya da fasaha. Daga cikinsu akwai **amsoshi.com** da **managarciya.com** da **hutudole.com**. Duk da haka, manufofin kafafen bai mayar da hankali kan kimiyya da fasaha dungurungum ba. Cikin sa'a sai aka samu bullar kafafen intanet waɗanda suka mayar da hankali kan wannan ɓangare. A duba hoto da ke kasa:

Hoto 4.6: Kafar Intanet Kan Kimiyya da Fasaha (*Jakadan Fasaha*)

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Jakadan Fasaha*: <https://www.jakadanfasaha.com/>

Idan aka duba hoto na 4.6 da ke sama, za a tarar da cewa kafar ta raja'a ne kan kimmiya da fasaha baki daya. Ko daga sunanta ma ana iya fahimtar hakan (Jakadan Fasaha). Kafa ce da ta shahara wajen kawo bayanai kan na'urori irin su kwamfutoci da wayoyi da makamantansu. Bayan haka, tana kawo bayanai game da duniyar intanet. Wannan ya shafi amfani da intanet, da kare kai daga damfarar intanet da makamantansu.

4.1.5 Makaranta

A matakin duniya, an dade da samun makarantu kan intanet. Hausa ta fara cin gajiyar wannan fasaha bayan samuwar kafafen intanet irin su *Makarantar Hausa da Pen Profile* da *Teach Yourself Hausa*. Makarantar Hausa tana da tsari ne na karanta mafi yawan abubuwan da ke kan kafar a kyauta. Duk da haka, akwai 'yan kadan wafanda sai an biya ake karantawa. Bayan haka, makarantar ba ta samar da darrusa kai tsaye domin dalibanta ba. A maimakon haka, ta kasance ne tamkar sauran kafafen intanet masu dora bayanai da ke ilimantarwa. A hoton da ke fasa an kawo shafin farko na kafar:

Hoto 4.7: Shafin Farko na Kafar *Makarantar Hausa*

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Makarantar Hausa*:

<https://makarantarhaus.com/akawun>

Kafar *Teach Yourself Hausa* ita ma shahararriya ce. Tana dauke da rubuce-rubuce da hotuna da ke ba da damar koyon Hausa. Kafar ta fi amfanar waƙanda ba Hausawa ba. An samar da ita cikin tsarin Ingilishi da Hausa. Babayan haka, bayananta na da saukin fahimta. Sannan kafar na ba da hurumin aika gyara ga duk wanda ya gani. A duba hoton da ke kasa:

Hoto 4.8: Kafar *Teach Yourself Hausa*

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Teach Yourself Hausa*:

<http://www.teachyourselfhaus.com/>

Kafar *Pen Profile* ita ce ke da tsarin makaranta kai tsaye. Tana da tsari na kwasai da dalibta. Dalibai na yin rigista sannan su karanta kwasai-kwasai. Akwai kuma tsari na ba da jinga da jarabawa. Duk wannan na faruwa ne a duniyar intanet.

4.1.6 Adabi

Abu ne mai matuƙar muhimmanci a ce adabin wata al'umma na da gindin zama a duniyar intanet. "Adabi fage ne babba da ake iya hango kowane abu da ya shafi rayuwar Bahaushe" (Bunza da Atuwu, 2015: i). A wannan ɓangare ma, ba a bar Hausawa a baya ba. Tuni an samu kafafen da suka yi fice wajen dora abubuwan

da suka shafi adabin Hausawa. Kafar *Hausa Top* na ɗaya daga cikin waɗanda suka fi saura shahara a wannan fanni. A duba hoto da ke kasa:

Hoto 4.9: Hoton Rukunnen Kafar *Hausa Top*

Madogara: Shafin Farko na *Hausa Top*: <http://www.hausatop.com/>

Idan aka duba hoto na 4.9 da ke sama, za a tarar gaba ɗaya rukunnen an rubuta su ne cikin harshen Ingilishi. Duk da haka, kafar ta Hausa ce. Ta shara wajen kawo waƙoƙin Hausa cikin sautukan odiyo da bidiyoyi. Sun wallafa a shafin cewa:

HausaTop.Com is the Most Visited Online Platform that Delivers Hot Fresh Northern Nigerian Music, Video, Entertainment Gist & News Content on a daily Basis to Nigerians Home and Abroad. Hausa Top, (2020: 1)

Fassara:

HausaTop.Com ta kasance kafar da aka fi ziyarta wacce take kawo zafafan sabbin waƙoƙin Arewacin Nijeriya da bidiyoyi da wasanni da labarai a kowace rana. Tana samar da su domin 'yan Nijeriya a cikin gida da kuma kasashen waje.

4.1.7 Kasuwanci

An daɗe ana cinikayya a duniyar intanet. Idan aka bi fahimtar Pulatoriyya, ana iya cewa, yadda duniyar zahiri take da kasuwanni, haka duniyar intanet ma. Tun da kuwa zamani riga ce, bai dace a bar Hausa a baya ba dangane da cinikayya a duniyar intanet. Irin wannan nau'in cinikayya ya shafi duba abin da ake buƙata tare da tura kuɗin ta intanet. Daga nan za a ba wa mutum damar samun abin da ya sanya (misali rubutu, odiyo, bidiyo da sauransu). Idan na kawowa ne kuma, za a

kawo zuwa adireshin da mai saye ya zayyana (kamar mota, tufafi da sauransu).

Hausa ta fara shiga wannan tsari. A duba misali da ke kasa:

Hoto 4.10: Kasuwanci a Duniyar Intanet

Madogara: Shafin sayar da littattafai na *WikiHausa*:

<https://www.wikiHausa.com.ng/littattafai/>

A hoto na 4.10 da ke sama, za a iya kallon littattafan sayarwa, kowanne da farashinsa. Masu saye na iya yin odar littattafan kai tsaye daga wannan kafa ta *Wiki Hausa*. Hakika wannan nau'in ci gaba na bukatar saka hannun masana da mahukunta domin habaka shi. Hanya ce ta saukaka rayuwa.

4.2 Kalubalen Bunkasar Kafafen Intanet na Hausa

A farkashin 4.1 an bayyana cewa, daya daga cikin manyan matsaloli ko kalubalen kafafen intanet na Hausa shi ne masu gudanarwar. An bayyana cewa, kafafen intanet biyu ne kacal masu gudanar da su suka karanci Hausa a matakin digiri. A bisa wannan ana samun kalubale nau'uka uku:

- i. Saba wa al'adu
- ii. Kurakuran rubutu barkatai

iii. Rashin ingancin bayanai¹³²

4.2.1 Saba wa Al'adu

Akwai kafafen intanet na Hausa da kai tsaye suke saba wa al'ada da addinin Hausawa. Mafi shahara a cikinsu ita ce *Batsa Post*. Kamar yadda sunan ya nuna (batsa), wannan kafa babu abin da take yi face kawo rubuce rubuce da hotuna da kuma bidiyoyin batsa. Babban maƙasudin wannan kafa shi ne nuna tsiraici cikin hotuna da bidiyoyi. Kafar na ƙoƙarin kalato hotunan tsiraici na matan Hausawa. Haka abin yake dangane da bidiyoyi.

Babu makawa kafar ta Hausa ce. Hatta rukunne da ɓangarorin kafar duka cikin harshen Hausa aka rubuta su.¹³³ Duk da haka, kai tsaye za a iya gane cewa ba Hausawa ba ne ke gudanar da shafin. Dalilan da aka dogara da su domin yanke wannan hukunci su ne:

- a. Kusan babu wata jimla da aka rubuta ta daidai ba tare da tafka kurkuren rubutu ba (karya ƙa'idojin rubutu).
- b. Karin harshen bai yi kama da na Bahaushen asali ba. Akwai wurare da ana iya kallon karin harshen mai koyo (L2) kai tsaye.

¹³² Wannan ya shafi ɓangaren tarihi da sauran bayanai da suka shafi al'adu da adabi da harshen Hausa.

¹³³ Akwai ɓangarori kaɗan da aka bar su cikin harshen Ingilishi. Hakan na iya kasancewa sakamakon kasa samun takamaiman fassarorinsu.

Hoto 4.11: Samfurin Rubutu Daga Kafar *Batsa Post*

Madogara: <https://www.batsapost.com/category/news-labarai/>

An dauko hoto na 4.11 kai tsaye daga kafar intanet ta *Batsa Post*. Duk da rubutun ba shi da yawa, akwai kurakurai sosai da za a iya kallo daga ciki. Waɗannan kurakurai sun haɗa da:

- a. An rubuta “taunawa” a maimakon “tona wa.”
- b. An rubuta “kamashi” a maimakon “kama shi.”
- c. An rubuta “akace” a maimakon “aka ce.”
- d. An rubuta “dauki” a maimakon “ɗauki.”
- e. An rubuta “vidiyan” a maimakon “bidiyon.”

Ko bayan wannan, wurare da dama daga cikin kafar na nuna cewa ba Hausawa ba ne ke gudanar da shafin. Akwai wuraren da karara za a iya fahimtar cewa inji ne ke musu fassarar rubuce-rubuce da suke ɗorawa. Misali, a inda suke fofarin rubuta manufar shafin, sai suka sanya:

Hoto 4.12: Misalin Fassarar Inji a Kan Kafar *Batsa Post*

Madogara: Shafin farko na *Batsa Post*: <https://www.batsapost.com>

A hoto na 4.12 da ke sama, za a tarar kai tsaye salon fassarar inji ne. Ya kasance:

- i. An fara rubutun da Hausa, sai aka ci gaba da Ingilishi. Daga karshe kuma aka karkare da Hausa.¹³⁴
- ii. An rubuta “ba’a” a maimakon “ba a.”
- iii. An rubuta “fada” a maimakon “fada.”

Bayan wannan shafi, akwai shafuka da dama da ke dōra hotuna da suka ci karo da al’adun Hausawa. Nau’ukan hotunan yawanci na mata ne cikin shigar da ta ci karo da addini da al’adar Bahaushe. Mafi akasarin hotunan sun shafi:

1. Hoton matan Hausawa ‘yan fim (jaruman finafinan Hausa)
2. Hoton matayen ketare ‘yan fim da ‘yan tallata haja.¹³⁵
3. Hoton sauran mata na Hausawa ko mataye daga kasashen ketare.¹³⁶

4.2.2 Kurakuran Rubutu Barkatai

“Dan’adam tara yake bai cika goma ba!” Haka kuma: “Yin daidai sai Allah!” Duk da haka, kurakuran da ake samu a kan wasu kafafen intanet na Hausa sun yi yawa sosai. Hakan na faruwa ne sakamakon masu gudanar da su ba su da ilimin rubutun Hausa. A karkashin 4.1, an kawo misalan amsoshi da wasu masu

¹³⁴ Wannan salo ne na fassarar inji. Inji na fassara iya wurin da ya sani (ta hanyar amfani makamantan fassarori da aka dōra masa). Sauran bangarorin da bai sani ba kuma, yakan bar su haka nan ba da fassara ba.

¹³⁵ Yawanci matan da ke tallata haja suna shiga da ta ci karo da al’adun Hausawa. Misali, waɗanda ke tallata rigar mama, akan ɗauke su hoto ba tare da tufafi ba. Daga su sai rigar mama da suke tallatawa.

¹³⁶ Yana da kyau a fahimci cewa, an fi kawo misalan hotunan ne domin kare martabar al’ada da addinin Bahaushe (kasancewar sun saba musu). Idan aka ce za a kawo misalan hotunan, to tamkar “mai dokar barci ne ya buge da gyangyadi.”

gudanar da kafen intanet suka bayar dangane da abin da ya ja hankalinsu wajen bude kafafen. Za a tarar da cewa a cikin kowace amsa akwai matsalar ka'idojin rubutu barkatai. Matsalar ta fi shafar hadawa da rabawa da kuma rashin amfani da bakake masu kugiya. Ko bayan wannan, akwai misalan saba ka'idojin rubutu a kafafen intanet na Hausa daban-daban. Ga 'yan misalai a kasa:

Dan Allah kira ga mafi yawancin ku yan uwan mu mawakan Hausa Hip Hop ma su tasowa, ku daina turancin da ba daidai ba ne ko ku rage inya zama dole ku yi turancin da ba daidai ba ne a wakar ku, kuna bada Arewa da ma jihar Kano ne, domin babu anfanin ka yi yaran da ba ka iya ba daidai a waka bayan ga na ka yaran na asali wanda ka kware a kai. San nan sama da kashi 70% na wannan turancin da su ke yi ba daidai ba ne, gashi kuma sama da kashi 80% na ma su sauraron wakokin ku ba sosai su ke jin turancin nan ba, kunga asara biyu kenan, ka yi waka amma kai kan ka ba ka san abun da kake fada ba a ciki, kuma ga sakon ka bai kai ga wadan da su ya kamata ya kaiwa ba (Dabo, 2019: 1).

- i. Dukkanin tsawon rubutun a matsayin jimla guda aka rattabo shi. Ya dace a raba shi zuwa jimloli da dama.
- ii. Ba a sanya bakake masu kugiya a wuraren da suka dace ba.
- iii. An hade kalmomi a wuraren da ba su dace a hade ba.
- iv. An rabe kalmomi a wuraren ba su dace a rabe ba (kamar gajeruwar mallaka).

A shafin *Qalubale* ma an samu misali kwatankwacin wannan. Ga yadda rubutun ya kasance:

Shidai wannan matashi yasamu nasarar kammala tattakinsa lafiya ya kuma isa kano tangaram inda kai tsaye yawuche ofishin ABBA KABIR YUSUF dake a nasarawa shikadai batare da yan tarba ko rakiya ba inda ya,isa office din amma ko ruwa ba,abashi ba, hasalima

bai samu ganin kowa ba chikin jagororin kwankwasiyar inda aka shaida masa wai sunyi tafiya zuwa ABUJA (Ahmed, 2020: 1).

Idan aka yi la'akari da rubutun da ke sama, za a tarar da cewa:

- a. Duk yawansa an rubuta shi ne a matsayin jimla guda.
- b. Akwai wuraren da aka haɗe rubutu alhali ya dace a rabe su.
- c. An yi amfani da "ch" a matsayin "c" misali "yawuche" a maimakon "ya wuce."

Ko bayan waɗannan misalai, akwai wasu masu tarin yawa. Kusan duk wata kafar intanet ta Hausa da aka ɗauka sai an ci karo da ire-iren waɗannan misalai na kurakuren rubutu.¹³⁷ Kafafen da suka yi zarra dangane da bin ka'idojin rubutu guda biyu ne. Na farko akwai kafar *Amsoshi* (<https://www.amsoshi.com/>). Kafa ta biyu ita ce *Makarantar Hausa* (<https://makarantarhaus.com/>).

4.2.3 Karya

Bayanan karya sun yawaita a kan intanet. A farkashin 1.1 (Dalilin Bincike) da ke babi na ɗaya an kawo bayani mai alaƙa da wannan. A shekarar 2017, fitaccen Dangaladiman Farfesan, Abdullahi, I. S. S. A ɓangaren al'ada ya yi tir da cin karo da bayanai marasa inganci dangane da Maguzawa da Maguzanci a intanet. Idan dai marasa ilimin Hausa suka ci gaba da jagorantar kafafen intanet na Hausa, babu makawa waɗannan kurakurai ba za su kau ba.

¹³⁷ An kawo jerin kafafen intanet na Hausa guda arba'in da uku (43) a farkashin 1.6 da ke babi na ɗaya.

Babban misali a wannan ɓangare shi ne, masu gudanar da kafafen intanet ba su karanci al'adun Bahaushe ba. A bisa wannan dalili, babu yadda za a yi bayanai da za su kawo dangane da al'adu su kasance na zahiri. Ilimin al'adu fage ne mai zaman kansa. Ana neman sa tamkar yadda ake neman sauran ilimummuka. Ana nazarin sa tamkar yadda ake nazarin sauran ilimummuka. Ke nan, ba abu ne da za a yi wa hawan kawara ba. Haka abin yake ga adabi da harshen Hausa. Yayin da aka samu marasa ilimin abin su ne ke jagorancin sa a duniyar intanet, to "a garin neman kiba za a samo rama."

4.3 Dalilan Koma-Bayan Kafafen Intanet na Hausa

Akwai dalilai da dama da suke mazaunin kalubale ga bunkasar kafafen intanet na Hausa. A kasa an kawo bayanansu dalla-dalla:

4.3.1 Muhalli

Harkar intanet abu ne mai bukatar muhalli na musamman. Akwai bukatar wutar lantarki mai dorewa. Daukewar wuta abu ne mai kawo cikas ga harkar. A ɓangare guda kuwa, akwai bukatar sabis na intanet mai nagarta. A wuraren da suka ci gaba, wadannan duka ba matsaloli ba ne. Wuta tana da tabbas. Haka ma akwai sabis na intanet mai karfin gaske. A kasar Hausa kuwa, ana iya fadin abin da jakin dawa ya fada wa na gida: "Allah wadai naka ya lalace!"

4.3.2 Karancin Tallafi da Karfafa Guiwa

A kasashen da suka ci gaba, tallafa wa masu hobbasar kirkiro wata fasaha abu ne sababbe. Wannan ne ma dalilin da ya saka kafafe da dama suke sanya madannin

ba da tallafi (donate) a kafafen nasu. Madannin na ba wa masu ra'ayi damar tura tallafinsu zuwa ga kafafen intanet din. Yayin da aka bincika, za a ci karo da ire-iren waɗannan madanne a kafafen intanet manya da kanana. A cikinsu har da shahararriyar kafar nan wato *Wikifidiya*. A kasa an kawo misalin hoton tambarin neman tallafi:

Hoto 4.13: Hoton Tamfarin Neman Tallafi

Madogara: Binciken “*Donate Botton PNG*” a Rumbun Hotunan Gogul

Dangane da kasar Hausa, abin ba haka yake ba. Ba a damu da tallafa wa fasahohi masu tasowa ba. Hasali ma, masu gudanar da kafofin sukan sha suka da tsangwama. Sau da dama, akan samu al’ummar da ke kallon bata lokaci kawai masu wannan hobɓasa suke yi.

Lawal Dalha (mai gudanar da kafar Bakandamiya) ya bayyana wannan korafi inda ya ce: “Babbar matsala ta karshe ita ce matuƙar ba a samu hanyar shigowar kudi mai dorewa ba da zai taimaka wajen gudanar da taskar, mai yiwuwa nan gaba mu kasa iya rike ta.” Dangane da karfafa guiwa kuwa, Bashir Ahmed (Maigudanar da kafar Hutu Dole) cewa ya yi: “... Rashin masu sharhi waɗanda za

su yi sharhi a kan al'amuran yau da kullun, kamar yanda ake samu a shafukan jaridun Turanci.”

4.3.3 Yanayin Intanet

Yanayin intanet kansa na tasiri ga bunkasar harkokin intanet na Hausa. Intanet wani al'amari ne mai sarkakiya tare da cakwakiya. Yana bukatar ilimi na musamman. Yana tafiya da yaruka na daban. Yayin gudanar da al'amuran intanet, akwai bukatar samun ilimin waɗannan yaruka. Fitattu daga ciki su ne:

- a. HTML (Hypertext Markup Language)¹³⁸
- b. PHP (Personal Home Page Tools)¹³⁹
- c. CSS (Cascading Style Sheets)¹⁴⁰
- d. Javascript¹⁴¹

Rashin samun ilimin waɗannan yarukan intanet koma baya ne ga gudanar da harkokin kafafen intanet. Sun kasance tamkar tubalan ginin kafafen intanet. Idan babu su, kafafen intanet ba za su iya wanzuwa ba kamar yadda ake kallon su. Akwai dalilai da ke sa Hausawa kasa a guiwa a wannan bangare na koyon yarukan intanet. Sun haɗa da:

- i. Babu wadatattun masu ilimin da za su koyar da yarukan intanet da kwamfuta.

¹³⁸ Yaren gina kafafen intanet

¹³⁹ Yaren daidaita ginin kafafen intanet domin ba shi tsari mai kyau

¹⁴⁰ Yarin ba wa kafafen intanet umarnin aikata wasu ayyuka

¹⁴¹ Yaren harhaɗa ɓangarorin kafafen intanet da ba su umarni

- ii. Babu wadatattun santoci da makarantun koyar da yarukan intanet da kwamfuta.
- iii. Yawancin Hausawa ba su da ra'ayi a wannan bangaren ilimi.
- iv. Koyon yarukan kwamfuta da intanet na bukatar biyan kudin horaswa.
- v. Yawancin waɗanda ke da ra'ayin koyon ba su da damar biyan kudin horaswar da ake bukata.

A ɓangare guda kuwa, harkar gudanar da kafafen intanet abu ne mai bukatar lokaci. Da farko akwai bukatar lokacin koyon yaruka kamar yadda aka ambata a sama. A duba "a" da "b" da "c" da ke farkashin 4.2.3. Samun wannan lokaci ba karamin kalubale ne ba. Da a ce akwai tallafi ga masu wannan hobɓasa, haƙifa gudanar da kafafen zai zo da sauƙi. Dalili shi ne, tallafin zai ishe su biyan bukatur rayuwar yau da kullum. Ke nan za su dukufa ka'in da na'in wajen aiki ba kama kafar yaro, tun da ba sa tunanin rashin ruwan ciki wanda da shi ake jan na rijiya.

4.3.4 Kin Karɓar Sauye-Sauyen Rayuwa

Dan'adam na da halin kin karɓar sauye-sauye a rayuwa. Wannan ne ma ya sa ake da ra'in "*resistance to change*" da "*cultural lag*" (kin karɓar sauyi da like wa al'ada). Waɗannan ra'o'i suna nuna cewa, dan'adam na jin shakku da wasi-wasi game da duk wani sauyi da aka gabato masa da shi a rayuwa. Zuciyarsa za ta raya masa cewa, tsohuwar hanyar da yake bi ita ce daidai. Zai kuma ji cewa, sabuwar hanyar na iya kasancewa cike da kalubale da wahalhalu, sannan ba za ta bulle ba.

Mutum na karɓar sauyi a rayuwa yayin da ya yi amfani da abin da ake ce wa “*overcoming resistance to change*” (yakar dabi’ar fin karɓar sauyi). Sau da dama yayin da mutum ya karɓi sabon al’amari, zai yi mamakin kasancewar har ya fi tafarkin da yake bi da. Bayan haka, zai yi mamakin yadda zai saba da shi a hankali. Wato koma bayan yadda da yake tunanin ba zai iya sabo da shi ba.¹⁴² Masu fokarin samar da kafafen intanet na Hausa na fuskantar wannan kalubale. Hirar da wannan bincike ya yi da wasu masu kafafen intanet na Hausa na nuna cewa:

- i. Ba sa samun goyon bayan da ya kamata yayin da suka tunkari cibiyoyi ko sasukan nazarin Hausa.¹⁴³
- ii. Ba sa samun goyon bayan da ya kamata yayin da suka tuntubi masana harshen Hausa.¹⁴⁴
- iii. Ba a samun goyon baya daga daliban Hausa kamar yadda ya kamata.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴² Har ya zuwa shekarar 2020, mutane da dama suna amfani ne da samfurin *Microsoft Office 2007*. Sun fi karɓar sababbi da aka samar waɗanda an bunkasa su sama da na 2007. Wasu da suka karɓi sauyi kwana-kwanan nan, sun nuna farin ciki da gamsuwa. Kamar haka abin yake a sauran ɓangarorin rayuwa. Wannan ne ya sa Bahausha ke cewa: “Sai an gwada akan san na kwarai.”

¹⁴³ A kasashen da suka ci gaba, kusan abu ne da ya zama tilas kowane sashe a jami’a ya kasance yana da kafar intanet (za a iya tabbatar da hakan yayin da aka bincika duniyar intanet). Dangane da sasukan nazarin Hausa, ba haka abin yake ba. Har ya zuwa 2020, wannan bincike bai ci karo da ko da sashen koyar da Hausa a Nijeriya ko Nijar da ke da kafar intanet tasa ta kansa ba! Wai “wata miyar sai a mafwabta!”

¹⁴⁴ An yi hira da Bunza, (2019) bayan ya dawo daga taron kara wa juna sani na kasa da kasa wanda aka gudanar a Folan. Ya bayyana cewa mallakar kafar intanet dole ne ga malami a kasashen da suka ci gaba. Wannan abu ba haka yake ba a kasar Hausa. Dangane da abin da wannan bincike ya gano, masana Hausa masu kafar intanet ba su da yawa.

¹⁴⁵ Daliban Hausa sun fi kwarewa a kafan sada zumunta kamar su Fesbuk da Was’af. Sukan bata lokaci matuƙa a ire-iren waɗannan shafuka. Da a ce za su mayar da hankali wajen bibiyar shafukan intanet na Hausa, to “da ba kwado ba inji gaya.”

Cikin sauki, abin da ya kamata shi ne a bi maganar Bahaushe da ke cewa: "Zamani riga." Ya jaddada wannan batu in da ya ce: "Zamani abokin tafiya."

4.3.5 Rashin Ingantattun Injunan Gyara Rubutun Hausa

Rashin ingantattun injunan gyara rubutun Hausa ya kasance kalubale ga ci gabanta a duniyar intanet. Idan aka dauki harshen Ingilishi, za a tarar da cewa yana da injunan gyaran rubutu. Yayin da mutum ya rubuta kuskure, injin gyaran rubutu zai iya nuna masa akwai kuskure. Babban misali a nan shi ne *Microsoft Word*. Da zarar mutum ya rubuta kalma ba daidai ba, to za a ga jan layi ya bayyana a kasan kalmar. Idan kuwa jimla ce aka rubuta ba daidai ba, za a ga layi ruwan bula a kasan jimlar baki dayanta.

A kan kafafen intanet ma (har da kafafen sada zumunta) akwai injunan da ke iya gyara rubutu. Babban misali a nan shi ne injin din *Grammarly*. Ya kasance inji da ake iya setawa a kan kwamfuta ko waya. Da zarar mutum ya rubuta kuskure, wannan inji zai zakulo kuskuren sannan ya nuna wa mai rubutun zaɓuɓɓukan gyara. Wani lokaci kuma yakan gyara rubutun kai tsaye ba tare da jiran mai rubutun ya yanke hukunci ko daukar wani mataki ba.

Hoto 4.14: Injin Gyaran Rubutu na *Grammarly*

Typen missige fulle of misteks for
exemple

Madogara: Rubutu a Gimel Bayan an Sauke *Grammarly* Kan Kwamfuta

A hoto na 4.14 da ke sama, za a ga cewa dukkanin kalmomin da ke cikin sakon da aka rubuta an ja musu layi ban da guda biyu (“of” da “for”). Wannan ya faru ne sakamakon an rubuta su bisa kuskure. Haka wannan injin gyara na *Grammarly* ke taimaka wa marubuta wajen nuna musu kurakuren da ke cikin rubuce-rubucensu na Ingilishi.

Dangane da Hausa, ba haka abin yake ba. A maimakon gyara, sai dai ma injunan su rika rikita mai rubutu. Wani lokaci har sukan bata masa rubutun. Misali, idan mutum na rubutu a kan *Microsoft Word*, idan ya rubuta wata kalma mai kama da ta Ingilishi, injin din na iya sauya tsarin abajadan zuwa kalmar Ingilishi da ke kama da ita. Misali:

- a. “bara” (begging) na iya sauyawa zuwa “bar a”
- b. “boko” (formal education) na iya sauyawa zuwa “book”
- c. “buga” (hit) na iya sauyawa zuwa “bugs”

- d. “daya”¹⁴⁶ (one) na iya sauyawa zuwa “days”
- e. “ita ce” (she is the one) na iya sauyawa zuwa “it ace”
- f. “waje” (place) na iya sauyawa zuwa “wake”
- g. “yamma” (east) na iya sauyawa zuwa “gamma”
- h. “yawo” (movement) na iya sauyawa zuwa “yawl”

Wannan matsala na haddasa yawaitar matsalolin kurakuran da suka shafi ka’idojin rubutu. Yakan kasance aiki biyu mutum zai yi. Na farko gyara kurakuran da ya tafka da kansa. Na biyu kuma gyara kurakuran da suka samu sakamakon sauya masa rubutun da inji ya yi. Mafi yawan rubuce-rubucen Hausa a duniyar intanet cike suke da kurakuren da suka shafi ka’idojin rubutu.¹⁴⁷

Ba wannan ba ne kadai dalilin samun yawaitar kurakuran da suka shafi ka’idojin rubutu a kafafen intanet na Hausa. Akan same su yayin da masu gudanar da kafa ba su nakalci ka’idojin rubutun Hausar ba. A takaice ke nan, zai kasance suna rubuta Hausar kamar yadda tsammaninsu ya raya musu. Babu wata doka da ta hana buɗe kafar intanet ga wanda bai fware ga harshe da al’adar al’umma ba. A bisa haka, ya rage ga masana da manazarta Hausa da su yi hobbasar samar da ingantattun kafafen intanet. Hakan ne zai yaƙi wannan matsala ta karya ka’idojin rubutun Hausa a duniyar intanet.

¹⁴⁶ A farkashin 4.2.7 da ke kasa, an kawo bayani kan amfani da bakafe masu fugiya a kan intanet.

¹⁴⁷ An tabbatar da haka bayan an nazarci kafafen intanet na Hausa guda 39, tamkar dai yadda aka bayyana a farkashin 1.7 (Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike) da ke babi na ɗaya.

4.3.6 Bakake Masu Kugiya

Hausa tana da bakake na musamman. An fi saninsu da “bakake masu kuniya.” Sun kasance kamar haka: /K/, /k/, /D/, /d/, /B/, /b/. Rubutun Hausa babu su tamkar miya ce da ba ta da gishiri. Kasancewar sanya su na da wahala, yawancin kafafen intanet suna amfani ne da makamantansu. Haka ma sauran na’urori kamar a wayar salula da sauran kafafen intanet da ke ba da damar rubutu. Misali:

- a. /K/ a maimakon /K/
- b. /k/ a maimakon /k/
- c. /D/ a maimakon /D/
- d. /d/ a maimakon /d/
- e. /B/ a maimakon /B/
- f. /b/ a maimakon /b/

A wasu lokuta kuwa, akan dan yi musu kwaskwarima. Wannan bincike ya ci karo da rubuce-rubuce da dama a kafafen intanet inda aka yi wa bakake kwaskwarima da nufin su wakilci bakake masu kugiya. A kasa an kawo misali:

- i. /K'/ a maimakon /K/
- ii. /k'/ a maimakon /k/
- iii. /'D/ a maimakon /D/
- iv. /d'/ a maimakon /d/
- v. /'B/ a maimakon /B/
- vi. /'b/ a maimakon /b/

Duk da akan yi amfani da wannan dabara sosai, ba ta wadatar ba. Daga baya ne aka samu salailan rubutu (font styles) da ke dāuke da bakafen Hausa masu kugiya rubutun da aka fi sani da Rabi'at da kuma Abdalla.¹⁴⁸ Daga baya an ci gaba da samun manhajojin bakake masu kugiya. A shekarar 2019 ne kuma kamfanin *Microsoft* ya fitar da bakafen Hausa masu kugiya waɗanda za a iya amfani da su a kan kowace kwamfuta.

4.3.8 Rashin Ilimin Amfani da Kafafen Intanet Daga Bangaren Hausawa

Hausawa da dama na da matsalar rashin ilimin yadda za su yi ta'ammuli da kafafen intanet. Wannan ya haɗa da (i) Yadda ake hawa kafen intanet ɗin da (ii) Yadda ake binciko bayani ko bidiyo ko odiyo da ake bukata. Lawal Dalha (mai gudanar da kafar Bakandamiya) ya bayyana wannan korafi inda ya ce: "Akasarin mutanenmu (Hausawa), musamman waɗanda ba su yi makaranta mai zurfi ba, ba sa fahimtar yadda za su yi amfani da taskar cikin sauki."

4.4 Naɗewa

Ya zuwa yau, manyan kafafen intanet da ake da su na Hausa sun kai arba'in da uku (43). Wannan adadi mai yawa ne idan aka kwatanta da da takwarorinta harsunan Nijeriya da Nijar. Duk da haka, yawan kafafen bai taka kara ya karya ba idan aka kwatanta da adadin kafafen intanet a duniya waɗanda sun haura biliyan guda da ɗigo bakwai. Kafafen intanet na Hausa na fuskantar kalubale daban-

¹⁴⁸ Fasfesa Abdalla Uba Adamu ya cancanci yabo matuƙa a wannan fanni. Ya taka muhimmiyar rawa a duniyar intanet ta Hausa. Shi ya samar da waɗannan salailan rubutu a saukaƙe a karon farko. Ya zuwa shekarar 2019, ana amfani da salon rubutun Abdalla ne domin rubuta bakake masu kugiya a mafi yawan rubuce-rubucen Hausa. Salon rubutun Rabi'at shi ke bi masa.

daban. Wadannan kalubale sun shafi yanayin duniyar intanet da yanayin kasar Hausa da yanayin Hausar kanta. A bangare guda kuwa, sun shafi halayyar Hausawa na karancin ilimin amfani da kafafen intanet da kuma rashin ba da gudummuwa da kuma karfafa guiwa ga masu gudanar da kafafen intanet din.

BABI NA BIYAR

KAMMALAWA

5.0 Takaitawa

Samuwar kafafen intanet ya zo da wani juyin-juya-hali a kusan dukkanin al'amuran duniya. Tuni duniya ta karkata kan amfani da intanet domin gudanar da al'amuran yau da kullum. Daga ciki har da abubuwan da suka shafi:

- i. Ilimi
- ii. Kiwon lafiya
- iii. Tattalin arziki
- iv. Kasuwanci
- v. Shugabanci
- vi. Siyasa

Tafiya ta yi tafiya inda duniyar intanet ta kasance wata duniya ta daban da ke buƙatar wakilci. Maganar haka take musamman yayin da aka yi la'akari da Pulatoriyya inda ya nuna gaskiya iri biyu (bayyananniya da boyayyiya). Dole ne a yi hoɓɓasa domin samar da ingantaccen wakilcin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Da ma dai Bahausha na da karin maganar da ke cewa: "Zamani riga," inda Yunusa, (1989: 40) ya yi nuni cikin tambaya da cewa: "Wato ke nan idan ya zo sai kowa ya dauka ya sa a jikinsa?"

Manufar wannan bincike ba ta fita a kadadar nazartar al'adun Hausa a duniyar intanet ba domin gane inda aka fito da wurin da ake yanzu da kuma fofarin

gyaran gobe. Domin cimma manufar ne aka dukufa kan makasudai da suka hada da nazartar tsurar al'adun Hausawan cikin duniyar intanet. Bayan nan an nazarci ci gaba da kalubalen da kafafen intanet ke fuskanta. Wannan shi zai ba da damar gane tangardar da ake samu wajen samar da wakilci na kwarai na al'adun Hausawa a kafafen. A farkashin shawarwari kuwa, an mayar da hankali kan zayyano hanyoyi da matakan da ka iya taimakawa wajen bunkasawa da yayata al'adun Hausa a duniyar intanet.

An yi amfani da hanyar dora aiki da kuma ra'i domin cimma manufar wannan bincike. Ko da ma Ojua, (2019: 1) ya nuna cewa ba a faye samun ra'i guda ya wadatar ga binciken da ake gudanarwa a kimiyyar zamantakewa da na mu'amala ba. Karin maganar nan ta "zamani riga" ita ke taimaka wa wannan bincike wajen nuna cewa ya kamata a yi hobbasar samar da wakilcin al'adun Hausawa da bunkasa su a zamanance. Domin tabbatar da intanet a matsayin duniya mai bukatar wakilcin al'adu kuwa, an yi amfani da ra'in Pulatoriyya.

Masana da manazarta da dama sun gudanar da bincike a bangarorin ilimi da suke da dangantaka da wannan bincike. Daga ciki akwai bincike kan (i) zamani da (ii) al'adun Hausawa da (iii) intanet. Duk da haka, ba a ci karo da wani bincike da ya nazarci al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet ba. Lura da haka, an samu hujjar ci gaba da wannan bincike. Idan binciken ya samu cimma nasara, zai kasance mai muhimmanci a bangarori daban daban. Zai amfani mahukunta da masana da

manazarta da dalibai. Baya ga haka, zai kasance mai amfani ga masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa.

Binciken ya nazarci al'adun Hausawa a farfajiyar duniyar intanet. Al'adun Hausawa da aka ci karo da su sun hada da bayyanannu da kuma boyayyu. Cikin bayyanannun al'adu akwai gine-gine da tufafi da wasanni da makamantansu. Boyayyu kuwa sun hada da tarihi da halayya da dabi'u. Yayin da aka nazarci tasirin intanet kan al'ummar Hausawa da al'adunsu, sai aka tarar da cewa sun kasance hanjin jimina "akwai na ci akwai na zubarwa." Intanet na da matufar amfani. Daga cikin amfaninsa akwai ba da damar sada zumunta da habaka Hausa da yayata ta. Yana kuma taimakawa wajen adana al'adun Hausawan. Aibin kafafen intanet ga al'ummar Hausawa sun hada da bata tarbiyya da bata lokaci da samar da kafar damfara da makamantansu.

Wannan bincike ya nazarci kalubalen da ke tattare da gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa musamman ta bangaren bunkasa al'adun Hausawa. Bayan haka, binciken ya nazarci amsoshin da aka tattara yayin hirarraki da masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa. Bayan duk wadannan, ya nazarci hanyoyi da matakan da za a iya dauka domin bunkasa al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

5.1 Sakamakon Bincike

Bayan kammala wannan nazari, binciken ya gano abubuwan da suka shafi al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet. Abubuwan da wannan bincike ya gano su ne kamar haka:

1. Wannan bincike ya tabbatar da cewa, babu wani bangaren rayuwa a yau da zai iya ci gaba ba tare da an haɗa da intanet ba. Ko da addini da ake kallon an fara shi shekaru aru-aru kafin bullowar fasahar intanet, a yau ba ya ci gaba yadda ya kamata har sai an haɗa da intanet. Misali, wa'azuzzukan malaman addini na zagayawa matuka yayin da aka yi amfani da intanet. Wannan dalili ne ma ya sa Clement, (2020: 1) yake da ra'ayin cewa, a yau ba za a iya kwatanta duniya ba tare da intanet ba. Ma'ana dai, ba a san ma yaya duniya za ta kasance ba idan aka ce babu intanet a yau.
2. Idan har ana son ci gaban al'adun Hausawa da dauwamarsu cikin inganci, dole a auri duniyar intanet. Hakan ne zai ba da damar samar da wakilci mai inganci. Wannan ya yi daidai da faɗin Bahaushe na "zamani riga." Bahaushe ya karfafa wannan batu inda yake cewa "zamani abokin tafiya." Masana da manazarta da daliban Hausa suna mazaunin jakadun Hausa ne a duniyar zahiri. A tunani irin na Pulatoriyya, wannan wakilci ba zai cika yadda ya kamata ba har sai an samu kwatankacinsa a duniyar intanet.
3. Kafafen intanet na da matuƙar tasiri kan al'umma da al'adunsu. Masu ziyartar kafafen intanet na tasirantuwa daga rubuce-rubuce da bidiyoyi da odiyoyi da ake dorawa. A haka al'umma ke iya tasirantuwa da daukar halaye da dabi'u baki.

4. Al'adun Hausawa tuni suka fara mamaye duniyar intanet. Kafafen intanet na Hausa kalilan ne yayin da aka kwatanta su da adadin dɔukacin kafafen intanet da ake da su a duniya. Duk da haka, da zarar an bincika wani abu ta Hausa (ta amfani da injunan nema), sakamakon da ke bayyana na Hausa ne. Bugu da fari, kafafen intanet da za a ci karo da su na Hausa ne. A bisa haka, idan aka inganta kafafen intanet na Hausa ta ɓangaren dɔra ingantattun bayanai, lallai kwalliya za ta biya kudin sabulu. A babi na huɗu farkashin 4.1 an bayyana cewa kafafen intanet na Hausa sun mamaye kusan dukkanin ɓangarorin rayuwa. Akwai kafafe da suka shafi kimiyya da fasaha da waɗanda suka shafi ilimi da koyarwa da kasuwanci da al'ada da zamantakewa makamantansu.
5. Dumbin amfanin da intanet yake da shi, bai hana shi samun aibi ba. A farkashin 3.3 da ke babi na uku an bayyana wasu alfanun intanet. An bayyana aibinsa kuma a farkashin 3.4 da ke babi na uku.
6. Binciken ya gano cewa, akwai kafafen intanet na Hausa da ke barazana ga al'adun Hausawa. Hakan na faruwa ne kasancewar kafafen na dɔuke da kura-kurai barkatai tare da saɓa wa al'ada da addinin Bahaushe. Daga cikin koma bayan da kafafen intanet na Hausa suke dɔuke da shi akwai:
 - i. Suna cin karo da al'adun Hausawa
 - ii. Suna dɔuke da kurakurai barkatai

- iii. Sukan kunshi bayanai marasa inganci
7. Daga karshe, binciken ya fahimci cewa kafafen intanet na Hausa suna fuskantar kalubale matuka. A takaice, kalubalen sun shafi:
- a. Muhallin kasar Hausa da ke dake da kalubalen wutar lantarki da sabis na intanet
 - b. Karancin tallafi da karfafa guiwa daga bangaren masana da hukumomi
 - c. Yanayin tsauri da wuyar koyo da harkar intanet ke da shi
 - d. Kin karɓar sauye-sauyen rayuwa ga waɗanda abin ya shafa
 - e. Rashin injunan gyaran rubutun Hausa wanda hakan ke mazaunin kalubale ga rubuta ingantacciyar Hausa bisa tsarin ka'idojin rubutu
 - f. Rashin takamaimai hanyar rubuta bakake masu kugiya cikin sauki
 - g. Karancin ilimin da Hausawa ke da shi kan tsarin intanet da amfani da shi

5.2 Shawarwari

A farkashin 5.2 an bayyana sakamakon wannan bincike. An zayyano sakamakon da aka tattara daga alƙaluman wannan bincike. A wannan bagire kuma (5.3) za a mayar da hankali wajen ba da shawarwari. Sun kasance shawarwari ga matsaloli

da kalubale da binciken ya gano waɗanda ke dabiɓaye da al'amuran al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

1. Ya kamata a samu wata haɗaka tsakanin masana harkar kwamfuta da cibiyoyi da sasukan nazarin Hausa domin tanadi mai kyau na tunkarar zamani ta fuskar intanet. Wannan zai ba da damar buɗe ingantattun kafafen intanet na Hausa waɗanda za su yi wakilcin kwarai ga al'adun Hausawa. Kowa a cikin tafiyar zai ba da gudummuwa irin tasa. Masana intanet za su dukufa wajen gina nagartattun kafafen intanet na Hausa. Masana da manazarta da daliban ilimi za su ci gaba da gudanar da bincike da za a rika sabunta bayanan kafafen a-kai-a-kai. Cibiyoyi da sasukan nazarin Hausa kuwa za su tallafa ta bangaren samar da abubuwan bukata da suka shafi kuɗin gudanar da kafafen.
2. Ya kamata kowace cibiya da sashen nazarin Hausa ta mallaki kafar intanet na kanta. A cikin kafar, ta rika gudanar da al'amuranta tare da ɗora nau'ukan bincike da mambobinta ke gudanarwa. Abubuwan da cibiyoyi da sasukan za su rika ɗorawa na iya haɗawa da:
 - i. Sunaye da adireshin mambobi: Hakan zai ba wa masu ziyartar shafin damar tura tambayoyi ga waɗanda suka dace. Har ila yau zai ba da dama ga masu ziyartar shafin na kusa da na nesa tuntuɓar masu gudanar da cibiyoyin yayin da suke bukatar haɗin guiwa kan wani bincike da za su gabatar.

- ii. Bayani a kan cibiya ko sashe: Wannan zai taimaka wa masu ziyartar kafafen na kusa da na nesa. Yayin da suke neman wafanda za su hada guiwa da su wurin bincike, kai tsaye za su tuntubi masu kafar. Bayan haka, zai iya sanya sha'awa ga masu ziyarar kafafen na kusa da na nesa. Bayan karanta bayanai dangane da sashe, suna iya zuwa domin karatu a sashen.
- iii. Sanya bincike ko wani ɓangare na bincike da aka gudanar: Wannan zai taimaka wajen haɓaka Hausawa da yayata ta.
3. Ba za a iya hana matasa da yaran Hausawa ta'ammuli da duniyar intanet ba. Haka kuma, ba za a iya hana su tasirantuwa da abubuwan da suke cin karo da su a intanet din ba. A bisa wannan dalili, mafita guda ta rage ga Hausawa. Mafitar ita ce buɗe kafafen intanet na Hausa tare da inganta su. Yayin da ya kasance 'ya'yan Hausawa na da zaɓi, a kalla za a samu rangwame.
4. Kasancewar an samu kafafen intanet na Hausa masu ƙarfin tasiri a duniyar intanet, abin da ya saura shi ne ba wa masu gudanar da su ƙarfin guiwa. Bayan haka, yana da kyau a ci gaba da buɗe kafafen domin a samu inganci a ɓangaren kowace al'ada. A ƙarƙashin 4.1 da ke babi na huɗu, an kawo tsokacin Seibert, (2017: 1) da ke kan kafar intanet dinsa ta Hausa. Ya bayyana cewa, ya dena sabunta bayanan kafar ne samboda an samu yawaitar kafafen intanet na Hausa. Wannan na nuna cewa, idan aka samu wadatar kafafen intanet na Hausa masu inganci, za

su nashe taron yu-yu-yun da ake da su, har a daina jin duriyarsu baki daya.

5. La'akari da amfani da kuma aibin kafafen sada zumunta, dabara ta rage ga mai shiga rijiya. Mahukunta da iyaye da masana da manazartar ya kamata su yi aikin hadin guiwa a wannan ɓangare. Kowa ya yi bakin kokarinsa wajen tabbatar da yara masu tasowa suna amfana da alfanun intanet tare da guje wa aibinsa.
6. Kamar yadda aka bayyana a farkashin lamba ta 4 da ke 5.3, samar da ingantattun kafafen intanet ne kawai zai ba da damar kawo gyara a duniyar intanet. Ta wannan hanyar ne za a samu kyakkyawan wakilcin al'adun Hausawa.
7. Hakika kalubalen da kafafen intanet na Hausa ke fuskanta abin dubawa ne. Domin samun sassauci dangane da wadannan kalubale, wannan bincike ya ba da shawarwari kamar haka:
 - a. A samar da muhalli na musamman ga masu gudanar da kafafen intanet na Hausa. Misali, a samar da zaɓin da za a iya amfani da shi yayin da babu wuta (janareto). Haka kuma, a samar musu sabis din intanet mai nagarta. Wannan na iya kasance tsare-tsaren da cibiyoyi da sasukan nazarin harsunan Nijeriya za su gudanar.
 - b. Kamar yadda aka bayyana a lamba ta 1 a farkashin 5.3, a samu hadin guiwa tsakanin cibiyoyi da sasukan nazarin Hausa domin

tallafa wa harkar intanet. Ta haka ne za a bunkasa lamarin al'adun Hausawa a duniyar intanet.

- c. A rika samar da darrusa da horarwa da tarukan karawa juna sani na musamman (karkashin kulawar mahukunta da aka zayyana a lamba ta 1 karkashin 5.3). Taruka da darrusa da horarwar su kasance na musamman kuma keɓaɓɓu ga waɗanda suke da rigayayyen sani kan harkar kwamfuta tare da waɗanda suka da sha'awar shiga harkar domin ba da gudummuwa.
- d. Ya kamata a samu wani yunkuri da ya shafi rubuce-rubuce da tarukan karawa juna sani da za su fadakar dangane da amfanin intanet a yau. Dole ne al'umma (musamman malamai da daliban Hausa) su koyi ta'ammuli da intanet. Amfani da intanet ya kasance dole a yau. Idan Hausawa ba su yi ba, to za a musu. Yayin da wasu suka yi kuwa, gurɓatar haɓkanin wakilci tabbas ne. Bahaushe ya yi gaskiya da ya ce: "Sai bango ya tsage kadangare ke samun mafaka." Sai a hana bangon tsagewa sannan a like tsagon da ya soma aukuwa. Ma'ana, a samar da kafafen intanet na Hausa tare da toshe komadar da kafafen yanzu suka fara samarwa dangane da illoli da koma-bayansu ga al'adun Hausawa.
- e. Muhammad Bello (Mai Kafar Makarantar Hausa) shi ne sanannen mutum guda da ya yi hobɓasar samar da injin gyaran

rubutu na Hausa. Farfesa Abdalla Uba Adamu kuwa shi ne ya samar da tsarin rubuta bakake masu kugiya na Rabi'at da Abdalla. Yana da kyau a karfafa wa ire-irensu guiwa domin samun ingantattun injunan gyaran rubutu.

- f. A yanzu an kawo karshen matsalar bakake masu kugiya tun bayan da kamfanin *Microsoft* ya samar da bakake masu kugiya na gama gari (kamar yadda aka bayyana a karkashin 3.3.7 da ke babi na uku). Abin da ya rage yansu shi ne a yaya waɗannan bakake tare da bayani game da yadda ake amfani da su.
- g. Ya kamata a bi hanyoyin da suka dace na faɗakar da Hausawa game da amfani da intanet. Waɗannan hanyoyin sun haɗa da shirye-shirye a gidajen rediyo da wakofi da kuma tarukan kara wa juna sani.

MANAZARTA

- Abdullahi, I. S. S. (2008). "Jiya ba Yau ba: Waiwaye a Kan Al'adun Matakan Rayuwar Maguzawa na Aure da Haihuwa da Mutuwa." Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato. ...sa..1
- Abincin Hausawa, (2015). "Waina." An dɔuko ranar 17 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://abinci.com/post/130573384693/waina>.
- Abraham, R. C. (1962). *Dictionary of the Hausa Language*. London: Hodder Sydney.
- Abu, M. (1985). "Al'adun Aure da Canje-canjensu a Katsina." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Abubakar, A. S. (2007). "Dangantakar Intanet da Harkokin Rayuwa". Takardar da aka buga a cikin jaridar Aminiya ta ɗaya (1) ga watan Maris.
- Abubakar, H. S. (2020). "Ba'amurkiya Daga California ta Biyo Saurayinta Zuwa Kano." An dɔuko ranar 20 ga watar Fabarairu na shekarar 2020 daga: <https://freedomradionig.com/?p=17928>.
- Abubakar, S. da Ladan, H. (2019). "Dusashewar Wasannin Gargajiya A K'asar Yabo (2)." An dɔuko ranar 19 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://www.amsoshi.com/2018/01/dusashewar-wasannin-gargajiya-kasar-31.html>.
- Abubakar, S. Y. (1997). "Bori A Zariya." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Koyar da Harsunan Nijiriya, Jami'ar Ahmadu Bello, Zariya.
- Adamu, A. U. (2000). "Hausa Language and Culture on the Internet." An article published in the *Weekly Trust* of 20th November.
- Adamu, A. U. (2004). "Hausa Information and Communication (ICTs)." A paper presented at the 6th International Conference on Studies in Hausa Language, Literature and Culture at Beyero University, Kano.
- Adamu, J.S. (2013). Gudummuwar Shirye-Shiryen Gidan Radiyon Muryar Jama'a, Kano Wajen Kare Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa: Nazari a Kan 'Aiki Da Hankali' Da 'Tamburan Kano.' In Bunza, A.M. et al (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 645-660. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Adamu, M.T. (1998). *Asalin Magungunan Hausawa da Ire-Irensu*. Kano: Dansarkin Kura Publishers Ltd.

- Adamu, S. (2020). "Talla Cikin Siddabaru." An dauko ranar 20 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://www.amsoshi.com/2019/12/talla-cikin-siddabaru.html>.
- Ado, A. (2017). *Ra'o'in Bincike Kan Al'adun Hausawa*. Katsina: Kanki Classical Media Enterprises.
- Ahmad, A.A. (2013). Tasirin Wayar Salula a Kan Tarbiyyar 'Ya'yan Hausawa. In Bunza, A.M. *da wasu* (editoci). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 743-758. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Ahmed, I. A. (2020). "Comrade AAT ya yi Tattaki Daga Katsina Domin ta ya Kwankwasiyya Alhinin Faduwa Zabe." An dauko ranar 21 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://qalubale.news.blog/2020/02/09/comrade-aat-yayi-tattaki-daga-katsina-domin-ta-ya-kwankwasiyya-alhinin-faduwa-zabe/>.
- Akibu, G. (2001). "Fassarar Kalmomi Dari (100) na Na'ura Mai Kwakwalwa Tare da Bayaninsu." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Akindele, F. & Adegbite, W. (1999). *The Sociology and Politics of English in Nigeria: An Introduction*. Ife: O.A.U. Press Limited.
- Akodu, A. (1985). "A Comparative Study of the Traditional and the Contemporary Arts of the Maguzawa of Kaduna and Kano States. Unpublished Ph. D. Thesis, Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University.
- Almajir, T. S. (2008). "Hausa da Sadarwar Intanet." A cikin *Harsunan Nijeriya, Vol. XXI*. Kano: Northwestern University Press.
- Almajir, T. S. (2009). "Tasirin Zamani a Kan Rayuwar Hausawa Matasa a Kano." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Amfani, A. H. (2010). "Hausa Internet Terms." A paper presented at School of Oriental and African Studies - University College London/Department of Nigerian Languages, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.
- Aminu, N. (2015). "Bakin Dole: Nason Al'adun Turawa ga Al'adun Hausawa a Lardin Sakkwato da Gwandu da Argungu, 1903-2010." Kundin digiri na Uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Arewa24, (2018). "Tashe Ep 5." An dauko ranar 12 ga watan Afirilu, shekara ta 2020 daga: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FcLUspfbOGE>.

- Argungu, D. M. (2016). "Language and National Development in Nigeria – The Unfinished Business." A lead paper presented at the 1st National Conference on the Role of Language, History and Religion in the Development, Integration and Security in Nigeria, held in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.
- Armstrong, M. (2019). "How Many Websites Are There?" Retrieved on 20th February 2020 from: <https://www.statista.com/chart/19058/how-many-websites-are-there/>.
- Ashafa, A. M. (2016). "Language/Ethnicity, Religion and National Security: The Missing Links in National Development and Nation Building." A lead paper presented at the 1st National Conference on the Role of Language, History and Religion in the Development, Integration and Security in Nigeria, held in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria.
- Ashiru, H. M. (2012). "Gudummuwar Intanet ga Bunkasa Adabin Hausa." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Umbaru Musa 'Yar'aduwa, Katsina.
- Augustyn, A. *et al* (2020). Platonic Criticism. In Encyclopedia Britannica. Retrieved on 17th March 2020 from: <https://www.britannica.com/art/Platonic-criticism>.
- Ayad, A. (2008). *Healing Body and Soul*. Saudi Arabia: International Islamic Publishing House.
- Babajo, S. A. (2001). "Yaji da Biko a Auren Bahausha." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Bamgbose, A. (1991). *Language and the Nation: The Language Question in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Bargery, G. P. (1934). *A Hausa-English Dictionary*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Bargery, G.P. (1934). *Hausa-English Dictionary, English-Hausa Vocabulary*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Barlow, J. P., S. Birkets, K. Kelly and M. Slouka (1995). "What Are We Doing On-Line?" In *Harper's*. 291: 35-46.
- Baruah, T. D. (2012). "Effectiveness of Social Media as a Tool of Communication and its Potential for Technology Enabled Connections: A Micro-Level Study." In *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*. Volume 2, Issue 5, Pp. 1-10, ISSN 2250-3153.

- Basu, S. (2019). What are the 5 main network Topologies? Explained with Diagram. Retrieved on 9th August, 2021 from: <https://www.how2shout.com/what-is/what-are-the-5-main-network-topologies-explained-with-diagram.html>.
- BBC (British Broadcasting Company) (2010). "Gagarabadau: Tasirin Intanet kan rayuwar Hausawa." Retrieved on 19th February 2020 from: https://www.bbc.com/hausa/news/story/2010/03/printable/100318_gallerysuperpower.shtml.
- BBC (British Broadcasting Company) (2016). "Yadda Facebook ya Zama Makekiyar Makabarta." An dauko ranar 20 ga watan Fabarairu na shekarar 2020 daga: https://www.bbc.com/hausa/mujalla/vert_fut/2016/08/160822_unstoppable_rise_of_facebook_rise.
- BBC, (British Broadcasting Company) (2020). "Matan Najeriya ba su Iya Soyayya Kamar Turawa ba." An dauko ranar 20 ga watan Fabrairu na shekarar 2020 daga: <https://www.bbc.com/hausa/labarai-51190140>.
- Bourgeois, S. (2016). 11 Types of Networks Explained: VPN, LAN & More. Retrieved from: <https://www.belden.com/blogs/network-types>.
- Bryson, J. (2019). "The Cambridge Platonists in Henry Fielding's Christian Platonic History of Tom Jones." Retrieved on 6th March 2020 from: <https://cprg.hypotheses.org/>.
- Bunza A.M (2006). *Gadon Fedè Al'ada*. Lagos: Tiwal Nigerian Limited.
- Bunza, A. M. (1990). "Hayaki Fid da na Kogo." Kundin digri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Koyar da Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Bunza, A. M. (2004). "Magana da Iskoki ta Bakin Dokinsu." Muƙalar da aka gabatar a taron kara wa juna sani karo na 6 kan Nazarin Harshe da Adabi da Al'adun Hausawa. Cibiyar Nazarin Harsunan Nijeria, Jami'ar Bayero Kano.
- Bunza, A. M. (2005). "Borufiyyah: Tazarar Bori da Rukiyya a Idon Manazarta." Takardar da aka gabatar a taron tattaunawa da kara wa juna sani na musamman da Cibiyar Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya Jami'ar Bayero, Kano ta shirya kan "Bori" da "Rukiyya".
- Bunza, A. M. (2014). "Matakan Kyallaro Asalin Bahausha: (Ruwa Na Kasa Sai Ga Wanda Bai Tona Ba)." Takardar jagora da aka gabatar a taron kara wa juna sani na kasa-da-kasa na farko a Jami'ar Jihar Kaduna, farkashin inuwar Hausa Studies Scholars Association, kulawar Department of Nigerian Languages and Linguistics bisa taken 'The Hausa People, Language and History: Past, Present and Future' ranar 15th - 17th Disamba 2014 a Arewa House, Kaduna.

- Bunza, A. M. (2019). "Hausa da Hausawa a Duniyar Karni na Ashirin da Daya: (Amsa Kiran Majalisar Dinkin Duniya (UN) Ga Ranar Hausa Ta Duniya – Litinin 26 Ogusta, (2019)." Takardar da aka gabatar a bikin Ranar Hausa ta duniya da Majalisar Dinkin Duniya ta keɓe a ranar Litinin 26 ga Ogusta, 2019. An gudanar da taron a Jami'ar Bayero Kano.
- Bunza, A. M. (2019). "Kwarya a Farfajiyar Adabi da Al'adun Bahaushe." A cikin *East African Scholars Journal of Education, Humanities and Literature*, Mujallad na 2, Fitowa na 12, Shafi na 720-727. ISSN 2617-443X.
- Bunza, A. M. (2020). "Tsakanin Kabi Da Sakkwato: Kar Ta San Kar Aljani Ya Taki Wuta (Daular Kabi A Ma'aunin Bakandamiyar Buda Dantanoma)." An dauko ranar 19 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://www.amsoshi.com/2018/12/tsakanin-kabi-da-sakkwato-kar-ta-san.html>.
- Bunza, A.M. (1995). "Magungunan Hausa a Rubuce." Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Koyar da Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Bunza, D. B. (2013). "Zama da Madaukin Kanwa Ke Sa Farin Kai: Nason Baqin Al'adu Cikin Al'adun Auren Hausawa." Muƙalar da aka gabatar a taron kara wa juna sani na kasa a Sashen Harusan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Ummaru Musa 'Yar'aduwa.
- Bunza, U. A. (2008). "Jaridu da Mujallun Hasua: Samuwarsu da Rashin Tabbatuwarsu Daga 1986-2006: Nazari Daga Tarihin Adabin Hausa." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Bunza, U. A. da Atuwu, A. A. (2015). "Adabin Wayo a Tantance Bahaushen Asali (Duba Cikin Adabin Abubakar Imam)." Makalar da aka gabatar a taron kara wa juna sani na kasa da kasa na Farko Kan 'Al'ummar Hausawa, Harshe Da Tarihi: Jiya, Yau Da Kuma Gobe' da Kungiyar Malamai Manazarta Hausa Kaduna 2014 ta shirya wanda za a yi a Sashen Koyar Da Harsunan Nijeriya da Ilimin Harsunan, Jami'ar Jihar Kaduna, Kaduna.
- Clement, J. (2019). "Daily active users of WhatsApp Status 2019." Retrieved on 3rd January, 2020 from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/730306/whatsapp-status-dau/>.
- Clement, J. (2020). "Worldwide digital population as of January 2020." Retrieved on 20th February 2020 from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/617136/digital-population-worldwide/>.

- Dabo, D. (2019). "Shawara a Kan Turanci ga Mawakan Hausa HipHop Masu Tasowa - Daga Dabo Daprof." An da'uko ranar 21 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <http://www.hausatop.com/shawara-akan-turanci-ga-mawakan-hausa-hiphop-masu-tasowa-daga-dabo-daprof/>.
- Dan Zubair, (2017). "Muhimmancin Sunayen Hausawa na Gargajiya a Gargajiyar Bahaushe." An da'uko ranar 18 ga watar Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://gobirmob.com/ha/matsayin-sunayen-hausawa-na-gargajiya-a-gargajiyarsu/>.
- Danladi, S. S. (2013). "Language Policy: Nigeria and the Role of English Language in the 21st Century." In European Scientific Journal June 2013 edition vol.9, No.17 ISSN: Pp: 1857 - 7881.
- Danyaya, M. B. (2007). *Karin Maganar Hausawa*. Sokoto: Makarantar Hausa.
- Dordal, P.L. (2021). An Introduction to Computer Networks (Release 2.0.4). Retrieved on 12th August 2021 from: <http://intronetworks.cs.luc.edu/current2/ComputerNetworks.pdf>.
- Faruk, S. I. (2011). "Tasirin Aikin Gwamnati a Kan Matan Auren Hausawa a Jihar Katsina." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Fraenkel, J. R. & Wallen, N. E. (2003). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education. Fifth ed.* New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Funtuwa, A. I. da Gusau, S. M. (2010). *Al'adun da Dabi'un Hausawa da Fulani*. Kaduna: El-Abbas Printers and Media Concept.
- Furniss, G. (1996). *Language, literature and Hausa popular culture*. London: Edinburgh.
- Gada, N. M. (2014). "Kutsen Bakin Al'adu Cikin Hidimar Aure a Sakkwato." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Galadanci, M. K. M *da wasu* (1990). *Hausa: Don Kananan Makarantun Sakandare 1*. Lagos: Longman Nigeria Plc.
- Garba, S.A. (2013). Auren Zoben Bahaushe da Rediyo a Goshin Karni na 21: (Gidan Rediyon Rahama 97.3 FM da Ginin Tariyya a Mahangar Al'ada). In Bunza, A.M. *da wasu* (editoci). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 707-722. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Gerf, V. G. (2004). "On the Evolution of Internet Technologies." In *Proceedings of the IEEE*, VOL. 92, NO. 9. DOI: 10.1109/JPROC.2004.832974.

- Gerson, L. (2013). "Was Plato a Platonist?" In *From Plato to Platonism* (pp. 3-33). Cornell University Press. Retrieved on 7th March 2020, from: www.jstor.org/stable/10.7591/j.ctt32b4gd.5.
- Gerson, L. (ND). "What is Platonism?" Retrieved on 5th March, 2020 from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/236825147_What_is_Platonism.
- Gerson, P. L. (2005). "What is Platonism?" In *Journal of the History of Philosophy*, Vol. 42, Pp: 253-257. DOI: 10.1353/hph.2005.0136.
- Getso, H.A. (2013). Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa a Wannan Zamni: Rawar Da Kafofin Yada Labarai Suke Takawa Wajen Bunkasa Ko Ruguza Al'adun Hausawa a Yau. In Bunza, A.M. et al (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 607-618. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Gobir, Y. A. & Sani, A-U. (2017). "The Jinn, Women Vulnerabilities and The Act of Healings in The Hausa Communities Of 21st Century." In *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, Volume 23, Issue 1, ver. 5 (January. 2018) PP 67-73 e-ISSN: 2279-0837, p-ISSN: 2279-0845.
- Gobir, Y. A. & Sani, A-U. (2018). "Traces of Supernatural in Hausa Oral Songs: A Special Reference to Dr. Mamman Shata." In *International Journal of Recent Advances in Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 05, Issue 04, pp 3755-3760. ISSN: 2350-0743.
- Gobir, Y. A. & Sani, A-U. (2019). "Witchcraft in the Light of Hausa Culture and Religion." In *Academic Journal of Current Research*. Vol. 6, No.12; Pp., 23-30. ISSN (2343-403X); p-ISSN 3244-5621. Available at: <http://cird.online/AJCR/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/CIRD-AJCR-19-12033-final.pdf>.
- Gobir, Y. A. (2002) "Iskoki a Idon 'Yan bori da Masu Rukiyya." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usamu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Gobir, Y. A. (2012). "Tasirin Iskoki ga Cutuka da Magungunan Hausawa." Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Gobir, Y. A. (2012). "Tasirin Iskoki ga Cututtuka da Magungunan Hausawa." Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Cibiyar Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Guiji, I. I. (2006). "Modern Information Technology: An Assessment of the Role of Hausa on the Internet." A masters dissertation submitted to the Department of African Languages and Cultures, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

- Guibi, I.I. da Bakori A.D. (2013). Rawar da Kafafen Yada Labarai Suke Takawa Wajen Ruguza Al'adun Hausawa a Yau. In Bunza, A.M. *et al* (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 619-628. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Gusau, G. U. (2012). *Bukukuwan Hausawa*. Gusau: Ol-faith Prints.
- Gusau, S. M. (2010). "Al'adun Hausawa a Takaice." A cikin Funtua, A. I. da Gusau, S. M. (editoci) *Al'adu da Dabi'un Hausawa da Fulani*. Kaduna: El-Abbas Printers and Media Concepts.
- Gusau, U. G. (2012). *Bukukuwan Hauswa*. Gusau: Ol-Faith Prints.
- Gwarjo, Y. T. *da wasu* (2005). *Aure a Jihar Katsina*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Hassan, B. Y. (2013). "Nason Bakin Al'adu Kan Al'adun Aure da Haihuwa da Mutuwa na Hausawa." Mukalar da aka gabatar a taron kara wa juna sani na kasa a Sashen Harusan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Umbaru Musa 'Yar'aduwa.
- Hausa Top, (2020). "About Us." Retrieved on 18th April 2020 from: <http://www.hausatop.com/about-us/>.
- Hutu Dole, (2018). "Game da Hutudole." An dauko ranar 18 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: https://hutudole.com/dangane-da-hutudole_7/.
- Ibrahim, M. S. (1982). "Dangantakar Al'ada da Addini Tasirin Musulunci kan Rayuwar Hausawa ta Gargajiya." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Ibrahim, M. S. (1985). "Auren Hausawa: Gargajiya Da Musulunci." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Ibrahim, M. S. (1985). *Auren Hausawa: Gargajiya da Musulunci*. Kano: Shoguna Commercial Press.
- Ibrahim, S. M. (1981). *Auren Hausawa*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press.
- Internet Live Stats, (2020). "Home Page". Retrieved on 20th February 2020 from: <https://www.internetlivestats.com/>.
- Isah, S. (2013). Gudummuwar Gidan Rediyon Companion FM 104.5 Mhz Katsina Wajen Bunkasa Al'adun Hausawa. In Bunza, A.M. *da wasu* (editoci). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 699-706. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Java Point (ND). Computer Network Types. Retrived on 20th August, 2021 from: <https://www.javatpoint.com/types-of-computer-network>.

- Jayasekara, A. H. D. (2015). "Facebook Users and Undergraduates (Specially Reference to Selected Universities in Sri Lanka)." In *International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology*, Vol.: 2, No. 5 , Pp. 78-85. ISSN: 2313-3759.
- John, G. W. (1998). "A Definition of Theory: Research Guidelines for Different Theory-Building Research Methods in Operations Management." In *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol.: 16 Pp: 361-385. Retrieved on 22nd February 2020 from: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.470.4555&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.
- Kaina, H.M. (2019). Matar Shugaban Najeriya Ta Maida Martani Akan Jita Jitar Mijinta Zai Sake Aure. An da'uko ranar 24 ga watan Disamba, shekarar 2021 daga: <https://www.voahausa.com/a/matar-shugaban-najeriya-ta-maida-martani-akan-jita-jitar-mijinta-zai-sake-aure/5122106.html>.
- Kano Online, (2020). "Fadar Mai Martaba Sarkin Katagum Dake Azare." An da'uko ranar 18 ga watar Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <http://azareonline.com/Home>.
- Keary T. (2021). Network Topology: 6 Network Topologies Explained & Compared. Retrieved on 12 August 2021 from: <https://www.comparitech.com/net-admin/network-topologies-advantages-disadvantages/>.
- Kiyawa, H.A. (2013). Tsokaci a Kan Wasu Matsalolin Finafinan Hausa Wajen Bata Tarbiyya. In Bunza, A.M. et al (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 661-668. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Kleinrock, L. (2010). "An Early History of the Internet." In Schwartz, M. (ed). *History of Communications*. IEEE Communications Magazine August, Issue: August 2020.
- Korkmaz, M., Celebi, N. & Yucel, A. S. (2014). "Practical Review of the Place of Social Networks in our Daily Life and Their Effect on Today's Youth." In *International Journal of Academic Research Part B*; 6(1), Pp. 250-261. DOI: 10.7813/2075-4124.2014/6-1/B.35.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). "Determining Sample Size for Research Activities." In *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, Vol.: 30, Issue: 3, Pp: 607-610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>.
- Leiner, B. M. et al (1997). "The Past and Future History of the Internet: The Science of the Future Technology." In *Communications of the ACM*, Vol.: 40, No. 2, Pp. 102-108.
- Magaji, F. Y. (2018). "Tasirin Zamananci a Kan Zumuncin Al'ummar Hausawa." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Koyar da Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.

- Mahmud, A. M. (1997). *Hanyoyin Gane Sihiri da Warware Shi*. Kano: Burji Publishers & Co.
- Mai'aduwa, A.A. (2013). Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa a Yau: Nazari a Kan Finafinan Hausa. In Bunza, A.M. *da wasu* (editoci). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 723-730. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Maikwari, H. U. (2020). "Wasu Al'adun Hausawa Cikin Rubutattun Wafofin Hausa." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a matakin jarabawa ta cikin gida a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Makuwana, A. A. (2011). "Yaduwar Harshen Hausa Cikin Intanet." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Malumfashi, I. & Nahuce, M. I. (2014). *Kamusun Karin Maganar Hausa*. Kaduna: Garkuwa Media Services.
- McCombes, S. (2020). "How to Write a Literature Review." Retrieved on 26th March 2020 from: <https://www.scribbr.com/dissertation/literature-review/>.
- Meinwald, C. C. (2020). "Plato (Greek Philosopher)." In Encyclopedia Britannica. Retrieved on 17th March 2020 from: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Plato>.
- Morakinyo, O. (2015). "Language Policy in Nigeria: Problems, Prospects and Perspectives." In *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Vol.: 5*, No. 9. Retrieved on 17th February 2020 from: www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol_5.
- Muhammad, D. (2011). "Hausa a Duniyar Yau: Tasirin Game Duniya Kan Harshen Hausa." A cikin Yalwa, L. D. *da wasu* (editoci). *Studies in Hausa Language Literature and Culture - Proceedings of the Sixth Hausa International Conference - Center for the Study of Nigerian Languages, Bayero University, Kano, 15th - 17th December 2004*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Limited.
- Muhammad, T. A. (1998). *Aure Da Buki a Kasar Hausa*. Kano: Dan Sarkin Kura Publishers Ltd.
- Mukoshy, J. I. (2015). "Keɓaɓɓun Kalmomin Intanet da Amfaninsu a Nazarin Hausa." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.

- Mukoshy, J. I. (2016). "Kebaɓɓun Kalmomin Intanet da Amfaninsu ga Bunkasa Tattalin Arzikin Kasa." Mukalar da aka gabatar a taron kara wa juna sani kan Matsayin Harshe da Tarihi da Addini Wajen Bunkasa Cigaba da Haɗin Kai da Tsaro a Nijeriya, Tsangayar Fasaha da Nazarin Addinin Musulunci ta Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Mukoshy, J. I. da Umar, S. (2014). "Jagora ga Amfani da Intanet don Bunkasa Harshen Hausa." Mukalar da aka gabatar a taron kasa da kasa na farko kan Karatun Hausa a Karni na Ashirin da Daya (Krn. 21) a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Musa, M. B. (2019). "Sana'ar Kiwo a Kasar Hausa." An dauko ranar 17 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020 daga: <https://www.alummarhaus.com.ng/2019/11/sanaar-kiwo-a-kasar-hausa.html>.
- Mwami, J.A.L. (2013). The Roles of Films in Moral Decadence Among Hausa Youth and the Emergence of Kauraye Miscreant Activities in Katsina. In Bunza, A.M. et al (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 685-698. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Nadama, G. (1977). The Rise and Collapes of a Hausa State: A Social and Political History of Zamfara." Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University.
- Nasir, I. (2009). "Gabatar da Katun na Hausa a Kan Tatsuniyar Gizo da 'Baure." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- Newman, P. (2007). A Hausa-English Dictionary. United States: Yale University Press.
- Nie, N. H. (2001). "Sociability, Interpersonal Relations, and the Internet: Reconciling Conflicting Findings." In *American Behavioral Scientist*, 45(3), pp: 426-437.
- Nie, N. H., Hillygus, D.S., & Erbring. L. (2002). "Internet Use, Interpersonal Relations and Sociability: A Time Diary Study." In Wellman, B. & C. Haythornthwaite (eds.), *Internet and Everyday Life*. pp. 215-243. London: Blackwell.
- Ogbonna, N. A. (2013). "Language in National Development: The Nigerian Perspective." In Ndimele, M. & Yakasai H. M. (ed) *Language, Literature and Culture in a Multilingual Society*. Port Harcourt: M & J Grand Orbit Communications Ltd.

- Ohio Department of Taxation, (2004). New Definition of Food. Retrieved on the 20th of August 2021 from: http://tzhcpas.com/wp-content/uploads/2011/01/streamlined_sales_tax_food_BR.pdf.
- Ojua, T. (2019). "Can I Use Two or More Theories to Support my Research Model?" Retrieved on 22 February, 2020 from: https://www.researchgate.net/post/Can_I_use_Two_or_more_theories_to_support_my_research_model.
- Olatuja, O. (2016). "Revisiting the Question of the National Language in Nigeria by Olatuja Oloyede." Retrieved on 16th February 2020 from: <http://oloyede001.yu.tl/revisiting-the-question-of-the-national.xhtml>.
- Owusu-Acheaw, M. & Larson, A. G. (2015). "Use of Social Media and its Impact on Academic Performance of Tertiary Institution Students: A Study of Students of Koforidua Polytechnic, Ghana." In *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol. 6, No. 6, 2015 ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper), ISSN 2222-288X (Online), Pp.: 94-101.
- Pandey, K. K., Shukla, P. K. & Pradhan, N. (2015). "Internet Search Engine: A Comparative and Performance Evaluation of Web Search Engine and Meta Search Engine." In *Proceedings of International Conference on Emerging Research in Computer & Software Engineering*. ISSN: 2393-9931. Retrieved on 17th March 2020 from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Kamlesh_Pandey2/publication/321685207_Internet_Search_Engine_A_Comparative_and_Performance_Evaluation_of_Web_Search_Engine_and_Meta_Search_Engine/links/5a2ad8af0f7e9b63e538c79c/Internet-Search-Engine-A-Comparative-and-Performance-Evaluation-of-Web-Search-Engine-and-Meta-Search-Engine.pdf.
- Pena, I. G. (2018). "Platonism as a Philosophical Method." In *Athens Journal of Humanities & Arts - Volume: 5, Issue 1 - Pages 45-60*. DOI: = 10.30958/ajha.5.1.3.
- Philip, J. J. (2001). *Hausa*. Netherlands: John Benjamins Publishing.
- Press, G. (2015). "A Very Short History of the Internet and the Web." Retrieved on 18th March 2020 from: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/gilpress/2015/01/02/a-very-short-history-of-the-internet-and-the-web-2/#12bc09017a4e>.
- Rambo, I. (2007). "Nazari Kan Wasu Keɓaɓɓun Al'adun Auren Hausawa da na Dakarkari." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Rashid, A.R. (2019). Jita-jitan auren Buhari da Sadiya: Masallacin Aso Villa ta cika yau. An dauko ranar 24 ga watan Disamba, shekarar 2021 daga: <https://hausa.legit.ng/1265641-jita-jitan-auren-buhari-da-sadiya-masallacin-asovilla-ta-cika-yau.html>.

- Romualdo, P. & Alessandro, V. (2007). *Evolution and Structure of the Internet: A Statistical Physics Approach*. New Yourk: Cambridge University Press.
- Rumbun Ilimi, (ND). Abinci. An cirato ranar 20 ga watan Ogusta, shekarar 2021, daga: <https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng/Abinci.html#gsc.tab=0>.
- Sa'id, B. *da wasu* (editoci) (2006). *Kamusun Hausa na Jami'ar Bayero*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press.
- Sallau, B.A.S. (2009). Sana'ar Wanzanci da Sauye-Sauyen Zamani Jiya da Yau. Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero.
- Sallau, B.A.S. (2010). *Magani A Sha A Yi Wanka A Buwaya*. Kaduna: M.A. Najju Professional Printers.
- Sallau, B.A.S. (ND). HAU 214: Hausa Trades and Crafts. Department of Languages, Faculty of Arts, National Open University of Nigeria, Jabi, Abuja.
- Sambo, M. M. (2009). "Kebaɓɓun Kalmomin Kwamfuta." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsuna da Al'adun Afirka, Jami'ar Ahmadu Bello, Zariya.
- Sani, A-U. and Umar, M. M. (2018). "Global Growing Impact of Hausa and the Need for its Documentation." In *Contemporary Journal of Language and Literature*, Vol.: 1 No.1, Pp.: 16-34. Available at: <http://sgpicanada.com/index.php/CJLL/issue/download/1/Abu-Ubaida%20Sani%20and%20Muhammad%20Mustapha%20Umar>.
- Sani, A-U., Buba, U. & Mohammad, I. (2019). "Wanda Ya Tuna Bara...: Bida da Tanadi a Tsakanin Hausawa Matasa a Yau." In *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol-1, Iss-2 pp-44-50. 44. ISSN: 2706-901X (Print), 2707- 2576 (Online). Available at: https://gajrc.com/media/articles/GAJHSS_12_44-50.pdf.
- Sarkin Gulbi, A. (2014). "Magani a Ma'auin Karin Magana." Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Sarkin Gulbi, A. (2014). "Magani a Ma'aunin Karin Magana." Kundin digiri na uku wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Seibert, U. (2017). "Greetings to the Followers of this Group." Retrieved on 20th Afril 2020 from: <https://hausasonline.wordpress.com>.

- Shehu, I. (2013). Gudummuwar Wasannin Hausa na Rediyo Wajen Bunkasa Al'adun Hausawa: Tsokaci Daga Wasan Kwaikwayo na 'Duniya Budurwar Wawa' da 'Jami'iyar Jatau Na Albarkawa.' In Bunza, A.M. et al (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 629-644. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Shehu, M. da Aliyu, L. (2019). "Tasirin Wayar Salula Wajen Gurbata Rayuwar Hausawa a Yau." A cikin *East African Scholars Journal of Education, Humanities and Literature*, Vol - 2, Issue - 12, Pp 706-711. ISSN: 2617-443X.
- Shehu, M. da Rambo, R. A. (2019). "Shafin Zumunta na Was'af (Whatsapp): Tasirinsa ga Lalacewar Tarbiyyar 'Ya'yan Hausawa." A cikin *EAS Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, Vol. 1, Issue 6, Pp 357-362. ISSN: 2663-0958.
- Shehu, M. da Sani, A-U. (2020). "Zamantakewar Hausawa Jiya Da Yau." An dauko ranar 17 ga watan Afirulu, shekarar 2020 daga <https://www.amsoshi.com/2019/02/zamantakewar-hausawa-jiya-da-yau.html>.
- Siddiqui, S. & Singh, T. (2016). "Social Media its Impact with Positive and Negative Aspects." In *International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research*. Vol. 5, Issue 2, Pp. 71 - 75, ISSN:- 2319-8656.
- Strickland, J. (2020). "How did the Internet Start?" Retrieved on 17th March 2020 from: <https://computer.howstuffworks.com/internet/basics/internet-start.htm>.
- Sulaiman, A.I. (2013). Ta'addancin Fyade a Finafinan Hausa: Tsokaci Kan Tasirin Finafinan Hausa ga Tabarbarewar Al'adu a Yau. In Bunza, A.M. da wasu (editoci). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 731-742. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Tambuwal, A. Y. (2018). "Manunin Tarbiyya a Karin Maganar Bahausha." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Thein, K. (2018). "Soul and Incorporeality in Plato." In *Eirene Sudia Graeca Et Latina, LIV, 2018*, Pp. 53-95. Centre for Classical Studies Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague.
- Tsaure, M. B. & Sani, A-U. (2016). "The National Question: Language Policy and the Quest for a Common Language in Nigeria." Being a paper presented at the international conference of the Faculty of Arts and Islamic Studies, on The Role of the Arts on Development held at Musa Abdullahi Auditorium, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria.

- Tukur, A. (1988). "Nazari a Kan Cututtukan da Suka Shafi Fatar Jiki da Magungunansu a Bahaushiyar Al'ada." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Koyar da Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Bayero, Kano.
- UF College of Journalism and Communications, (ND). "What is Theory?" Retrieved on 22nd February, 2020 from: <http://faculty.jou.ufl.edu/mleslie/spring96/theory.html>.
- Umar, B.U. (2013). Nason Zamananci Wajen Zaɓen Mijin Aure: Tsokaci a Kan Wata Addu'ar 'Yammata Ta Cikin Wayar Salula. In Bunza, A.M. *et al* (eds). *Excerpts of International Seminar on The Deterioration of Hausa Culture (Tabarbarewar Al'adun Hausawa)*, Pp 669-684. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Umar, M. M. (2012). "Nazarin Sakon GSM a Wayar Salular Hausawa." Kundin digiri na biyu wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Usman, B. B. da Bunza, D. B. (2020). "Fina-Finan Hausa a Mahangar Al'umma: Gyara ko Barna?" A cikin *East African Scholars Journal of Education, Humanities and Literature*, Vol. 3, Issue 3. Shafi 52-61. ISSN: 2617-443X. DOI: 10.36349/EASJEHL.2020.v03i03.010.
- Weinstein, S. (2016). "History & Technologies of the Internet." A lecture note delivered between 22nd September to 13th October 2016 every on Thursdays 7:30pm – 9:00pm at WEA Community Room, Lincoln Towers University.
- Wellman, B. (2001) "Physical Place and Cyber-Place: The Rise of Networked Individualism." In *International Journal for Urban and Regional Research*, 25: 22752.
- Wellman, B. *et al* (2002). "Examining the Internet in Everyday Life." Keynote address (given by Barry Wellman) to the Euricom Conference on e-Democracy, Nijmegen, Netherlands.
- Wikiwand, (ND). Hausawa. An cirato ranar 20 ga watan Ogusta, shekarar 2021, daga: <https://www.wikiwand.com/ha/Hausawa>.
- Yahaya, S. U. (2020). "Damben Hausawa a Zamanance." Kundin digiri na biyu da aka gabatar a matakin jarabawar cikin gida (Internal Defense) a Sashen Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- 'Yartsakuwa, U. D. (2017). "Zumunci a Yanar Gizo: Harshen Sadarwa Tsakanin Matasa a Shafin Whatsapp." Kundin digiri na farko wanda aka gabatar a Sashen Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya, Jami'ar Usmanu Danfodiyo, Sakkwato.
- Yunusa, Y. (1989). *Hausa a Dunkule*. Kano: Triumph.

Yusuf, L.M.S. (2017). Tasirin camfe-camfen Hausawa cikin tarbiyyarsu (Na daya). An cirato ranar 20 ga watan Ogusta, shekarar 2021, daga: <https://bakandamiya.com/blogs/865/143/tasirin-camfe-camfen-hausawa-cikin-tarbiyyarsu-na-daya>.

KAFAFEN INTANET DA AKA ZIYARTA

<http://azareonline.com/>

<http://duniyarso.blogspot.com/>

<http://hausadictionary.com/>

<http://kanoonline.com/>

<http://katsinaposthausa.com/>

<http://tsangayaradabi.blogspot.com/>

<http://tzhcpas.com>

<http://www.dandali.com/>

<http://www.gumel.com/>

<http://www.haiman.com.ng/>

<http://www.hausang.com/>

<http://www.hausatop.com/>

<http://www.teachyourselfhausa.com/>

<http://zahramuhammadmahmud.blogspot.com/>

<https://abinci.com/>

<https://computer.howstuffworks.com>

<https://cprg.hypotheses.org/>

<https://dealdey.com.cutestat.com/>

<https://gidannovels.guidetricks.com/>

<https://gobirmob.com/ha/>

<https://hausa.leadership.ng/>

<https://hausaonline.wordpress.com/>

<https://hausaweddings.com/>

<https://hutudole.com/>

<https://jaridarhausa.com/>

<https://makarantarhaus.com/>
<https://managarcia.com/>
<https://parktelonline.com/>
<https://qalubale.news.blog/>
<https://slot.ng/>
<https://www.6pm.com/>
<https://www.allsaints.com/>
<https://www.alummarhaus.com.ng/>
<https://www.amazon.com/>
<https://www.amsoshi.com/>
<https://www.anntaylor.com/>
<https://www.arewafresh.com.ng/>
<https://www.arewanishadi.com/>
<https://www.arewarmu.com.ng/>
<https://www.arewaswag.com.ng/>
<https://www.asos.com/>
<https://www.babansadik.com/>
<https://www.bakandamiya.com/>
<https://www.barnesandnoble.com/>
<https://www.batsapost.com/>
<https://www.britannica.com/art/Platonic-criticism>
<https://www.comparitech.com>
<https://www.forbes.com>
<https://www.hausagett.com.ng/>
<https://www.hausaloded.com/>
<https://www.hausatrust.com/>

<https://www.hausawasite.com.ng/>
<https://www.internetlivestats.com/>
<https://www.isyaku.com/>
<https://www.jakandanfasaha.com/>
<https://www.javatpoint.com>
<https://www.jumia.com.ng/>
<https://www.kara.com.ng/>
<https://www.konga.com/>
<https://www.madubiya.com/>
<https://www.muryarhausa24.com.ng/>
<https://www.muryaryanci.com/>
<https://www.ray-ban.com/usa>
<https://www.rumbunilimi.com.ng/>
<https://www.statista.com/>
<https://www.urbanoutfitters.com/>
<https://www.wikihausa.com.ng/>
<https://www.wikiwand.com>
<https://www.yoox.com/us>

WADANDA AKA YI HIRA DA SU

Suna	Tsokaci
Prof. Aliyu Muhammad Bunza	Farfesa
Prof. Bashir Aliyu Sallau	Farfesa
Ass. Prof. Abdullahi I. S. S.	Dan galadiman farfesa
Ass. Prof. Yakubu Aliyu Gobir	Malami a jami'a
Malam Aliyu Muhammad	Malami a jami'a
Dr. Abdullahi Isah Muhammad	Malami a jami'a
Mr. Uwe Seibert	Mai kafafen Hausa Online da Karin Magana
Sa'idu Umar Yahaya	Kasuwancin Waya
Lawan Dalha	Mai kafar Bakandamiya
Bashir Ahmed	Mai kafar Hutu Dole
Abubakar Muhammad Tsangarwa	Mai kafar Rumbun Ilimi
Bello Muhammad	Mai kafar Makarantar Hausa
Shehu Auwal	Mataimakin mai kafar Amsoshi
Mohammed Atabo	Mai kafar Gidan Karatu
Zainab Sani	Mai sana'ar sayar da abinci
Abdulrahman Muhammad Manga	Masanin Intanet

RATAYE

Rataye na 1: Wakar Soshial Midiya Duniyar Matasa ta Dan'iro Katsina

Amshi: Soshial midiya duniyar matasa,
Mu yada alkairi kar mu yada zamba.

1. Soshial midiya duniyar matasa,
A duniyar catin yanzu ta yi rassa,
Ya sa zukatan wasu sun shagalta wasa,
Ya sa wadansu a hansen su rinka gasa,
Maza da 'yammata kanku zan yi casa,
Har da matan gidan ma ba sa ki ji ba.
2. Gudu muke ta faman yi ba muts tsaya ba,
Muna saman wani tsauni ba mus sani ba,
Dakin duhu mun fita ba da fittila ba,
Ana ta nisa dawa ba da jin kira ba,
Ana shiga rijiya ba da shawara ba,
Gun fita ya ake? Ban ji mun sani ba.
3. A yada alkairi kar a yada zamba,
A nan ake mai da kadan ta zamma babba,
A nan ake haddasa ki a rai da gaba,
A nan ake tarbiyyar da ban fadi ba,
A nan ake wargaza tarbiyyar su baba,
Duk a nan midiya in ba kus sani ba.
4. Wadansu ko sun zo don su yo zumunta,
Wadansu na yi domin su yo abota,
Su kare addini ko a gyara bauta,
Su sanya ayoyi har ko ak karanta,
Domin a wanke duka zuciya kasanta,
Wassu na yin hakan midiya ku duba.
5. Wadansu ko lamarin ba ni son tunawa,
Irin abin da idanu suke ganewa,
Wadansu hoto na tsiraici za su sawa,
A midiya nan ne dandalin gwadawa,
Kowa irin mai halinsa zai kulawa,
Wa ya ce watta rana ba sa hade ba?

6. Abin takaici ma har da ma amare,
Su samu kato catin suke a tare,
Su kama yin soyayya kwarai a tare,
Har ma ta ce masa honi su canza yare,
Da iggiyar aure ukku kanta daure,
Shi miji gwangwani kun ga bai sani ba.
7. A dole matarka waya ka ba ta babba,
A kan hakan ka hana sai ku rinka gaba,
Da kai bayanin ka cocilan ta karba,
Sai ta fake maka kallo ba ta bari ba,
Kewarka in ba ka nan ba ta sake ba,
Me ya sa Alkur'ani ba kya rife ba.
8. Sannan batun 'yammata da 'yan samari,
Babbar waya kadada ta sakan barar da gari,
Su dai kawai catin shi suke ma fari,
Shi ne yake kai su cikin jakar magori,
A kama labari sun barar da gari,
Duk a nan midiya ban ji kun musa ba.
9. Ga 'yan siyasa ita midiya ku duba,
Nan ne wurin jawo tsokana da zamba,
Nan ne wurin ce ma gwaninka bai iya ba,
Nan ne wurin nuna abin da bai yi kyau ba,
Nan ne wurin haddasa gardama da gaba,
Dandali ne ake ba na fa'ida ba.
10. Batu na alkairi ba a son azawa,
Batu na sharri shi ne abin gwadawa,
'Yan mintuka ka gani ya yi zagayawa,
Duk duniya kowa za ya yo ganowa,
Sirrin waninka a nan ka yi bayyanawa,
Babu da-na-sani tun da bai gama ba.
11. Idan ina wakar wassu za su tsargu,
Barai a ce an sanyo kidan kalangu,
Ga wanda bai da fahimta ko za ni zagu,
Tuna tunanin rushe musu katangu,
Ina nufin wassu su zam kamar guragu,
Ni ko Dan'iya ban yo nufin hakan ba.

12. Dan Kattsinawa ne wanda yay yi wake,
A da ina barci yanzu ga ni farke,
Ku gane noma shi ne ake a duke,
Ku san batun tafiya na wurin fatake,
Da an yi nisa yaro ka gan shi d'auke,
Don ba zai juriya ne da taffiyar ba.
13. Nai godiyata tari a gun masoya,
Dan'iro mai waka ba ni kin masoya,
Ni dan Mutan Katsinawa muna da kunya,
Gami da tarbiyya gunsu ne na koya,
Lambar waya in na fade ta sai ku juya,
Gaisuwa ni da ku don ba ta katse ba.

Rataye na 2: Tsarin Zaben Samfuri na Krejcie & Morgan (1970)

A duba Krejcie & Morgan (1970) domin samun karin bayani game da yadda ake amfani da wannan tsari na zaɓen samfuri.

<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>S</i>
10	10	220	140	1200	291
15	14	230	144	1300	297
20	19	240	148	1400	302
25	24	250	152	1500	306
30	28	260	155	1600	310
35	32	270	159	1700	313
40	36	280	162	1800	317
45	40	290	165	1900	320
50	44	300	169	2000	322
55	48	320	175	2200	327
60	52	340	181	2400	331
65	56	360	186	2600	335
70	59	380	191	2800	338
75	63	400	196	3000	341
80	66	420	201	3500	346
85	70	440	205	4000	351
90	73	460	210	4500	354
95	76	480	214	5000	357
100	80	500	217	6000	361
110	86	550	226	7000	364
120	92	600	234	8000	367
130	97	650	242	9000	368
140	103	700	248	10000	370
150	108	750	254	15000	375
160	113	800	260	20000	377
170	118	850	265	30000	379
180	123	900	269	40000	380
190	127	950	274	50000	381
200	132	1000	278	75000	382
210	136	1100	285	100000	384

Note.—*N* is population size. *S* is sample size.

Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970

Rataye na 3: Tsarin Intanet Mai Bin Sambai

Wannan shi ne tsarin hadakar intanet na farko. A nan, sabis na tafiya ne kawai ta alkibla guda. Zai tafi misali daga kwamfuta ta ɗaya, zuwa ta biyu, zuwa ta uku... Ba zai iya tashi daga ta ɗaya ya tsallake ta biyu domin ya je ta uku ba.

Madogara: Romualdo & Alessandro, (2007: 3)

Rataye na 4: Tsarin Intanet Maizobe

Wannan shi ne mataki ne biyu a ci gaban al'amarin intanet. A wannan mataki, sabis ɗin intanet na zagayawa. Misali idan akwai kwamfutoci biyar da ke haɗe da sabis ɗin, to sabis ɗin zai riƙa zagayawa (1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 > 1 > 2 ...).

Madogara: Romualdo & Alessandro, (2007: 3)

Rataye Na 5: Tsarin Intanet Mai Zubin Tauraro

A wannan tsari kwamfutoci na iya tura sakonni a tsakaninsu ta hanyar kwamfuta guda da ke tsakiya a matsayin jekada. Idan akwai kwamfutoci goma, ɗaya daga ciki (misali 10) za ta kasance a tsakiya. Duk kwamfutar da za ta tura sako, sai sakon ya bi ta cikin 10 kafin ya kai inda ake son ya je. Misali, $1 > 10 > 7$; $5 > 10 > 3$; $2 > 10 > 1$; da sauransu.

Madogara: Basu, (2019: 1)

Rataye Na 6: Tsarin Intanet Mai Zubin Jigida

Wannan shi ne tsarin intanet wanda ke ba wa kowace kwamfuta damar tura sako zuwa 'yar uwarta kai tsaye. Idan akwai kwamfutoci 10, kowace kwamfuta za ta iya tura wa 'yar uwarta sako kai tsaye. Misali, 1 > 9; 10 > 7; 4 > 2; da sauskansu.

Madogara: Keary, (2021: 1)

Rataye Na 7: Kididdigar Maziyarta Kafar *Hutu Dole* na ranar 8 ga watan Afirilu, shekarar 2020.

A wannan rana, sama da mutane dubu goma (10,000) ne suka ziyarci kafar.

Rataye Na 8: Kididdigar Maziyarta Kafar *Bakandamiya* Ranar 20/04/2020. A wannan rana, waɗanda suka ziyarci kafar sun hauwa dubu arba'in da huɗu (>44,000).

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Rataye Na 9: Sabis Din Karamin Wuri (LAN)

Mutum na iya haɗa na'urori daban-daban da yake amfani da su a kan sabis guda. Zai iya amfani da su duka a lokaci guda.

Madogara: Java Point (ND)